

**The World “Shattering”:
What’s In Store for the Geopolitical System to Come?**
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For the Publisher

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University of Belgrade – Faculty of Security Studies

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Mihajlo Kopanja and Nuno Morgado
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**Proceedings from the 6th International Workshop on Geopolitics and
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PANEL I

THE SYSTEM, THE REGION, THE ACTOR

Chair: Zoran Jeftić

Discussant: Nuno Morgado

**Where the World ‘shatters’?
Some reflections on geopolitics of mobilities in
the contemporary world**

María Lois¹

Abstract:

The aim of this contribution is to visit a debate, presenting some questions for discussion and exchange. It does not pretend to be a lecture, or to answer questions about contemporary geopolitics. Furthermore, it pretends to be a medium to discuss some political assumptions and social practices that may help to understand the socio-spatial configuration of present and future world politics.

In that way, I will start by locating this text theoretically, followed by some general readings on the geopolitical context. One of the challenges underlined in the contemporary geopolitics, that of mobilities, will be addressed in the COVID 19 and Russia-Ukraine war general scenario, in order to think how the making of geopolitical communities is tangled to the normality/exceptionality approach to mobilities.

Key words:

geopolitics, mobilities, containment of mobility, COVID-19

¹ University Complutense de Madrid

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Introduction

This manuscript is part of a geopolitical reading, that is, a spatial approach to power relations at the global scale. These power relations mark and define international space. And even today, to talk of Geopolitics as a field of research remains relatively controversial; precisely, because of the associations between the practice of geopolitics and various political projects and intellectual influences; from Ratzel's spatial determinism to the *Geopolitik* of Haushofer and the Institute for Geopolitical Studies in Munich, passing by Augusto Pinochet's Alpaca plan or the geopolitics of a militarized globalization of Thomas Barnett (Lois 2022, 5-6).

However, the use of geopolitics to justify political projects or to argue about hegemonic ways of seeing the world does not invalidate its object of study, nor does it weaken its transcendence, nor, above all, its tradition as an academic discipline. In any case, the differences in the conceptual definition of the term are precisely one of the keys to understanding the constant renewal of the discipline. So, geopolitics here is assumed as a re-reading, a re-visioning of the arguments, visions and geographical practices on which the space of world politics is performed and reproduced.

Now, the spatial part in the concept of geopolitics would not be equivalent to generate an instruction manual on how to dominate a space; or to understand space as a passive and static element of world politics; or as the support for a political project. But as a discursive field where the meanings of space are constructed from the political, academic, popular or any other plane of representation. Without ceasing to work with the arguments and logics of the elites, approaches to other hierarchies, other institutionalities, other voices allow us to question binary geographies, and open debates on power relations assumed as perpetual or introduce multiscale perspectives in a field that cyclically hatches to the rhythm of global upheavals. And, precisely for this reason, asking questions about what is assumed as global from different spaces, scales, networks, agencies... or working with everyday practices and representations and with the possible lines of escape that this allows are still absolutely necessary exercises (Lois 2022, 6).

The 'Shattering' Context

Understanding geopolitics as a discursive field, then, speaks to us of plans of representation and power relations in the production of that global scale. And questions as the COVID-19 pandemics in 2020, or the war between Russia and Ukraine bring attention to the cyclical changes and 'shattering' processes that renew understandings and assumptions underpinning the modern geopolitical imagination (Agnew 2005). Those may be read as symptoms, not as causes, of a multidimensional crisis with diverse aspects already started in the 2000's first decade.

The financial one, in 2008-2009, when the bank system breakdown affected the core and periphery states, pointing to the shrinking of the world GDP around 3% by the end of 2009, with the core countries suffering a reduction of almost 4%, while periphery countries slowed their growth to just under 4% per year (IMF 2023).

The eco-social crises, or the evidence that contemporary capitalism is not compatible with ecology and sustainability. Climate emergency and global warming are key in the creation of the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, UN), the 2030 agenda etc. But these developments and other international and global governance organizations are questioned, by their unequal reactions to the regression in rights and democracies, to war conflicts and inequality persisting in the global South.

The COVID 19 pandemics, an unprecedented crisis that defined global health crisis of our time, since it affected every continent (except Antarctica), in diverse manners. Starting in 2019 December, officially proclaimed by WHO (World Health Organization) in 2020 and ended in 2023, it shows an unofficial date of 20-30 millions of people deaths that underline, in an overwhelming manner, the social determinants of health and the pandemic's impact.

The military crisis, today centered in the war between Russia and Ukraine, probably because of European location and implication in the conflict. Some other continue (Yemen, Afghanistan, South Sudan etc.) out of the media and general attention. There is nothing inevitable in the outbreaks of war; unfortunately, they are not anomalies, burdens of the past but continuation of conflicts acquiring a war moment, final expression of scale practices in social and political constructions of the enemy, with a militaristic but also patriarchal background: as Eliane Brum wrote "this is another war of white men clinging to the past and their patriarchal values [...] while the world is configured by the carbon economy" (El País 2022). Militarization and belligerence have continuity on various scales, from the culture of cancellation in various events and academic circles, to the daily personalization of the enemy in nationalities, social psychologies and even meals that derive in the emotional demonization of the Other. All this complicates the possibility of contemplating other logics to resolve conflicts, which are certainly minimal.

These generally addressed contemporary dynamics set the scope to think about the world to come, not forgetting the necessary long perspective to think about global change but acknowledging this interregnum (Babic 2020) or liminal time (García Linera 2021).

Global health, food security, climate emergency, or human mobilities, have become essential challenges for contemporary geopolitics.

In that sense, open the lens to look to different regions may be a pattern to approach and discuss taken-for granted views and perceptions, from different planes of production of the global geopolitical imagination. In times of shattering, we may also interrogate and contemplate other dynamics that may highlight different tendencies and transformations or continuities in terms of responses to global

changes. For example, in times and terms of COVID 19, the other face of the coin was the creation or reactivation of mutual popular support networks. In the Brazilian Amazonia, in Bolivian highlands, or in Madrid some examples of this common dynamic featured the social construction of responses to exceptional times (Pachaguayaya & Terrazas 2021; Lois & González-Iturraspe 2021). When thinking about food sovereignty, the conformation of an international social movement also scores the articulation of global responses from locality experiences (see, e.g., International Movement for Food Sovereignty 2023). Another reading of the climate change policies, published in Foreign Policy, speaks about climate colonialism and green capitalism in the global South (Ramachandran 2021), and an eco-social and intercultural pact of the South is proposing frames to cope with the contemporary context in Latin America (Eco social and Intercultural Pact of the South 2020). Proposals such as the New Social Contract (Common Action Forum 2023) or demonstrations for peace in Europe scarcely visible in European media (Stop War 2023) wave the making of spaces for other geopolitical imaginations of the political community limits and central values. In sum, diverse voices seem to open answers of practices to outlook the world to come. Avoiding generalizations but also exceptionalisms, normal and exceptional practices and central political spaces in crisis times are projected and performed in many different forms.

In the next pages, addressing more specifically one of these challenges, that of human mobility in times of crisis will be an excuse to open a conversation around the social construction of normality (and exceptionality) for the daily contemporary geopolitics. Thinking about the delimitation of spaces and ways to manage who is in and out of the political community may be a fruitful exercise to find a vanishing point in thinking about global change.

Mobility, displacement, transit, movement²

Migration, understood as displacement, as the temporary or permanent mobility of people and/or groups, would seem to be consubstantial to the history of humanity. To the global history of humanity, so to speak. We were told that human beings moved, already in prehistoric times, and this is what we have learned. They moved in search of a better life, whatever the meaning of that adjective, which could range from having access to more food to a context of life projected as more favorable, in material, climatic, socio-environmental, affective, or any other possible terms; even none of them. In this sense, mobility and migrations are part of the social, in general, of how what we understand as social happens, and of how the communities themselves are defined, of which the people who move are part, regardless of their legal status. Rather than thinking of these mobilities as an external element, as an externally constituent other of these communities, migration and the ways of practicing movement and mobility shape social formation.

² A first version of the reflections to come was published in *Metápolis* as “Movilidades e (in)seguridades: de las políticas de vigilancia a las políticas de compasión” (Lois 2022).

However, in recent decades, especially in the last decade, a connection between mobility and (in)security has become stronger, imagining borders as devices for territorial control of mobility. Moments such as 9/11, the "cayuco crisis", the "Arab spring", the "long summer of migration" (also known as the refugee crisis) ... have become references of how this security-mobility nexus has been gaining centrality in the social imagination, performed from the constant demarcation of its limits, and practiced through its delimitation, in different times and spaces.

Surveillance and compassion

It does not seem that obstacles to mobility manage to slow or prevent migration. Neither in terms of border security, nor in terms of mobility-controlling technology, does a causal relationship emerge between the two. Granted, these obstacles transform migration routes and timescales, but they do not prevent borders from being crossed; in fact, paradoxically, some of the most heavily policed borders are also those which are most frequently crossed. However, these measures do play a role in strengthening the perception of the threat posed by movement, as well as the territorial effectiveness of these containment measures. They are part of a performance in which the obstacles play a key role in portraying movement as unsafe and threatening, but this dynamic is caught between two things: self-referential and effective territorial political practices with insecurity looming on the horizon, and possible cartographies which reflect social movements whose aim is to go beyond the territorial. In the same way, a whole political economy of migration has been generated around these movements, and it is a topic that has generated a growing amount of research in a number of different areas. It is not only people or groups who are in motion, but also various organizations, institutions, resources, laws, and so on. We are not only referring here to physical journeys, but also to elements of the projection, construction and reproduction of migratory situations and contexts, with little attention to the political condition of vulnerability engendered by mobility. Thus, migrants' situations are affected not only by obstacles and limitations, but also by the organizations, institutions, resources and rights involved in their movement. These can be at the origin of their journeys, at a temporary or permanent destination and, ultimately, in the very concept of mobility, which is rarely if ever perceived as a process with any degree of autonomy, more often being characterized by an assistance-focused approach.

Considering this, it may be valuable to see things from a different perspective. In this case one that highlights the strong contrast between both narratives, perceptions and data, surrounding the movement of people, which is a tremendously fertile area from which to explore the practices of control over mobility. The media summarizes migration at the southern border of Spain, and therefore at the southern edge of Europe itself, with images of 150 sub-Saharan men clambering or jumping over a wire fence. This portrayal is in stark contrast with the acknowledgement in reports by the European Commission that the majority of what are termed "irregular migrants" initially access the Schengen area via regular, legal

means by obtaining a non-permanent visa, but then fail to leave when their visas expire (European Commission 2020; Krotký & Kaniok 2020). The fact was also referenced on maps of migratory patterns published by Frontex on their old website and in other publications on risk analysis, as well as in academic work that has been widely read and referenced; all this is to say that these issues are institutionally recognized and have been the topic of debate. The contrast between different narratives indicates a certain level of exceptionality attached to certain movements, rooted in references to ideas of race, gender and criminalized forms of movement, from which large-scale policies are put into action to identify and control migration. The resulting vision boils down to the surveillance of foreign citizens who enter Europe with a likelihood of staying illegally, having crossed its borders in a *violent* and *disorderly* manner.

On the other hand, institutionally confirmed figures point towards a need for new perspectives on how migration is viewed. Returning to the context of Spain, the figures from the Spanish National Statistics Institute (INE, *Instituto Nacional de Estadística*) for the first half of 2022 established that migratory flows came from Morocco, Romania, Colombia, the United Kingdom, Italy and Venezuela, in that order. This essentially means that they come from a neighboring country in North Africa, members or former members of the European Union, and Latin America. Once again, exploring the contrast between rhetoric and reality can prove a thought-provoking exercise; think of how British or Italian citizens factor into this collective imagining of migration, or property investors, or applicants for so-called “citizenship by investment” (in Spanish CIP, *Ciudadanía por Inversión*), or members of the armed forces, to name but a few. It would appear that there is a lucid and clear abstraction of what constitutes a migrant, what their problems might be, their possible agendas and their position in society in terms of assistance or intervention needed to avoid exclusion (Colectivo IOE 2010; Ribas-Mateos 2018).

In the Other Spaces: some every-day making of exceptionality

In the year 2015, during the “long summer of migration”, when people were moving through Europe on foot in search of a temporary or permanent home, there were many experiences which I believe may help us to reflect about the everyday dynamics and spaces which reproduce and create inequality. However, we will focus on one of these experiences which is of particular interest to scholars of movement and borders. At Radboud University in Nijmegen, on the border between Germany and The Netherlands, a group of colleagues associated with the internationally renowned Nijmegen Centre for Border Research (NCBR) began an informal initiative which they named Asylum University. Under this title, they organized opportunities specifically for asylum seekers, which included guaranteed access to university education, arranging talks, debates and language classes. This initiative is central in the dissertation thesis of Kolar Aparna (2020), graduate student at the NCBR, embracing how the spirit of the project was to provide a space for everyday events related to teaching and research, through which connections could be formed

between spaces of knowledge exchange and temporary accommodation—i.e., shelters, refugee centers and the University—and in this way create safe places for collective action and reflection. Shortly after its inception, one of the Netherlands’ emergency shelters was opened close to the campus, housing around 3000 people opposite the main university community offices. In spite of the difficulties experienced by the initiative it managed, at least temporarily, to shake up people’s previously held notions around migration, migrant spaces, and socially expected or accepted forms of residence. Aparna (2020) lists some exchanges with academic experts in border studies and administrative personnel that reveal a fear of engaging with people who have some form of unregulated status, as well as an inability to involve with asylum seekers on a level beyond mere academic consideration. They are considered to be objects of study, always in some space of waiting for a status, but maybe never sharing that which is understood to be the same as our own.

Around that time several similar initiatives were proposed in universities in Spain, with varying degrees of acceptance. In addition to Spain’s migrant intake numbers being undeniably lower than those of countries such as Germany or the Netherlands, the initiatives failed to make much of an impact in an administrative, bureaucratic and academic landscape which believed it had already pinned down the problems (and solutions) of such a group. In many instances, the opening up of public spaces such as classrooms and University facilities for in-person, non-hierarchical social interaction was dismissed on grounds of security, citing possible disagreements and conflicts. The discomfort caused by an unregulated gathering which occurred outside the confines of preconceived expectations around the vulnerability of those who migrate and the help they receive demonstrates how complex perspectives on (some types of) migration can be. At the same time, this also highlights the disruptive potential of opening up every day social spaces, something that the hosts intended as a means, rather than an end in itself. Universities, as public spaces with a social function, are places for social change, and the ingenuousness of these proposals may well be a vital and powerful strategy if we are to continue thinking about the possibility of emancipating our gaze on mobilities, migration and movement.

It is precisely in the places where mobility and migration are researched, in public and in publicly acknowledged spaces of equal conditions, that the possibility of other kinds of encounters may be envisaged. If this does not prove true then, at least as Aparna implies, they can serve as places to reflect on the environment and sense of community of universities as a subject to be studied in itself, given that they do in fact create differences and inequalities. Despite the possible difficulties, I would also like to think that, in the immediacy and closeness of everyday life, the relationships we establish are complex, but also open and malleable, with the potential to free us from narrow, fixed perspectives on migration. Conflict is just as much a part of society as agreement, and it is much easier to resolve and explore it in relatively informal spaces that are free from regulation or interference. Therefore, it is by living among one another that we can finally find somewhere to explore both

conflict and agreement, and we must ultimately remember that diversity is not exclusive to populations in movement.

The territorial trap

Looking beyond the ingenuousness of the previous paragraphs, another important point to be made about the link between migration and (in)security is its territorial manifestations, which made a brief appearance at the beginning of the text in our discussion of the systematic recourse to territorial solutions for dealing with possible threats, specifically the building of border walls. The idea of creating a physical barrier between nations is, of course, nothing new—on the contrary, it is ontologically tied to the construction of the modern nation-state. However, it is worth noting that interest in them has reached a fever pitch in recent years in spite of their questionable efficacy. Elizabeth Vallet (2022) recounts how the existence of such walls has grown from 15 in 1989 to 74 in 2022, with at least 15 more at the planning stage. Her research relates this to the end of the Cold War, and then later to 9/11, arguing that the COVID-19 pandemic consolidated the trend towards the development and installation of physical infrastructure as the central component of a hermetically sealed border. In the context of the European Union, requests for financing to build border security infrastructure have been growing over time. At almost the same time as the implementation of the Temporary Protection Directive for people coming from Ukraine, the militarization and construction of a fence by Poland on its border with Belarus and the construction of another wall on its border with Russia in Kaliningrad clearly demonstrated the differentiated treatment for migrants depending on their supposed points of origin and subsequent political practices or beliefs. In public rhetoric on the matter, and in a letter to the European Commission, which was signed by 12 ministries of member states, attention was drawn to the “need to adapt the existing legal framework to the new realities, enabling us to adequately address attempts of instrumentalization of illegal migration for political purposes and other hybrid threats” (Politico 2021,1). The idea that certain types of migration can be saved by building walls to block other types of migration is paradoxical, to say the very least.

As Vallet notes, the COVID-19 pandemic brought certain trends in the relationship between migration and (in)security into focus. On the European stage, the decision was made for the first time to close external borders on 17 March 2020. In the weeks leading up to this closure, the connection between mobility, security and the pandemic had already been making its presence known on various parts of the global stage, in different to political leaders in Europa, such as Hungarian prime minister: “Because movement spreads the disease and makes the epidemic global, and migration is movement, therefore there is a logical link between the two [...] Hungary has managed to defend against migration, so we are protected against the infections migrants may bring with them” (Dunai 2020). In other words, what can be found outside the border may not stay put, and if it gets in, problems will only increase. This gestures to disease as something tied to place, meaning the antidote

to it is, consequently, a territorial matter (Lois 2020, 295). The border can therefore erase the very question of whether sick (or healthy) people exist, as it provides a line which divides sick people or carriers of disease from the healthy; in this particular case, it excluded anyone and everyone outside the country.

With the borders closed, the only permitted movement was that of goods and journeys considered essential to the continued functioning of shared territory. The request for coordination in communications from the European Commission firmly establishes the link between borders and security by creating an area where “the EU’s external border has to act as a security perimeter for all Schengen States” (European Commission 2020).

It is interesting to remark that EU interstate borders close on a relatively continuous basis in the presence of so-called “exceptional circumstances”. The Schengen Borders Code has always permitted the introduction of controls at its internal borders on the basis of such exceptional circumstances, as dictated by Chapter II of Regulation UE2016/399 which was reformed in 2016, in particular articles 25 and 30. In fact, *exceptional circumstances* have ranged from sporting events to Pope visits, G-7 meetings, NATO and climate summits, terrorist attacks, political protests or Hell’s Angels gatherings (Lois 2014). In COVID 19 times, the pandemic has led at least 14 countries (Austria, Czechia, Denmark, Hungary, Lithuania, Poland, Germany, Estonia, Portugal, Spain, Finland, Belgium, Switzerland and Norway) to strengthen their internal EU borders as a way to control the movement of people, with those of Germany, Austria, Denmark, France, Norway and Sweden being maintained in more or less the same conditions since the refugee crisis of 2015.

The generalization of restrictions on mobility in the context of COVID-19, on the other hand, can also allow for reflection on how immobility has come to be a strategy in the establishment of security. In a time of widespread restriction of movement, the irrelevance of spaces normally used to impose immobility and isolation were resoundingly revealed to be just another territorial tool for maintaining certain movement and security under *normal* circumstances. This was demonstrated as soon as these places where control of movement was exercised within the European Union became affected by the pandemic. For example, in Spain on 6 May 2020, the eight functioning Migrant Detention Centers (known in Spanish by the acronym CIE: *Centro de Internamiento de Extranjeros*), were closed. [9] These centers, originally conceived in 1986 as non-penitentiary facilities in which to hold migrants for a maximum of 60 days while they were in the process of being deported, are a product of the first Spanish Immigration Law on the rights and liberties of foreign nationals (*Ley Orgánica 7/1985 sobre Derechos y Libertades de los Extranjeros*). The suspension of administrative timeframes and processes, as well as flights (including repatriation flights), made it impossible to formalize deportation. It is interesting to note how the immobility of some turns out to be the mobility of others. Much like in other spaces which are intended to safeguard the movement of some by restricting that of others (CIEs, refugee camps, prisons), once movement was restricted in general, immobility and isolation ceased to be *convenient*. Restrictions

on mobility enable other forms of mobility which, in this case paradoxically became a strategy for survival. In short, the territorial trap, whereby different visions of spatial socialization become entangled, is of utmost significance; it points towards a territorial imaginary in which controlling mobility means that, by closing the borders, you limit danger, movement and exceptionality. Nevertheless, it was precisely this exceptionality that showed mobility to be a key element of how society is formed, how it is an integral part of the world economy, and that it is crucial to the maintenance of the labor activities needed to reproduce the system itself.

Throughout this complex rhetorical landscape, public policy conception and management plays a fundamental role. Decisions about rights, controls, interventions and, ultimately, what constitutes the legitimate movement of people all form part of the institutional framework and of the decisions institutionally taken at every possible level. Here, again, we can see how society starts with the establishment of free movement as a human right, as stated in, for example, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and the Canadian Charter of Rights and Freedoms. Such a right undeniably exists to ensure diversity without threatening national unity, but it ultimately amounts to an explicit protection of the right to movement within society.

Approaching now another crisis, that is, the war in Ukraine, we also find another context to think about how the approach to movement and mobility within a community underlines the limits of the (geo)political common space. In March 2022, the European Union activated the Temporary Protection Directive (TPD), which granted immediate protection for one year to those fleeing the war in Ukraine, including Ukrainian nationals, third countries nationals, stateless people and legal residents in the country. This protection granted residency permits, the ability to work, access to medical care, and so on. This directive, though created in 2001, was not put into action in 2015 during the Syrian War. Only in 2022 was it first implemented, when it showcased the efficient, effective and organized provision of asylum and protection based on certain universal rights. However, the impact on institutions and groups involved in previous movements has become evident, and thus decisions made by institutions at various levels—which have not been extended to others in similar circumstances—uphold inequalities, establish preferential treatment for legitimate or related migratory flows and, lastly, uphold the material and symbolic conditions which underpin this mindset, along with the hierarchies which differentiate and legitimize movements. Knowing this, we *may* establish a sense of responsibility and commitment, especially towards migrants on other levels of the hierarchy who, even now, are differentiated or cast aside. However, the near invisibility of this structural issue—by which we mean the practices of differentiation which permeate asylum and refugee policies—presents an uncomfortable home truth, namely that the racialization of migration according to origins and routes, becomes *normal*.

Previous publications have already underlined the *differential humanities* implied when approaching politics of refuge and asylum in the EU (De Conninck 2023; Musyimi

2023 Alsbeti 2022; Zarkov 2022; Costello and Foster 2022). Using a discourse analysis methodology, a recent thesis deepens on the different responses of the EU to refugee's movement in 2015 and 2022 (Prideaux de Lacy 2023). Approaching EU, Germany and Sweden immigration reports and newspapers, the author concludes that "EU values are utilized to alienate outsiders, and therefore not universally applied to all refugees" (2023, 49). Changes in the use of languages (from 2015 refugee to 2022 humanitarian crises), or the emphasis in 2015 in connections with EU threats against member states of the origin non-EU countries are part of the concluding findings of this work, that underlines the EU identity politics (Prideaux de Lacy 2023) embedded in the *normalization* of the 2022 mobilities geopolitical status.

The immobilization of war related refugees in the past under the paradigm of the containment of mobility has been superseded in the case of Russia-Ukraine war related mobilities. The exceptionality of the 2015 war mobilities and the normalization of war mobilities in 2022 stresses not only the inequalities in solidarity (Carrera *et al.*, 2022), but also a biased requalification of movements that defines what is *inside* and *outside* of the political community, performing its geopolitical limits.

The Numbers and Perceptions Game: what next?

Little remains to be said about the role of movement and migration in society. Institutions, research institutes and academics have all expounded on its impact in various terms depending on the context in question: economic and consumerist terms in contexts of limited growth; demographic terms when discussing ageing societies; and in terms of care in contexts of growing dependent groups. The impact of migrant remittances on the local and regional economies from which they originate shows the stability of a complex and counter-cyclical system of exchange and circulation of people, goods and money; according to the World Bank, the total amount climbed to 626 billion USD in 2022 (World Bank 2022).

However, divergences between different narratives continue to provide insights that would be worth exploring in bigger depth. A recently published article on immigration in Germany, France, the USA, Italy, the UK and Sweden, which draws on statistical data from a total sample of 24,000 non-immigrant people, suggests that a large part of the debate surrounding immigration is characterized by misinformation and stereotypes, often stemming from anti-immigration political parties and media outlets (Alesina, Miano & Stantcheva 2022).

The research therefore focuses on the discrepancy between perceptions and facts: with the exception of Sweden, the people interviewed assumed that the proportion of immigrants in their country was at least double the actual amount. They also had incorrect perceptions of where immigrants had come from, believed that they depend more on state Welfare than they really do, and that they are less educated and have a higher rate of unemployment than the corresponding figures show. The article concludes that narratives surrounding the politicization of mobilities and

movements hold greater sway over people's opinion than data. In light of this, now may well be the time to think about other narratives which make it possible to put movement at the center of how society is formed, without romanticizing, chasing, victimizing or coddling migrant experiences, but rather seeing them as a cornerstone of what defines the social formations and change. Perhaps it is an interesting route to reflect on the diverse dimensions and voices in the making of the geopolitics of global change, approaching the reproduction of institutional and non-institutional rhetoric that links (im) mobility to security, the practices and processes that legitimize certain forms of migration, the racialization of insecurity and hierarchies of movements, the sidelining and hiding of the mobile and the migrant, or the possibilities of unconventional dwelling spaces for people in movement. Imaginably we may question how all these elements have come to be as part of what is assumed and reproduced as *normal*.

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The “Long 2020”: The Unfolding Geopolitical Transition of the World Order

Mihajlo Kopanja¹

Abstract:

World orders might be relatively static, but they do change – and when a change occurs it triggers significant shocks throughout the world geopolitical system. We are acquainted with many different explanations to how such changes occur, be it Modelski’s Long Cycles, Organski’s power transition or Kennedy’s imperial overstretch. But while they all provide explanations to why and how the process of geopolitical system change happens, what they all lack is an understanding of how geopolitical structure impacts state behavior during these relatively short periods between two world orders. This is where Peter Taylor’s notion of geopolitical transition comes in. According to Taylor geopolitical transition represents a short time span in which radical restructuring of the international system occurs. Just as Taylor highlighted the “Long 1945” as the moment of geopolitical transition from the *Interbellum* geopolitical system to the (then) emerging Cold War geopolitical system, we hypothesize that we are now in the period of geopolitical transition - The “Long 2020”, moment between the *Pax Americanna* geopolitical system and the emerging geopolitical system whose characteristics are yet to be defined. Thus, the objective of this paper is three-fold. Firstly, we will provide an overview of the concept of geopolitical transition. Secondly, we will provide arguments to why we are currently living in such a period dubbed as the Long 2020. Finally, we will touch upon the implications of how structural uncertainty during periods of geopolitical transition impact the behavior of states.

Key Words:

Geopolitical transition, World Order, geopolitical system, U.S., China, Russia, COVID-19, Russo-Ukrainian war

¹ Assistant Professor, Faculty of Security Studies, University of Belgrade mihajlo.kopanja@fb.bg.ac.rs

A Brief Introduction

Few phrases gather so much attention both in academia and public discourse as world order. It is somewhat understandable why. The grandiosity behind this phrase stems from the fact that world order represents an overarching idea that gives context in which state interactions unfold. While this is by no means a definition of the concept of world order, it shows why so much attention is given to it. Akin to the rules of any game, world order is thought of as impacting everyone, everywhere, doing everything – and does so for a prolonged period of time. However, what happens during periods when one order changes to another? The central claim of this paper is that we are currently living in such a period – a period when the Liberal Order is transitioning to a new world order.

In geopolitics, such a process of transition between two orders is called geopolitical transition. It is a relatively short but rapid period of change in the way the world geopolitical system is structured (Taylor, 1990). During a span of a few years, geopolitical system goes through a rapid change marked with an increase in intrastate conflicts, change in alignment patterns and the shape of international institutions and regimes. This paper argues that ever since the COVID-19 pandemic began, the world entered a period of geopolitical transition – and we are still there. Following Peter Taylor’s label “The Long 1945”, used to signify the geopolitical transition to the Cold War Liberal Order, we call this period “The Long 2020” – highlighting how COVID-19 pandemic represented a similar turning point as the end of the Second World War did.

More concretely, in this paper we put forth three propositions regarding the current state of the world order. Firstly, the geopolitical view of world order allows for a better understanding of the interplay between world order and state behavior. By downplaying the “merits” of parsimonious generalities and thinking about world order through spatial lens we avoid thinking in a void (see: Booth, 1979, p. 147). Secondly, the rapid rise and unexpectedness of international conflicts following 2020 provides a clear sign that we are living in a moment of geopolitical transition. World order manages international competition. When the number and intensity of conflicts increase, and they do so unexpectedly for most observers, the managing effect of world order ceases and new order emerges. Finally, being in a period of geopolitical transition implies that international conflicts will

Geopolitics and the world system

The distinction of different types of international systems in more mainstream IR theory is relatively simple. Since Kenneth Waltz onwards, the international system has been observed namely through the given distribution of power and the number

of poles of such an international system (Waltz, 2010). Even if we take the English School's approach to international society, which is somewhat more detailed in its explanation of the structural effects, it is still overly parsimonious to encapsulate the full complexity of the international system (e.g. see Jervis, 1999). Simply put, IR theories focus either on power distribution, or international organizations and regimes, or the societal agreement on how states should behave. However, in the quest for theoretical parsimony and abstract generality they tend to miss out on how they intertwine and actually impact the world.

Geopolitics does this differently. Firstly, the defining characteristic of Geopolitics, compared to other approaches to the study of international politics, is that it sees spatial factors as the main driving force of state behavior. Yet, space need not relate to locations, natural resources, physical barriers, etc. as it is usually perceived. How individuals and groups perceive different spatial areas, how space is represented in popular culture, and even how global space itself is politically organized, can likewise be thought of as the spatial factors of geopolitics. Geopolitics is therefore best defined as the spatial analysis of international politics, whereas spatial factors are broadly defined.

Within the broader geopolitical approach, structural geopolitics studies how the spatial structure of the world geopolitical system conditions state behavior. We must note that the meaning of structural geopolitics (within geopolitical studies) is somewhat uncertain. While some authors like O'Tuathail mention it in their heuristic division of geopolitics (alongside formal, practical, and popular), most exclude structural geopolitics from the division. It is our understanding that structural geopolitics encompasses precisely the study of structural characteristics of the given geopolitical system and bases its explanation on state behavior through the influence on them by the geopolitical system itself. Therefore, any author who gives explanatory advantage to the structural/systemic factors or any conceptual/theoretical apparatus that highlights the global scale can be considered part of study of structural geopolitics (e.g. see: Cohen, 1975; 2015; Agnew and Corbridge, 1995; Dussouy, 2010; Taylor, 1990; 1993) The world geopolitical system represents the way in which space is organized on the highest scale – global. It is produced by the practices of and interactions between states as well as the collective imaginations on “how the world works”. This represents the “environmental, spatial frame” in which all state behavior occurs, and concrete characteristics of a given geopolitical system dictates the span of possibilities and limitations on state behavior.

Benefits of utilizing structural geopolitics

The previous discussion should be understood as the foundation to why the geopolitical approach to international politics is used, instead of IR theories.

Geopolitics avoids what John Agnew calls “the territorial trap” of IR, the notion that the international environment as a “set of fixed facts setting the environment for the action of territorial states that are essentially the same today as 200 years ago” (Agnew, 1994, p. 56). For the purposes of this paper, there are three main arguments as to why utilizing structural geopolitical approaches can provide us with a better understanding of the changing world order.

Firstly, although international systems can be categorized by polarity, the environment in which states operate is not always the same. Even minute changes of the environment, albeit of the same polarity-type, can impact the behavior of states. To say that the international system is unipolar, bipolar or multipolar not only gives us a wide range of possible state behavior, but we can also state that the same state behavior can, hypothetically, have quite different patterns of implementation as well as geographical focus. Take for an example Southeast Asia. The bipolar nature of the Cold War international system does not tell us much as to why it became such a foreground of proxy wars between the U.S. and U.S.S.R. and not, for an example, the Middle East or Northeast Asia or Central Asia. All these regions could have been (and in certain points of the Cold War were) the place of most prominent activity in implementing Containment. Yet, when we now say Domino Theory the first region that comes to mind is Southeast Asia. Some can argue that this is just how it is – in the sense that proxy wars were inevitable in the Cold War bipolar structure and in Southeast Asia. However, this cannot be seen as given. A myriad of factors, both external and internal to the region, had led to Southeast Asia being the focal point.

Secondly, the geopolitical system shifts are not something that happens overnight. Just observe the current state of the international system. There is no consensus whether we live in a unipolar, bipolar or a multipolar world. The lack of consensus stems from the fact that there is a vast gray zone in between different possible states of polarity in the international system. What happens before we enter the gray zone and what happens after we exit it, is easier to comprehend. But effects on state behavior during structural shifts are something that precisely happens in that black box of a gray zone. This directly connects to the second point. Even though states can be revisionist or status quo, the differences in the international environment impact not only what states prefer/don't prefer in the current international system but also precisely (as possible) what they wish to keep/change. Finally, relying on geopolitics gives us a conceptual apparatus for observing the black box of geopolitical system shifts gray zone – the concept of geopolitical transition.

Finally, another important note that differentiates the geopolitical view of the international system from the IR one is that the materialist-idealist divide need not exist. Sure, some IR theories would argue this as well, but this is something virtually built into the geopolitical view of international politics. Simply put, both space and

geography, that study spatial differentiations, rest upon physical as well as human characteristics. Those who would raise an objection by stating that geopolitics highlights only the physical side of space in providing explanations of international politics have quite a reductionist view of geopolitics that knows only the likes of Mackinder and Spykman – works a century old.

Conceptualizing geopolitical world system

Among different theoretical approaches in structural geopolitics, Saul Bernard Cohen's approach stands tall as a particularly well envisioned way to observe the world geopolitical system. Cohen sees the world as a set of hierarchically nested spatial wholes – ranging from the subnational regions, to states, geopolitical regions and geostrategic realms (Cohen, 2015, p. 37). Each spatial whole is defined by geopolitical features and patterns – features being “political-geographical nodes, areas and boundaries that contribute to the unit's uniqueness and influence its cohesiveness” (Cohen, 2015, p. 37) while patterns refer to “the shape, size and the physical/human geographical characteristics of the geopolitical units and the networks that tie them together...and...distinguish them from other units” (Cohen, 2015, p. 37). Geostrategic realms are at the highest spatial level that includes multiple geopolitical regions. They are geostrategic because only strategic interactions exist between them. According to Cohen, there are currently three geostrategic realms: Maritime realm – led by the U.S.; Eurasian continental realm – led by Russia; and East Asian realm – led by China (Cohen, 2015). Outside this framework, there exist independent geopolitical regions (only South Asia led by India), shatterbelts (internally fragmented and strategically located geopolitical regions that are caught in a competition between great powers), compression zones (similar to shatterbelts but caught in a competition between regional powers), gateway regions (that can serve as a place of cooperation between competing great powers) and convergence zones (regions which can lean either way) (Cohen, 2015, p. 37-63; Kopanja, 2020).

Observing the world geopolitical system in a certain period of time, a distinct geopolitical structure emerges – structure that is unique in its shape and characteristics. Although two separate world geopolitical systems can be thought of as unipolar/bipolar/multipolar, they are still distinct in their shape and characteristics. It is therefore that the impact of structural factors on the direction of a certain state's grand strategy becomes more evident. Likewise the strategic vision of a state becomes easier to determine, because it directly relates to the (relatively) concrete structure of the geopolitical system one state strives to achieve. Similarly, it gives us a better understanding of what makes a given state revisionist or status quo.

Although Cohen's approach to the world geopolitical system provides us with a better foothold for observing the impact of structural factors on grand strategy, it is (of course) not perfect and has issues of its own (see: Kopanja, 2020). One of the most important problems is that the model itself completely ignores the collective imaginations on how the world works. This point can be supplemented by another structural geopolitical approach by John Agnew and Stuart Corbridge. Unlike Cohen's detailed view of the geopolitical system, Agnew and Corbridge provide a relatively reductionist view of it through the notion of geopolitical order (Agnew and Corbridge, 1995). But what they lack in precision with the notion of geopolitical order, they more than compensate with the idea of a global geopolitical discourse.

For Agnew and Corbridge, global geopolitical discourse represents "how the geography of the international political economy has been 'written and read' in the practices of foreign and economic policies during different periods of geopolitical order" (Agnew and Corbridge, 1995, p. 46). In essence, this would mean that each geopolitical system has an overreaching discourse attached to it that induces specific geographical representations both into the practices of states as well as the communication between states (Agnew and Corbridge, 1995, pp. 46-47). The global geopolitical discourse impacts how states and their political leaders envision the current spatial distribution of power, legitimate courses of action, delineate between friend and foe and generally observe how states should interact. Insofar, Agnew and Corbridge identified three global geopolitical discourses: Civilizational (1815-1875), Naturalized (1875-1945) and Ideological (1945-1990), each succeeding one another following geopolitical system shifts (Agnew and Corbridge, 1995, pp. 52-76). With the introduction of global geopolitical discourse along with Cohen's view of the structure of the world geopolitical system we get a more complete geopolitical view of the international system.

The "Long 2020": Geopolitical Transition in Action

The main hypothesis of this paper is that that we are currently living in the period of geopolitical transition – the "Long 2020". Just as Taylor highlighted the "Long 1945" as the moment of geopolitical transition from the *Interbellum* geopolitical system to the (then) emerging Cold War geopolitical system, we are now in the period of geopolitical transition between the *Pax Americana* geopolitical system and the emerging geopolitical system whose characteristics are yet to be defined. The name – "Long 2020", immediately brings to mind the idea that the COVID-19 pandemic was the main driving force behind geopolitical transition. This is not the case. COVID-19 was just a trigger that expedited the process and brought the period of geopolitical transition quicker than it would have happened if there were no pandemic. Think of it in terms of the causes of the First World War. Assassination

of Archduke Franz Ferdinand was not the cause of WWI it was just *casus belli* that brought the inevitable confrontation between two major power blocks faster than expected.

The effects of the pandemic were similar in fashion. Even prior to the pandemic many challenges to the U.S. led order happened – Russian intervention in Georgia, BRICS, annexation of Crimea, Russian involvement in Syria, and the Belt and Road Initiative. While they were far from being a direct challenge to the existing order, they were glimpses of evidence pointing not only to the discontent by some states but also their willingness to act. On a more important note, Chinese economic and military rise over the past decade or so made the process of geopolitical transition bound to happen. When almost all ties to the outside world were severed due to the pandemic, hegemonic presence of the U.S. somewhat faded away. This allowed for action of not only other major powers but lesser states as well to act in a manner they otherwise probably would not. Having that in mind, events took the life of their own which in turn expedited the coming of the period of geopolitical transition. As we see today, “chaos” is the new normality in international affairs, with patterns of state behavior signaling that the structural constraints are lessening their grip on them.

The Notion of Geopolitical Transition

Theoretically speaking, neither Cohen nor Agnew and Corbridge see geopolitical systems as being a static category. International practices and interactions as well as representations and perceptions of geopolitical system are in a constant flux. Of course, they are relatively stable in the sense that we can talk about, let’s say, the Cold War system. But this does not mean that the Cold War geopolitical system was the same in the early 1950s as during the 1980s. From Korea to Vietnam and later on Afghanistan and the Middle East, there were changes in the characteristics of the structure of the world geopolitical system. Likewise, by the final stage of the Cold War, China became the leader of a completely separate geostrategic realm, which was not the case in its early stages. On the other hand, though, throughout the Cold War the same geopolitical discourse existed. But after 1990 things dramatically changed. With the sudden collapse of the U.S.S.R., Eurasian Continental realm lost its momentum, the Balkans “shattered”, Middle East enjoyed a brief moment of tranquility, and Eastern Europe became a temporary gateway region. Simply put, the geopolitical system quickly restructured itself. Similarly, ideological foundation of the predominant discourse went through an overhaul of its own being that the ideological geopolitical discourse gave way to a kind of a liberal-democratic one. But, in all honesty, there hasn’t been an attempt to map the predominant global geopolitical discourse of the post-Cold War system, at least to our knowledge.

Agnew and Corbridge hint that it might be a return to something like the civilizational discourse of the 19th century (apropos Huntington's *Clash of Civilization thesis*) thought they are not definitive on that point.

But this geopolitical system shift was not immediate, in the sense that one replaced the other in the matter of days or weeks following the end of the Cold War. From the fall of the Berlin Wall to the dissolution of the U.S.S.R. couple of year had passed in which there was great uncertainty regarding what's to come. Of course, there had been an understanding that the U.S. would probably be unmatched superpower, but their relations with the Russia that emerged as well as impact on the rest of the world were uncertain. That short period of time represents geopolitical transition. To put it simply, the concept of geopolitical transition relates to the relatively short but rapid period of change in way the world geopolitical system is structured as well as perceived (Taylor, 1990). More often than not, geopolitical transition is the result of a major war, something that Allison calls Thucydides Trap (Allison, 2017). This is obvious because the outcome of major wars virtually always leads to changes in relative power of states, namely those at the top of the "food chain". This produces shocks throughout the system in several different ways. Firstly, characteristics of certain regions change because there is no longer a competitive great power to lead to shatterbelts, or even regional powers for compression zone to emerge. Secondly, regions themselves might be restructured to include states that were previously in other regions or realms. Thirdly, old geostrategic realms might disappear while new ones might emerge. Finally, the discursive basis of the geopolitical system becomes redundant as there is no longer "the other".

While this is also true for the dynamism throughout the "lifespan" of a certain geopolitical system, the main difference is that this happens rapidly – in the span of couple of years, as well as more fundamentally. Having that in mind, it is evident that the concept of geopolitical transition is closely related to the idea of power transition (see: Organski and Kugler, 1980). As in the case of power transition theory, geopolitical transition relates to the change within the structure of the world system as one, or more powers start to decline relative to its/their challengers. But the major point of differentiation is that geopolitical transition is more encompassing. While power transition is necessary for geopolitical transition to unfold, power transition does not necessarily have to lead to a major restructuring of the world geopolitical system both in the sense of structure and discourse. Power transition that happened following WWI, when the U.S. surpassed Great Britain didn't lead to neither a major war nor geopolitical system shifts – thought this is because the U.S. did not want such a role.

When geopolitical transition unfolds structural effects on states become less strong as during periods of relative stability. This is because it becomes debatable whether international structure fully "exists" at that point. Therefore, during periods of

geopolitical transition states are less constrained by the structure. They can reevaluate their position as well as their approach to national security. As Johnston rightfully notices “major geopolitical transitions provide opportunities for political elites in a large number of states to evaluate their country’s international relationships and foreign and defense policies” (Johnston, 1997, p. 63). This reevaluation can lead to states pursuing alternate policies and strategies in order to profit from the permissiveness of the environment in the wake of structural shifts. It is at this point that grand strategic change can, and often does occur.

“The Long 2020”

What we are witnessing since the COVID-19 pandemic started, is that many states are doing precisely that – reevaluating their relationships and foreign and defense policies. Even more so, since 2020, states are even more ready to solve their long-term issues with other states by utilizing force to do so. The nature of the Liberal order was that interstate war was ostracized as a tool of statecraft. While the bipolar world of the Cold War mitigated the institutional and societal grip on legitimate interstate war, the Unipolar Moment broke such practice. In fact, the U.S. were the sole state that had the power to wage war on others – but even then, only with a (relatively) broad international support (see Finnemore, 2003). The reason for this was that world orders tend to lead to a more restrictive strategic environment for states. Once the grip of a world order loosens, the strategic environment becomes more permissive.

The COVID-19 pandemic was the turning point because the internal focus of states on preserving human security of its populus prevented them from major foreign policy action. Well, this is only partially true because each state was willing to focus on foreign policy questions that were of major importance to them. Most states did rely on public diplomacy and foreign aid, but what we are talking about here are the more traditional state behavior in geopolitical studies. This is important for two reasons. Firstly, even during the Pandemic states not only had foreign policy interests, but also acted upon them. Secondly, outside questions of major importance they did not have the resources or the focus to tackle less important questions. The practical implication of this was that the U.S. were unable to manage the world order as they did in the past, which allowed for a more permissive environment.

However, it is important to highlight that the Pandemic was not the cause for the outbreak of the geopolitical transition. Even prior to its beginning there were signs that the world is starting to “shatter” (Kopanja and Stekić, 2020). Relative power between the U.S. and other states was rapidly diminishing and actors both within the U.S. lead Maritime Realm and the Eurasian and East Asian Realms were

beginning to act contrary to U.S. interest. Early turmoil in Ukraine and the start of the Belt and Road Initiative were just the first signs of that. To put it simply, even before the Pandemic hit, there were signs that U.S. unipolarity was no longer unambiguous (see Wohlforth, 1999). While still not a multipolar world, other states in the world system started to perceive the U.S. as no longer the unanimous superpower as it once was. Therefore, the process of geopolitical transition was beginning to show itself even before the COVID-19 Pandemic started. It was nothing more than a catalyst that sped up the process which might have happened not in 2020, but half a decade or so later.

The reason we state that the world order is currently in flux – that is, that we are living in a period of geopolitical transition – is because of the vast increase in conflicts that have happened since 2020. The first major sign was the Armenia-Azerbaijan war over the disputed territory of Nagorno-Karabakh. The dispute between Armenia and Azerbaijan over said territory has been ongoing for more than three decades. The first series of conflicts lasted between 1988 and 1994, with a prolonged period of low-intensity conflict that lasted until 2020. In late September 2020 a 44-day war between the two countries erupted, signifying the first major conflict that excluded the involvement of major powers. Leaving the details of this conflict aside, the 2020 Armenia-Azerbaijan war is significant because it showed that states are once again willing and able to use force to achieve their will – something not seen since at least the end of the Cold War.

Taken on its own, the 2020 Armenia-Azerbaijan war might not have been that relevant had it not been both predated and followed by a series of conflict all around the globe. In the period of 2020-2023 there was much turmoil in many geopolitical regions of the world. In Africa, there were a series of both intrastate conflicts and military coups. Civil wars and conflicts erupted in Ethiopia, Eritrea, Ghana, Somalia, Morocco, Sudan and Nigeria to name a few, with the most important ones being in Ethiopia and Sudan. Likewise, there was a series of coup d'états in Mali, Niger, Guinea, Gabon and Sudan. In Asia, similar events unfolded in Myanmar, between Kyrgyzstan and Tajikistan, China and India, as well as Chinese military exercises around Taiwan. However, the two most important events that occurred were the Russo-Ukrainian War and the Israel-Hamas war². When first Russian soldiers entered Ukraine, it came as a sign that the international order has been severely challenged by Russia. Although arguments can be made that Russia has been forced to such action, this does not change the fact that one great power (which is not the U.S.) utilized war as a tool of influencing another state. Simply put,

² Since this paper was presented on the eve of the Hamas attacks on Israel, this case has not been covered in the paper. However, due to the impact it has had this sentence was revised to mention the Israel-Hamas war as well.

an order which was centered around U.S. dominance and to a certain point even governance, has been

Geopolitical theory tells us that when the structure of the world geopolitical system starts to modify, the change is not only rapid but is also violent. For a few years, the world experiences an increase in violent conflicts both between and within states that changes the subsequent political geographical landscape of the world. What we are seeing currently is precisely that – a rapid increase in violent conflicts in the world. Old allegiances are changing, new are forging and *homo homini lupus est* reigns supreme. The COVID-19 pandemic sped up the already unfolding process of world “shattering” by disabling U.S. presence and influence around the world. This created a permissive environment which has led other states to reevaluate their relationships and foreign and defense policies. Such events only further speed up the process of restructuring until, after much blood and destruction, the world system finally restructures itself into a relatively stable new form.

Instead of a conclusion: Great Power Behavior in the “Long 2020”

Assuming that we are living in a period of geopolitical transition, it is therefore undeniable that states will have to change their grand strategies (presuming that all major powers do in fact have them). This begs the question: which states will have to adjust their grand strategy and which will have to overhaul them? We can predict the following – the U.S. will have to completely overhaul their grand strategy, while Russia and China will have to adjust theirs. Everything that the U.S. had done in recent years seems to have had little to no effect on preserving the post-Cold War status quo. They were unable to distribute the burden of security expenses to their NATO allies, prevent projection of Russian power to Ukraine and Syria, block Chinese presence in regions of the world outside their geostrategic realm, as well as maintain their presence in Central Asia. Therefore, an overhaul is needed in order for the U.S. to shape the international order to come towards something reminiscent of the post-Cold War one where their leadership remains, albeit in a less preponderant manner.

On the other hand, Russia and China will have to adjust their grand strategies because, in their current form, do not seem to have a clear picture of the international order that might replace the existing one. Courses of action they had taken in the past decade can be described better in terms of “we don’t want this” than in terms of “we want that”. While knowing what you don’t want is the first step towards determining what it is that you want, you still need to adjust your strategy in order to stop fighting against and work towards building for. On the other hand, they also need not only to envision an order that favors them but also an order which the majority of other states in the international system find

appealing. Without this, they will not be able to legitimize their behavior and will find themselves even more constrained.

As far as lesser (but still powerful) states are concerned we can differentiate them into two groups based on the expectations of changes to their grand strategy. Brazil, India and perhaps even Iran will have to overhaul their grand strategies in the direction of a more active role in shaping the international order. If they let China and Russia to solely shape the international order, they might find themselves in a less favorable situation. This is truer for Brazil and India than Iran, but still we can expect them to overhaul their grand strategies in the coming years. On the other hand, states like Germany, France, the U.K. and Japan will have to adjust their grand strategies in the direction of taking greater and more direct contribution to the U.S. led efforts. So far they have overly relied on the U.S. for their security, therefore relying less on harder forms of power. We can expect that they will follow the U.S.'s approach to the international system in its overhauled form, just as they had for the past three decades, with the adjusted element of taking greater military contribution in these efforts. Finally, Turkey seems to be an exception to the rule. Their grand strategy seems to be reminiscent of something in the lines of a "grand hedge". Since the "no" to the U.S. prior to the invasion of Iraq, they pursued the grand strategy of Strategic depth which focused on its immediate neighborhood (see: Ajzenhamer, 2022). But on a greater level, Turkey seemed to have hedged between the U.S. and NATO on one hand and Russia-China duo on the other hand. The particularity of their position (both in geographic and diplomatic terms) might allow for their grand strategy to continue without overhaul or adjustment.

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PANEL II

A „SHATTERED’ WORLD

Chair: Maria Lois

Discussant: Mihajlo Kopanja

The Middle East: No Longer a Shatterbelt, Yet Still Divided¹

Vladimir Ajzenhamer²

Abstract

This article reexamines the contemporary geopolitical position of the Middle East through the lens of Saul Bernard Cohen's regional taxonomy, with particular emphasis on his concept of the shatterbelt and his post-Cold War claim that the structural conditions sustaining this status have begun to weaken. Cohen suggests that the erosion of symmetrical great-power rivalry has reduced the extent to which the region is primarily defined by external power competition, while internal dynamics have gained increasing significance. Although he does not codify this transformation into a distinct conceptual category, his reasoning opens analytical space for thinking about the Middle East in terms of an emerging – though still incomplete, process of regional systemic development. Building on this interpretation, the article critically reassesses the applicability of Cohen's diagnosis in light of subsequent developments, including post-Cold War and post-Arab Spring transformations of regional order. It advances the argument that while the Middle East no longer fulfills the core structural requirements of a classical shatterbelt, most notably sustained and symmetrical great-power rivalry – it also does not meet the criteria for what this article conceptualizes as a developing regional system: embryonic hierarchy, functional cohesion, institutional capacity, and relatively predictable interaction patterns. Instead of progressing toward systemic consolidation, the region remains marked by persistent fragmentation, episodic and reversible alliances, weak regional institutional architecture, and strategic indeterminacy. The analysis combines a historical reconstruction of the Middle East as a shatterbelt with a conceptual examination of contemporary regional dynamics and selected empirical illustrations. By revisiting Cohen's framework from a critical yet internal perspective, the article contributes to broader debates in political geography and geopolitical theory on regional transformation, post-hegemonic order, and the limits of system formation in deeply fragmented geopolitical environments.

Key Words:

Geopolitics, Middle East, Shatter Belt, Post-Hegemonic Order

¹ Editors note: Due to the fact that significant changes unfolded in the Middle East since the Workshop, editors have asked the author to revise the text.

² Associate professor, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Security Studies
ajzenhamer@fb.bg.ac.rs

Introduction

The Middle East is frequently described in contemporary geopolitical literature as a region marked by profound historical layering, geographic heterogeneity, and persistent political fragmentation. From Napoleon's expedition to Egypt, through colonial reconfigurations, to successive postwar and late-Cold War transformations, as well as their post-Cold War legacies, the region has emerged as a near-permanent epicenter of global, regional, and internal tensions. Such a configuration has rendered it a paradigmatic example of what Saul Bernard Cohen conceptualizes as a "shatterbelt" – a region that is simultaneously deeply divided internally and persistently drawn into the rivalry of external geostrategic realms (Cohen, 1963; 1992).

Over nearly six decades of theoretical work, Cohen developed a distinctive geopolitical framework grounded in possibilism, the hierarchical interaction of geostrategic realms and geopolitical regions, and an analytical differentiation of spatial attributes and patterns shaping the relationships between political actors. Within this framework, the concept of the shatterbelt – first systematically articulated in "Geography and Politics in a World Divided" (1963) and subsequently refined in works published during the 1980s and 1990s, constitutes one of the most influential, yet also most contested, components of Cohen's theoretical legacy (Kopanja, 2020).

The notion of the shatterbelt emerged from a synthesis of Hartshorne's distinction between centrifugal and centripetal forces (Hartshorne, 1950 pp.106-110) and Cohen's ambition to integrate regionalist and systemic insights into a coherent geopolitical scheme (Kopanja, 2020, p.64-65). In this sense, a shatterbelt is defined as the outcome of the simultaneous operation of internal fragmentation and external competition among major geostrategic realms, with neither of these factors being sufficient on its own to account for its existence.

However, in his 1992 article "Middle East Geopolitical Transformation: The Disappearance of a Shatterbelt," Cohen advances the provocative claim that the Middle East no longer fulfills the core criteria of a shatterbelt. While this post-Cold War diagnosis suggests that the region has moved beyond the structural logic of the classical shatterbelt and entered a qualitatively different phase of regional evolution, a closer examination of contemporary structural patterns reveals serious limitations to such an interpretation. In order to examine this transformation more systematically, this article introduces the conceptual category of a "developing regional system", derived analytically from Cohen's broader geopolitical framework but not explicitly formulated by Cohen himself. As conceptualized here, a developing regional system presupposes the emergence of at least an embryonic regional hierarchy (see Ajzenhamer, 2019) – even when such a hierarchy remains

contested, unstable, or only partially consolidated, and also presupposes the gradual formation of more recurrent and predictable patterns of regional interaction and a minimum level of functional cohesion. These criteria provide the analytical benchmark against which the contemporary Middle East will be assessed in the following section.

Cohen implicitly suggested that the Middle East might, over time, begin to evolve toward a condition that this article will refer to as a developing regional system (Cohen, 1992, p. 2-3, 10): a regional configuration in which political dynamics are increasingly generated from within, while dependence on direct great-power rivalry progressively diminishes. Within Cohen's regional taxonomy, this regional configuration may be understood as an intermediate stage situated between the classical shatterbelt (and, in certain instances, pressure zones)³ on the one hand, and what he defines as gateway regions on the other – regions in which great powers eventually develop cooperative patterns of interaction that transform previously conflict-prone spaces into functional links between opposing geostrategic realms (Cohen, 2005, p. 4).

Building on this claim, present article first examines the historical formation of the Middle East as a shatterbelt, its position across different phases of the international system, and the reasons why the contemporary Middle East no longer conforms to Cohen's classical definition of a shatterbelt. It then considers whether the region may be approaching a condition that this article conceptualizes as a developing regional system. Finally, the article demonstrates that although the Middle East has clearly moved beyond the structural logic of the classical shatterbelt, it nevertheless fails to fit neatly into the ideal-typical model of what we define as a developing regional system.

The analysis combines a historical narrative of the region's colonial, Cold War, and post-Cold War transformations with Cohen's theoretical apparatus, drawing on both his seminal works and subsequent systematizations and reinterpretations of his conceptual framework.

³ It is important to clearly distinguish between Cohen's notion of a pressure zone and our concept of a developing regional system. A pressure zone refers to a region still primarily structured by external great-power pressures and lacking internal hierarchy, whereas a developing regional system denotes a phase in which external determination weakens and regional actors begin to generate their own relatively stable patterns of power and interaction, even though full systemic consolidation has not yet been achieved.

Setting the Geopolitical Stage and the Formation of the Shatterbelt

The emergence of the modern Middle East as a geopolitical region is commonly traced to Napoleon's expedition to Egypt in 1798, which for the first time in modern history opened the region to European powers as an arena of strategic competition. The French campaign marked a critical turning point at which the Middle East ceased to function merely as a peripheral extension of the Ottoman Empire and became a space of external power projection by European imperial actors (Rogan, 2005, pp. 18–22).

Within Cohen's theoretical vocabulary, this period represents the phase in which the region's core geopolitical attributes crystallized: strategic passages (most notably the future Suez Canal), trade routes, concentrated urban agglomerations, and boundaries that increasingly assumed the role of political-geographical nodes. As Kopanja emphasizes (2020), Cohen conceives geopolitical structures as shaped through the interaction of historical cores, political centers, ecumene, and "non-conforming zones," all of which were clearly present in the Middle East throughout the nineteenth century.

Through the expansion of British footholds in the Persian Gulf, the consolidation of control over the Suez Canal from 1875 onward, and the projection of maritime power, the region was incorporated into the maritime geostrategic realm as one of its key strategic segments. At the same time, Russia pursued access to the "warm seas," introducing a distinctive dual geopolitical tension into the region: internal fragmentation associated with the erosion of the Ottoman order and external competition among great powers.

It is precisely this conjunction of deep internal political fragmentation and strong external conditioning that constitutes the foundational pattern of the shatterbelt, as later systematized by Cohen in his theoretical framework.

The First World War brought about the final collapse of the Ottoman Empire and the establishment of the League of Nations mandate system, through which new state boundaries were drawn largely irrespective of existing social, ethnic, and religious configurations. Colonial interventions thus produced an ambivalent outcome: while enabling the formation of new political units, they simultaneously embedded enduring lines of division into the very foundations of the region's political geography (Rogan, 2005, pp. 23-36).

From a theoretical perspective, Cohen interprets the mandate system as a process through which external powers imposed geopolitical patterns that did not emerge from the region's internal dynamics. Cohen (1992) stresses that geopolitical patterns are formed through networks linking centers of power, corridors of movement, trade routes, and borders. In the Middle East, these networks did not arise through

endogenous regional evolution but were externally projected, contributing to a long-term deficit of cohesion. It is for this reason that Cohen identified the Middle East as one of the most “mature” examples of a shatterbelt.

Following the Second World War, accelerated decolonization neither eliminated deep internal fragmentations nor diminished the role of great powers in shaping regional relations (Slugett, 2005, pp. 50-54; Louis, 2004). Arab–Israeli conflicts, rivalries among Egypt, Iraq, and Iran, and the control of energy flows further entrenched the Middle East as a space in which internal conflicts readily spilled across state boundaries – a defining characteristic of the shatterbelt in Cohen’s theory.

Cohen defines a shatterbelt as a strategically oriented region that is simultaneously deeply divided internally and caught in competition between great powers of opposing geostrategic realms (1992, p.2, 9). The Middle East conformed fully to this description until the final decade of the Cold War. In Cohen’s model of the global geopolitical system, the Cold War is characterized by a clear hierarchical structure composed of two dominant geostrategic realms – the maritime realm led by the United States and the continental realm under Soviet leadership, between which a number of geopolitical regions were situated. Within this structure, the Middle East lay outside the core geostrategic centers of the great powers, remained exposed to continuous projections of their power, and persisted in a state of deep fragmentation driven by local rivalries. This combination rendered it a typologically near-ideal case of a shatterbelt.

In his work Cohen demonstrates that the regional wars of 1956, 1967, and 1973 possessed a dual structure: internal rivalries among states and societies were amplified by external interventions and bloc alignments (1992, p.4,7). During the Cold War, at least six centers of power – Egypt, Saudi Arabia, Iran, Israel, Iraq, and Turkey, operated within the Middle East, their interests frequently colliding. Cohen further emphasizes that shatterbelts are characterized by a low degree of cohesion and a high level of competition among subregional actors, a pattern that the Middle East fully exemplified during this period.

The Fading of the Shatterbelt: Post–Cold War Reconfigurations

In his 1992 article, Cohen advances the thesis that the end of the Cold War leads to a qualitative transformation of the Middle East as a geopolitical region. According to his interpretation, the region enters a phase in which classical great-power rivalry weakens and the autonomy of regional actors increases, pointing to the possibility of an evolution from a shatterbelt toward what this article conceptualizes as a developing regional system.

Our argument is grounded in Cohen's developmental model of the global geopolitical system, within which geopolitical regions move from a stage of atomization toward hierarchical integration once they succeed in internally shaping their own patterns of equilibrium. From this perspective, the Middle East in the early 1990s is viewed as a region gradually departing from the status of a shatterbelt and entering an early phase of autonomous regional systemic development.

The classical definition of a shatterbelt presupposes the existence of a clear external axis of great-power rivalry. After 1991, the United States remained the only global power with a full capacity for power projection (Sokolsky, 2003), while Russia and China retained only limited and selective presences in the region. As a result, the Middle East ceased to be embedded in a symmetrical competition between opposing geostrategic realms, which, according to Cohen's typology, constitutes a fundamental structural precondition of a shatterbelt.

As Kopanja notes (2020), in the post-Cold War phase Cohen further develops new analytical categories – pressure zones, convergence zones, and gateway regions, designed to capture spaces in which direct rivalry among global powers no longer takes place, yet where instability remains pronounced. The Middle East increasingly fits this logic: it remains highly conflict-prone, but ceases to function as a central mediator of conflict between opposing geostrategic realms.

Developments after 2003, including the Iraq War, the processes triggered by the Arab Spring in 2011, and the rise of regional actors such as Turkey, Iran, Qatar, and the United Arab Emirates, further consolidated a configuration in which internal actors assume primacy in shaping regional dynamics (Alakel & Arab, 2025; Katz, 2025). External actors continue to exert significant influence, but the region is no longer structured around a clearly defined bipolar axis of conflict.

This evolution represents a substantial departure from Cohen's original definition of the shatterbelt, in which internal conflicts acquire full structural significance only in conjunction with intense and symmetrical external rivalry among great powers. In the contemporary context, the Middle East remains a highly conflictual space, yet it is increasingly difficult to describe it as a shatterbelt in the classical Cohenian sense and increasingly appropriate to view it as a complex and multipolar regional order in the making.

Cohen's 1992 claim that the Middle East had exited the status of a shatterbelt thus marked an important theoretical shift in the understanding of regional dynamics. According to his model, a shatterbelt can persist only so long as two structural conditions are simultaneously fulfilled: intense and relatively symmetrical penetration by great powers of opposing geostrategic realms, and deep internal fragmentation that renders the region persistently vulnerable. In the contemporary Middle Eastern context, both of these conditions have been weakened or

transformed. The region no longer fits the matrix of a bipolar international system, while internal actors have acquired growing autonomy in defining the directions of regional security.

Nevertheless, while the Middle East no longer conforms to Cohen's classical conception of a shatterbelt, the question arises as to whether it can develop the structural coherence, internal hierarchy, and functional autonomy necessary to be regarded as what this article terms a developing regional system.

A Regional System? Not Yet

Although Cohen's post-Cold War diagnosis suggests that the Middle East has moved beyond the status of a shatterbelt and entered a phase resembling what this article conceptualizes as a developing regional system, a closer examination of contemporary structural patterns reveals serious limitations to such an interpretation. Consistent with Cohen's broader theoretical framework, a developing regional system would presuppose the emergence of at least an embryonic regional hierarchy – even if such a hierarchy remains contested, unstable, or still in formation. In the Middle East, however, the presence of multiple regional power aspirants does not translate into a hierarchical order, but rather into a condition of persistent multipolar instability. Turkey, Iran, Saudi Arabia, and Israel possess substantial military, political, and economic capabilities, yet there is neither a minimal consensus regarding the legitimacy of their respective roles nor agreement on the boundaries of their influence (Alakel & Arab, 2025). The absence of an actor capable of stabilizing the regional order or imposing broadly accepted patterns of behavior prevents the consolidation of an internal power structure into a systemic form.

Empirically, this fragmentation of hierarchy is clearly observable in the case of Syria, which increasingly functions less as an arena of direct great-power rivalry and more as a “stress test” of a disrupted regional balance of power. Following the fall of Bashar al-Assad and the takeover of central authority by Hay'at Tahrir al-Sham (HTS) under Abu Mohammad al-Julani, Russia has adopted a restrained posture, focusing primarily on the preservation of its military facilities in Tartus and Hmeimim, while the United States exercises a mediating and verification-oriented role rather than direct strategic control. The core dynamics are instead generated by regional actors – most notably Israel, Turkey, and local forces, but in the absence of any shared regulatory framework capable of translating their competition into a stable regional hierarchy.

This structural deficit is further compounded by the prevailing patterns of interaction among regional actors. Within international relations theory and

geopolitical analysis alike, a region attains the quality of a “system” only when its actors exhibit recurring and relatively predictable patterns of cooperation and rivalry. The contemporary Middle East, by contrast, is characterized by ad hoc, instrumental, and reversible alliances, as well as multilayered and overlapping rivalries in which the same actors simultaneously function as partners and adversaries across different security, political, and economic domains. The dynamics of Israeli-Turkish competition in Syria are illustrative in this respect. Turkey’s military presence in northern Syria, its efforts to complete the containment of Syrian Kurdish actors and to support the new Syrian regime, as well as Israel’s preventive strikes against infrastructure formerly linked to Tehran – now perceived as a “portal” through which Ankara seeks to project its military power, derive from autonomous national strategies, yet fail to generate stable and predictable patterns of regional interaction. Rather than producing systemic cohesion, these dynamics result in a condition of persistent strategic fragmentation (Hazbun, 2018).

At the same time, the process of regional fragmentation has undergone a transformation. While the bloc-based fragmentation characteristic of the Cold War shatterbelt has faded, it has been replaced by deeper and more resilient forms of stratification. Contemporary conflicts are rooted in sectarian, ethnic, regime-based, and sub-state divisions that permeate the region and generate persistent political instability. In a developing regional system, fragmentation weakens in structural terms even when conflicts persist; in the Middle East, however, fragmentation remains systemic, albeit no longer organized around a single external axis – whether the U.S.–Soviet confrontation or subsequent U.S. balancing vis-à-vis Iran.

The absence of functional regional cohesion further reinforces this diagnosis. Although our concept does not require a high degree of institutionalization, a developing regional system presupposes at least a minimal capacity of the region to generate its own mechanisms of conflict management, normative coordination, and long-term alignment of interests. In the Middle East, however, regional institutions and forums lack the structural weight necessary to perform these functions, preventing the region from “carrying itself” as a system independently of external interventions.

By way of illustration, the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) functions primarily as an interest-based forum of wealthy Arab petro-monarchies and as an anti-Iranian alignment, rather than as an institutional representative of the geopolitical interests or strategic autonomy of the region as a whole (Kilibarda, Mladenović& Ajzenhamer, 2013). Conversely, the Arab League remains deeply embedded in a predominantly Westphalian logic: its member states prioritize the preservation of sovereign autonomy over the advancement of collective security, thereby severely limiting the organization’s integrative and regulatory capacity. Moreover, beyond ad hoc initiatives – such as the Baghdad Conference for Cooperation and Partnership

launched in 2021, there exists no adequate, exclusively regional framework capable of institutionalizing sustained cooperation among the key regional actors, including the Arab petro-monarchies, Iran, and Turkey. The absence of such a forum further underscores the lack of functional cohesion required for the consolidation of a developing regional system.

The security dilemma remains the dominant pattern of behavior. In a developing regional system, security ceases to operate exclusively according to a zero-sum logic and is partially replaced by pragmatic forms of cooperation and risk management. In the Middle East, however, security perceptions remain existentialized, military force retains a central role in political communication, and escalation remains a constantly available option. The Iranian–Israeli escalation during and after the 2023 Gaza war clearly illustrates this dynamic (Aldalala’a & Shukri, 2025). Military strikes, missile responses, and the spillover of violence into Lebanon, Iraq, and Syria unfolded on the basis of autonomous regional security calculations by Iran and Israel, while the United States responded belatedly, inconsistently, and without a coherent hegemonic strategy (Ajzenhamer, 2025a; Pratiwi, Qomara, & Syarafi, 2020). This pattern of behavior confirms that the region is no longer stabilized by an external regulator, yet simultaneously demonstrates that internal dynamics do not generate the degree of systemic discipline necessary for the consolidation of a developing regional system (Nowacka, 2023).

The same logic is observable beyond regional conflict arenas, becoming evident in extra-regional crises.

A further indication of the erosion of external hegemonic discipline can be observed in the positioning of the Gulf states toward the war in Ukraine. From the moment Russia recognized the self-proclaimed republics of Donetsk and Luhansk, Gulf actors adopted differentiated and carefully calibrated responses, revealing a broader pattern of strategic hedging rather than alignment (Szalai, 2023). Saudi Arabia, the United Arab Emirates, and Qatar publicly supported diplomatic efforts aimed at de-escalation, yet refrained from explicitly condemning Russia’s invasion of Ukraine or joining Western sanctions regimes. Notably, the United Arab Emirates – then holding a temporary seat on the United Nations Security Council, twice abstained from votes aimed at holding Russia accountable and condemning its military actions.

Qatar adopted a more explicit rhetorical stance in support of Ukrainian sovereignty, yet similarly avoided participation in sanctions. At the same time, none of these states recognized the separatist entities in eastern Ukraine, and all ultimately supported the UN General Assembly resolution condemning the invasion and calling for the withdrawal of Russian forces. This pattern reflects a deliberate strategy of hedging – signaling continued partnership with the United States while simultaneously preserving strategic autonomy vis-à-vis Russia.

From a regional-systemic perspective, such behavior is highly indicative. It demonstrates that the United States no longer possesses the capacity to enforce alignment or discipline even among its closest Middle Eastern partners. Yet this erosion of hegemonic authority does not translate into the emergence of a coherent regional order. Instead, it reinforces a condition in which regional actors pursue autonomous and interest-driven positioning without converging toward shared norms, hierarchies, or institutionalized coordination. As such, the weakening of U.S. hegemonic influence contributes not to regional system consolidation, but to a prolonged phase of strategic indeterminacy.

This dynamic is further compounded by the multiplication of subregional centers of power – including a now significantly weakened Hezbollah, Iraqi Shi‘a militias, the Houthis, and various Syrian factions, which further fragments the regional space and undermines the possibility of its hierarchical consolidation. Empirical accounts of episodes such as the so-called “twelve-day war” involving Iran, Israel, and the United States, in which military strikes, unilateral (and largely symbolic) declarations of victory, and calls for restraint followed one another in rapid succession and without a clear systemic framework, point to the absence of a stable external hegemonic architecture as well as to the region’s inability to generate a sustainable order on its own (Ajzenhamer, 2025b).

Finally, the problem of insufficient regional systematization is also reflected in the indeterminate spatial boundaries of the region.⁴ A developing regional system presupposes a relatively clear differentiation between core and periphery, as well as limited and manageable zones of overlap. By contrast, the Middle East is characterized by fluid and overlapping spatial configurations encompassing the Levant, the Persian Gulf, the Eastern Mediterranean, and the Red Sea, within which centers of power are dispersed in an essentially anarchic manner. This spatial indeterminacy further undermines the consolidation of the region as a coherent system.

In this sense, from a geopolitical perspective, the contemporary Middle East occupies a theoretical interstitial space between the two Cohenian concepts under discussion: it no longer fulfills the structural conditions of a classical shatterbelt, yet it simultaneously lacks the hierarchy, cohesion, and predictability that we associate with a developing regional system.

Concluding Remarks

⁴ An illustrative example of this spatial indeterminacy is the fact that Israel today is no longer surrounded exclusively by traditional Arab neighbors. As a consequence of Turkey’s entrenched military and political presence in northern Syria, Israel has, in a de facto geopolitical sense, acquired Turkey as an additional “neighboring” regional power, despite the absence of any de jure border between the two states. For a broader discussion of Israel’s evolving border environment, see Cohen (2020).

This study has taken as its point of departure Cohen's post-Cold War thesis that, by the late twentieth century, the Middle East had ceased to function as a shatterbelt and had begun a transition toward a developing regional system. The analysis of the region's historical formation as a shatterbelt, its role within the Cold War structure of the international system, and contemporary patterns of regional dynamics has enabled a critical reassessment of this claim. The central finding may be summarized as follows: the contemporary Middle East no longer fulfills the structural conditions of a classical shatterbelt, yet it likewise does not possess the key characteristics that we associate with a developing regional system. The region therefore occupies a theoretical intermediate position between these two ideal-typical models.

Historical analysis has shown that, throughout the nineteenth and much of the twentieth century, the Middle East corresponded closely to Cohen's definition of a shatterbelt. Deep internal fragmentation, combined with intense and symmetrical external penetration by great powers, rendered the region particularly sensitive to global shifts in power. During the Cold War, the Middle East was firmly embedded within the hierarchical structure of the bipolar international system, with local conflicts regularly amplified and redirected through external intervention and bloc alignment. In this period, the region constituted an almost paradigmatic empirical example of a shatterbelt in Cohen's theoretical sense.

However, the end of the Cold War produced profound changes in the external structure of regional security (Katz, 2025). The weakening of symmetrical great-power competition, the disappearance of a bipolar axis of rivalry, and the increasing autonomy of regional actors have undermined the sustainability of the shatterbelt model. As demonstrated in the analysis, the contemporary Middle East is no longer a space in which global rivalries are systematically refracted through local conflicts. External powers retain significant influence, but they no longer structure the region through a clearly defined and stable hierarchy. In Cohen's typology, this fulfills the first major condition for transcending the shatterbelt.

Yet the analysis has also shown that a weakening of external determination does not automatically lead to the consolidation of a regional system. A developing regional system, as we understand it, presupposes at least an embryonic hierarchy, recurring interaction patterns, functional cohesion, and a capacity for internally generated stabilizing mechanisms. In the Middle East, none of these elements are sufficiently developed. Instead of a hierarchical order, the region exhibits persistent multipolarity without consensus regarding the legitimacy or scope of regional influence of key actors.

Empirical findings consistently indicate the absence of structural preconditions for systemic consolidation. Although reduced external determinism has enabled greater autonomy for regional actors, this autonomy has not resulted in the formation of a

stable hierarchy or recognizable order. Regional dynamics remain largely unregulated and fragmented, while competition unfolds without mechanisms capable of translating it into systemic equilibrium. Rather than stabilizing, autonomous action produces prolonged strategic uncertainty (Hazbun, 2018).

This outcome is closely linked to interaction patterns that remain episodic and context-dependent. Alliances are temporary and instrumental, rivalries multilayered and fluid, and the roles of individual actors vary across issue areas. Such a configuration does not generate predictability or normative expectations but sustains a condition of enduring strategic fragmentation incompatible with Cohen's notion of regional systemhood.

At the same time, fragmentation has not disappeared but has assumed new, deeper forms. With the decline of Cold War bloc divisions, the region did not enter a phase of structural homogenization. Instead, it has remained stratified along sectarian, ethnic, regime-based, and sub-state lines. These forms of fragmentation have become durable features of regional politics and constitute an internal obstacle to systemic consolidation, independent of the external constellation of power.

The institutional dimension reinforces this conclusion. Existing regional organizations lack the capacity to function as vehicles of collective security or long-term coordination of interests. They remain either constrained by the interests of narrow groups of actors or bound by the sovereignty-centered logic of their member states, without the ability to generate functional cohesion at the regional level. The absence of an inclusive, stable regional format encompassing key actors further limits prospects for systemic consolidation.

The security dimension is particularly illustrative. The persistence of the security dilemma, the existentialization of threat perceptions, and continued reliance on military force as a primary instrument of political communication indicate that the region has not moved into a phase in which conflicts are managed through institutionalized or normatively stabilized mechanisms. Actor autonomy does not produce self-regulation but sustains a high level of instability.

Additionally, the weakening of external hegemonic discipline – observable even beyond the immediate regional context, does not lead to the emergence of an alternative regional order. Instead, it prolongs a condition of strategic indeterminacy in which regional actors operate autonomously, yet without converging toward shared rules, hierarchies, or institutionalized coordination.

Finally, the spatial indeterminacy of the region further undermines its systemic articulation. The overlap of multiple subregional spaces and the absence of a clear differentiation between core and periphery prevent the formation of a stable

regional framework. Under such conditions, the Middle East remains an open and fragmented space, unable to consolidate into a coherent regional system.

Taken together, these findings indicate that the contemporary Middle East constitutes a theoretical interstitial space between shatterbelt and developing regional system. It has moved beyond the logic of the shatterbelt but has not entered the phase of a developing regional system. This ambivalent position renders the region analytically challenging and underscores the need to reinterpret, rather than abandon, Cohen's framework – adapting it to the structural realities of current Middle Eastern dynamics.

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The Modern Shatterbelts: Testing the Theory of Borders in Global “Regional System”

Marta Zorko¹ and Andrea Bilandžija²

Abstract:

The Shatterbelt Theory is deeply embedded in classical and contemporary geopolitical thought (Fairgrieve, 1917; Whittlesey, 1942; Hartshorne, 1944; Cohen 1963; Huntington, 1997). When labelling regions and explaining world order(s) contacting areas have always been thoroughly challenged. Both from the perspective of defining and belonging as well as from the aspect of power-politics. The aim of this paper is two-folded. First part is oriented towards an overview of shatterbelt theory through development of contemporary border theory while the second part applies two combined theories onto contemporary geopolitical order showing old/new territorial discrepancies and cutting edges. The focus is on macro geopolitical level, but national, and micro levels will be taken into consideration as well. The presumption is that old division lines still exist while new fractures emerge each day. The Shatterbelt Theory is both time and space susceptible but, in some cases, geographical givens are hard to avoid. This paper highlights abovementioned discrepancies and constants. There are few challenges related to Eurocentric, and later so-called western worldview. As it constructed world maps and named world order(s) it has left huge impact on shatterbelts regions on one hand and made its own definition ambiguous on the other. These open-end definitions leave border zones in the constant flux and dependent on current distribution of world power. All mentioned categories are highly subjective making geopolitical analysis the main tool for such categorization and research. Therefore, methodological concept of this paper is embedded in geopolitical analysis of current world power distribution including four key factors – geographical power, social power, economy power and military power – aiming towards redefinition of world regional system, potential shatterbelts and contemporary frontiers. We argue that the concept of frontiers (wide border zones prior to the phase of forming nation states) are being reintroduced in the form of shatterbelts and should be used to define such areas instead of regions. Modern shatterbelts are simultaneously places of hybrid warfare and forgotten no man’s lands. Place of hybrid warfare in a sense of neighboring powers playground and no man’s land in a sense of definition and belonging.

Key words:

Geopolitics, Shatterbelts, Borders, World Regional System, Political Cartography

¹ Full Professor, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Political

² Ph.D. Candidate, University of Zagreb, Faculty of Political Science

Introduction

The innovation of this approach is in its emphasis on borders and border theory in shattered spaces. The ambiguity of shatterbelts and crush zones worldwide relies upon definition of where such contested regions begin and where they end. Border theory and the significance of borders in the context of shatterbelts should highlight how borders shape and influence the dynamics of conflict, competition, and fragmentation within these regions. Borders act as physical and symbolic markers of identity, territory, and control, and understanding their role is crucial for comprehending the complexities of geopolitical processes within shatterbelts. On the other hand, contested regions are hard to define in strict geographical sense, they are geopolitically fluid, and identification of their specific borders is an impossible task. Moreover, such regions have been labeled without respect towards its heterogeneity and/or any kind of regional ownership of the process whatsoever. Identification of crush points leading towards layered zones of various intensity of contestation, rather than regions, may help in understanding shattered spaces both in theory and practice. Starting from the assumption that such spaces are not homogeneous regions with clearly defined borders, but rather multilayered areas of geopolitical conflicts of interest, considering them within the framework of frontiers is helpful for understanding its dynamics and could lead towards more clearly geographical understanding of their spreading.

Labelling spaces and giving them etiquettes of meaning is in the core of classical geopolitics global view since Mackinder's Heartland theory (1904). While such an approach helps in understanding the global world order of given time it simultaneously produces three-fold discrepancies (O Tuathail, Dalby and Routledge, 2007). The first one is related to the presumption that such big world regions are homogenous. From Mackinder's Heartland to Huntington's civilizations, geopolitical labelling creates falsely consolidated spaces with imposed meanings. The second shortage is related to labelling theory in general with labels and etiquettes that impose or subtract power from places. Finally, the third problem is related to labelling usually leading towards opposed world regional system with conflicted characteristics. Moreover, when labelling regions and explaining world order(s), contacting areas have always been thoroughly challenged. Both from the perspective of defining and belonging as well as from the aspect of power-politics. Such in-between spaces were named shatter zones or shatterbelts. And while shatterbelt theory recognizes conflicting meaning of the world order it also depends on particular time-space relation. Even more, practical reasoning of shattered zones in given time frame vary due to the subjectivity, perspective, and imaginations of the author. Because of the ambiguity of such places and its bordering nature it is necessary to test concepts of border studies and border theory in general for understanding of such regional systems.

The major quantity of papers mentioning shatterbelts do not emphasize the borders as key factor in analysis (Fairgrieve, 1917; Whittlesey, 1942; Hartshorne, 1944;

Cohen 1963; Huntington, 1997). On the contrary, it is mostly stated that borders of such regions are being fluid. One must ask oneself how it is possible for borders to be fluid in contested spaces, and if so, what are the actual fragile lines of opposition? Having that in mind we argue that whole shatterbelts are border zones rather than regions and as such might be fluid due to the power play in contesting centers. Therefore, it is essential to apply border theory when analyzing such spaces, emphasizing the reintroduction of frontiers for shattered spaces: zones rather than regions. The second challenge of existing shatterbelt theory is the unit of analysis. Some authors mention clusters of fragile states (Mahan, 1890; Fairgrieve, 1917), some authors refer to fragile regions in general (Cohen, 1963; Ó Tuathail, 1997; Huntington, 1996; Flint, 2004; Murphy & O'Loughlin, 2009; Dodds, 2017). The question here are levels taken into consideration – or if you want – the interchangeable nature of fragile lines that consist of micro spaces, national states and peripheries of global play. Rather than quantifying and calculating fragility of the states in shattered region for making it fit the definition, the complexity of shatter spaces should start from global view (current world order and its fraud lines), the role of states along those lines in question, and micro hotspots along the way. Borders, both physical and symbolic, are central to the functioning of shatterbelts and the dynamics described by the theory.

Borders often define the spatial extent of different ethnic, linguistic, or religious groups within a shatterbelt. The presence of diverse identities and ethnic groups within close proximity can lead to tensions and conflicts over resources, political representation, or cultural dominance. Borders can act as markers of identity and serve as catalysts for identity-based conflicts. Other than Identity and ethnicity-based reasons, borders act as dividing lines. These lines of separation can be highly contentious, as different groups may have competing claims over the same territory. Conflicting territorial claims and border disputes can contribute to the overall instability in shatterbelts. Furthermore, the aspect of security and control is driven through the control of borders and borderlines. Borders are critical for states and actors within shatterbelts to assert control over their territories. They act as a mean to regulate the movement of people, goods, and ideas across political boundaries. Disputes over border control, such as border security, smuggling, or migration, can intensify existing conflicts and contribute to the overall instability in shatterbelts. Border theory in this context is also important since shattered spaces often attract the attention of external powers seeking to exert influence or control over the region. Borders become contested spaces where geopolitical competition takes place. External powers may support different factions within the shatterbelt, leading to proxy conflicts and power struggles along the borders. Finally, in its core definition shatterbelts are characterized by political, social, and ideological fragmentation. Borders within these regions can further contribute to the fragmentation, as different groups may strive for autonomy or independence based on ethnic, cultural, or political differences. This fragmentation can lead to the creation of new borders or the redrawing of existing ones, further complicating the geopolitical landscape.

But, in all those cases one fact remains unclear: What is the nature of borders of shattered spaces? Are they fluid or hard? If they are fluid what changes their nature, and how is it possible that ambiguous space is contested? From the other perspective, if they are hard, solid and defined, why and how are those areas being challenged?

This paper suggests three answers to these questions. The first one is breaking through state subjectivity and contribution of the concept of fragile states to shatterbelt theory. The second one is connected to the nature of borders in shattered spaces. Those borders can be fluid, influenced by contestation, evolving geopolitical dynamics, and changing alliances. While some borders may start out as hard and defined, the contested nature of these spaces can lead to challenges and attempts to redefine or undermine existing borders. Finally, the third one is related to layered circles of power and center-periphery relations perspective in shatterbelt spaces.

The aim of this paper is two-folded. First part is oriented towards an overview of shatterbelt theory and development of contemporary borders and border theory while the second part applies two combined theories onto contemporary geopolitical order showing old/new territorial discrepancies and cutting edges. The focus is on macro geopolitical level, but national, and micro levels will be taken into consideration as well. The presumption is that old division lines still exist while new fractures emerge each day. All mentioned categories are subjective, making qualitative geopolitical analysis the main tool for such categorization and research. Therefore, methodological concept of this paper is embedded in geopolitical analysis of current world power distribution including four key factors – geographical power, social power, economy power and military power – aiming towards redefinition of world regional system, potential shatterbelts and contemporary frontiers.

This paper will provide a state-of-the-art overview of shatterbelt theory from the angle of borders and border realities included. In the second part border theory will be introduced and tested on already defined shatterbelt regions while third part will test findings in practical surrounding of contemporary crush zones and geopolitical flashing points. We argue that the concept of frontiers (wide border zones prior to the phase of forming nation states) are being reintroduced in the form of shatterbelts. Modern shatterbelts are simultaneously places of hybrid warfare and forgotten no man's lands. Place of hybrid warfare in a sense of neighboring powers playground and no man's land in a sense of definition and belonging. Thus, shatterbelts are modern frontiers and border zones and should be analyzed through the complexity of contemporary world system theory marking it contested spaces in a form of modern frontiers.

State of the Art – Shatterbelt Theory with a critical twist?

Classical geopolitical thought theory and their authors highlight constant fight between land and sea powers. Their contact points are defined as contested

nonetheless the name given to such spaces – from crush zones, shatter zones, shatterbelts or geopolitical flashpoints. Starting with Mackinder, the key to ruling the world was Eastern Europe – contested point of contact between Heartland and Rimland (land and sea powers) (Mackinder, 1904). Although Mackinder does not define Eastern Europe as a shatterbelt it is evident that he gives the upmost importance to this geographical region, naming it the key for ruling the World. Mackinder believed that the Heartland, with its vast resources, strategic location, and relative inaccessibility, held the key to global power. He saw Eastern Europe as a crucial region due to its geographical position at the heart of the Eurasian landmass. In his view, whoever controlled this region could potentially control the entire “World-Island”, a term he used to describe the interconnected landmass of Europe, Asia, and Africa. Mackinder argued that the Heartland's central location, abundant resources (such as coal and iron), and the potential to mobilize a large population gave it an inherent advantage. He argued that control over this region would provide the ability to project power outward and control the surrounding “Rimland” regions, which included Western Europe, East Asia, and the coastal areas of Eurasia. In essence, Mackinder saw Eastern Europe as a key to world domination because he believed that controlling this region would grant a nation immense geopolitical power. By dominating the Heartland, a state could potentially control the vast resources, transportation routes, and influence over neighboring regions, thus establishing a position of global supremacy. But starting with this theory one must recognize that Eastern Europe is a vague term, at least when it comes to its borders in specific time period, orientation and scope.

It's worth noting that Mackinder's Heartland Theory has been subject to various criticisms and debates among scholars, and the world has undergone significant geopolitical changes since he first proposed his ideas in the early 20th century. However, his theories continue to be influential in the field of geopolitics and have contributed to discussions on the strategic significance of certain regions in global affairs. Moreover, it makes him the first author that contributed to the theory of shatterbelt spaces in general setting the ground for labelling world regions and contested spaces between them. Like Mackinder, Hartshorne, naming it Shatter zones, defines Eastern and Southeastern Europe as a crucial region(s) for world stability. Calling upon creating World organization(s) in order to provide security and stability he implies that “stability in the shatter zone cannot be achieved by absorption from the outside, ... nor by the reestablishment of free but hopelessly small units, but only by integration into a free association of free peoples, capable of providing a major element of its own defense” (Hartshorne, 1944: 214).” Moreover, “The problem of security as the requirements of modern economy demand a more effective organization of large blocks in this part of Europe, blocks large enough to impose some considerable obstacle, checking any potential new effort of German expansion” (Hartshorne, 1944: 212). Writing in a particular historical moment, he sought for mechanisms of providing world peace and found one in uniting capabilities of Europe.

Furthermore, Whittlesley (1942) divided the world into distinct regions based on both physical and cultural characteristics. His classification system aimed to capture the diversity and uniqueness of different areas across the globe. Although not mentioning the concept of shatterbelts at first, he defines the zone of Eastern Europe challenging as well. His follower Saul Cohen (1963, 2015) has made important contributions to the understanding of shatterbelts and gateways. In his new geopolitical division of the world, the spaces that do not belong to either of the two major powers are called “Gateways” and “Shatterbelts”. Regarding shatterbelts, Cohen describes them as regions characterized by their fragmentation, instability, and propensity for conflict due to their location between powerful and competing geopolitical forces. These areas often experience internal divisions, ethnic or religious tensions, and are subject to the influence of external actors vying for control. Shatterbelts are seen as zones of geopolitical contestation and are crucial in the analysis of global power dynamics. As for gateways, Cohen refers to them as strategic locations that hold significant geopolitical and economic importance due to their function as transit points or channels of access between regions. Gateways can be natural, such as waterways or mountain passes, or artificial, like major transportation hubs or chokepoints. These areas are essential for the movement of goods, people, and ideas, and they can shape trade routes, alliances, and conflicts. In his analysis the key emphasis is on stability, so war and peace theory in this context should be mentioned as well.

At the beginning of the 21st century, Cohen developed Shatterbelts theory and defines it as: “a region torn by internal conflicts whose fragmentation is increased by the intervention of external major powers” (Cohen; 2015: 9). As he warns, great powers are prone to meddling in political, military, and economic affairs within the states of unstable regions with the aim of providing support to their clients. “Shatterbelts, which form zones of contact between realms, may be divided into separate subplates, such as compression zones, by such movement or totally subsumed within one realm. Regions, or medium-sized plates, may also change their shapes and boundaries as they shift within realms or from one realm to another, becoming convergence zones. Compression zones, or regional subplates, may be formed or disappear with shifting within regional plates” (Cohen, 2015: 40). “Compression zones”—smaller atomized areas that lie within or between geopolitical regions – are torn apart by the combination of civil wars and the interventionist actions of neighboring countries” (Cohen, 2015: 9). Cohen explains that: “Shatterbelts and their boundaries are fluid” (Cohen, 2015: 48). For such a concept peace and war theory with its peace-building and peace-making mechanisms is prone to creation and re-creation of shatterbelts or frontiers of insecurity. So, the key question is how to interpret the insecurity and what are the final limits of border fluidity in a sense of definition of shatterbelt spaces. A contemporary author Phil Kelly also rethinks shatterbelt theory through the concept of security/insecurity. His analysis includes several world regions as contemporary shatterbelts. He identifies “four conceptual problems encountered in traditional descriptions as a means toward improving the term's utility: shatterbelt uniqueness,

dynamism, location, and escalation potential” (Kelly, 1986: 161). As explained, the important parts of this concept include individual case study approach (uniqueness); time specification (dynamism); geographical factor (location) and (in)security (escalation potential). All of the abovementioned categories will be included in our analysis. Furthermore, Kelly suggests a new definition for shatterbelts: “a shatterbelt is a geographic region over whose control great powers seriously compete. Great powers compete because they perceive strong interests for doing so and because opportunities are present for establishing alliance footholds with states of the region. Consequently, a high potential exists for escalation of conflict into major power warfare. A shatterbelt originates when rival great powers have footholds in a single area. Six contemporary world regions met the criteria of this standard: the Middle East, East Asia, Southeast Asia, Sub-Saharan Africa, Middle America, and South Asia”. (Kelly, 1986: 161) Closer to our proposition of modern frontiers, Kelly recognizes competitive frame as important one but keeps referring to such spaces in a form of region(s).

Other authors engaged in shatterbelt theory are using the term in similar matter – the one of (in)stability. Biondich (2014) uses the terms for zones of violence in WW1, while Bugge (2002) also engage historical perspective in Eastern Europe geographical area. Similarly, Bartov & Weitz (2013) are doing historical perspective in their study oriented towards European empires and their peripheries. From this perspectives, center-periphery theory seems relevant for development of shatterbelt concept in this particular timeframe. Antun Gosar (2000: 107) test this centre-periphery idea on Slovenia stating that: “Europe in general is in a great state of change. States uniting with difficulty, states collapsing in pain, newly freed states struggling for new political, economic, and social identities - it is a region in a true transition”. He is focused on, as he calls it, “European Shatter Belt, formerly known as ‘Eastern Europe’”. And yes, most of the authors dealing with crush zones, zones of instability and shatterbelts name eastern part of Europe as a fragile one although does not really explain what Eastern Europe means in geographical sense. Same region is in the focus of later Saul Cohen’s (2005) work where he studies geopolitical implications of U.S. influence in a vast Eurasian Convergence Zone, within which the influence of major world geopolitical powers (Maritime Europe, Russia, China, India, and Japan) intersects. After a comprehensive analysis of the U.S. involvement in key segments of the Zone (specifically Eastern Europe, Transcaucasus, Central Asia, and East Asia), Cohen proceeds to explore the economic, demographic, and military strategic interests of major geopolitical actors in this region. Eastern Europe is not uncommonly defined as a shatterbelt. George W. Hoffman (1972: 265) even uses singular to apostrophe its importance. He defines the Shatterbelt as: “between the Soviet Union and what is generally called Western Europe bordered by four seas – Baltic, Adriatic, Aegean and Black seas – is located an area which in many ways occupies a central position in Euroasia. Various names are given to this area – East Central Europe, Eastern Europe, Central Europe, Middle Europe – but geographers for some times have been calling this region “The Shatter-Belt””. Closest to defining

the region in geographical sense he still identifies that space in regional sense giving it homogenous meaning and calling upon non-existing regional characteristics.

Other than by attempts in defining geographical location shatterbelts are being defined by conflict potential. David Reilly (2000: 48) divides states on those with high-risk and low-risk conflict behavior bearing in mind shatterbelt areas and globalization processes. By examining how conflict behavior has changed over time, and in conjunction with trade openness, his results indicate that “domestic instability and fragmentation are more directly tied to high-risk state behavior than are systemic influences. In contrast, the probability that low-risk states originate or participate in conflicts, and resort to violence, is tied to international factors”. His findings suggest that “trade openness has an important pacifying effect on high-risk states, but appears to be irrelevant to the conflict behavior of all others”(Ibidem).

Phil Kelly suggests that “most 20th-century wars among major powers have originated in shatterbelts, geographic regions from which local turmoil escalates to serious competition among outside larger states. Because of the concept's impredenseness, the relevance of shatterbelts to war and peace largely has been ignored within international affairs literature” (Kelly, 1986: 161). Two other authors, Paul R. Hensel and Paul F. Diehl, tested the theory of shatterbelts and their conflict potential in empirical rather than as they call it “impressionistic” manner. Their findings are similar to qualitative contributions as: “the results indicate that shatterbelts are more likely than other regions to be the setting for interstate wars, but this is largely because they also generate more militarized disputes that can go to war, rather than because of any greater likelihood that those lesser conflicts will escalate. Internal conflicts were also more common in shatterbelts, although the effect was more modest than with interstate conflict. The portion of conflicts, especially interstate wars, that involve outside intervention is greater in shatterbelts. Yet, given that intervention occurs, conflicts in shatterbelts (with the exception of interstate wars) are not more likely to expand further or to include major powers as the intervening parties. Shatterbelt conflicts, both internal and external, were also generally considerably longer and bloodier than conflicts in other regions” (Hensel and Diehl, 1994: 33).

But, regarding contemporary space/place relations one must ask themselves is it even possible to rethink shatterbelt theory through solely territorial lenses and how could cyberspace be included. The emphasis on competition between sea and land powers seems a bit outdated in an era of virtual interconnections and contestations. How is it possible for territorial flash points to remain as important as ever? There are two possible explanations. The first one is related to the thesis of learned behavior. So, power games and territorial contestations mirrored to outer space and cyber space as well. Although they lack a territorial component, these spaces also become arenas of power struggle, where states and other subjects of international relations engage in familiar principles of competition and rivalry. While shatterbelts originally referred to geopolitical regions characterized by multiple conflicting interests and contested boundaries, the concept can be applied to other domains,

including the cyber realm. In the cyber context, a shatterbelt can be understood as an area or zone where different actors with diverse interests and agendas engage in intense competition, conflict, or power struggles. These conflicts may involve issues such as data sovereignty, cybersecurity, information warfare, or control over critical infrastructure. Shatterbelts in cyberspace can emerge due to a variety of factors. These may include geopolitical rivalries, economic interests, ideological differences, or attempts to exert influence and control over digital networks and resources. As various actors with different goals and capabilities operate within the cyber domain, they may vie for control, seek to shape norms and standards, or engage in offensive and defensive cyber operations. Similar to traditional shatterbelts, cyber shatterbelts exhibit fluid boundaries and contested spaces. The nature of cyberspace allows for rapid and dynamic shifts in power and influence, as actors adapt their strategies and tactics in response to changing circumstances. Shatterbelts in the cyber domain can also be characterized by ambiguity, as the attribution of cyber-attacks and the determination of responsibility can be challenging. Furthermore, the interconnected nature of cyberspace means that conflicts and power struggles within one defined or named shatterbelt can have ripple effects across other regions or even globally. Cybersecurity incidents, such as large-scale data breaches or disruptive cyber-attacks, can impact multiple actors and regions, leading to broader destabilization and tensions and goes beyond regional contexts.

Visualization of data in political cartography and limitations of the research

Critical twist refers both to new subjectivity and new spaces of struggle while engaging the same classical mechanisms of geopolitical power games in contemporary environment. Therefore, there are several restrictions in visualization of potential world orders and world power distribution. Cartography and visualization are inherently subjective and can be influenced by the biases and perspectives of the mapmakers or data analysts. Representing power distribution requires making choices about what factors to include, how to classify or categorize data, and what symbols or colors to use, which can introduce unintentional or intentional biases.

Moreover, power dynamics in the world are constantly evolving, with shifts in economic, political, and military influence among countries and regions. Keeping up with these changes and accurately reflecting the current distribution of power can be challenging, especially as emerging powers gain prominence and traditional power structures undergo transformations. Therefore time-space continuum should be taken into consideration as well. Additionally, reliable and up-to-date data on power distribution can be difficult to obtain, especially in countries with limited transparency or political complexities. Data collection methods, access to information, and the quality of data sources can vary across regions, making it challenging to ensure accuracy and consistency in power visualizations. Finally, power distribution is not solely based on a single indicator or factor but is influenced

by multiple interrelated variables, including economic strength, military capabilities, technological advancements, diplomatic influence, cultural influence, and more.

Shihai Wu and Jianzhong Yan (2022: 1109) suggest future elements for shatterbelt research in China (as a new emerging power). Their ideas include: “1) constructing a theoretical analysis framework of shatter belt, and strengthening the visualization, quantification, and simulation of shatter belt by combining big data and other analytical methods; 2) strengthening the examination of the evolution processes and driving mechanisms of shatter belts in China's peripheral regions and along the Belt and Road, and identifying and assessing the geopolitical risks in shatter belts; and 3) exploring the ways to integrate shatter belts by combining the thought of a community with shared future for mankind”. Strongly agreeing with the first one the model and map of current shaterbelt areas will be analyzed in following chapter.

If new subjectivity (other than states) is included as well as new areas of battle (or contested spaces e.g. cyberspace) there are practical challenges in visualization of potential contemporary shatterbelts and fraud lines. For example, when John B. Sparks tried to create visual representation of the history of world power, his Histomap had no geographical data whatsoever.

Picture 1: Histomap and its perspectives.³

³ Source: Sparks, John B. (1931) The Histomap. Four Thousand Year of World History. Relative Power of Contemporary States, Nations, and Empires. Chicago: Histomap Inc., Cartography Associates, David Rumsey Collection, available on Visual Capitalist, <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/11/histomap-big.html>, 7/7/2023.

Other than time continuum, visualization of new subjects other than states is challenging using classical cartography methods. Kaplan (1996) suggest hologram of mobile axes of power as one of possible solutions in such contested spaces (in his case Africa). Moreover, new spaces of contestation, from outer Space to cyber are impossible to visualize in 2D cartographical solutions. Holographic visualization refers to a three-dimensional representation of data or information using holographic technology. In the context of world order or power, holographic visualization can be applied to depict the distribution and dynamics of global power relations in a spatial and interactive manner.

One of the solutions for power related visualizations are power-relations maps. This kind of maps do not follow geographical realities but introduce relations as a key factor for visualization. These kinds of cartograms show more accurately and in real time relations rather than geographically correct data and facts. Power-related maps and diagrams are useful tools for presenting complex information, enhancing understanding, supporting decision-making, and fostering discussions about global power dynamics. They provide valuable insights into the distribution, dynamics, and implications of power, contributing to a deeper understanding of geopolitics and international relations. Power-related maps and diagrams help simplify and visualize complex data related to power distribution, such as geopolitical influence, economic strength, military capabilities, or diplomatic relationships.

Picture 2 – Raffestin’s Power-relation map.⁴

⁴ Source: Raffestin, Claude; Lopreno, Dario; Pasteur, Yvan (1995). *Géopolitique et Histoire*. Paris: Payot.

By presenting information in a visual format, these visualizations make it easier to grasp and understand patterns, trends, and relationships. They can present spatial relationships, highlight regional disparities, or demonstrate the concentration or diffusion of power across different areas. Power-related maps and diagrams often generate discussion, debate, and further exploration of global power dynamics. They serve as a catalyst for critical thinking, academic research, and policy discourse. By visualizing power distribution, these visualizations can stimulate conversations about equity, geopolitics, international relations, and the distribution of resources and influence. In this context it helps in showing and analyzing contemporary shatterbelt spaces as well.

The conceptualization of used data

Suggested visualizations request data background related to rankings of powers and world power distribution. Hence, the aforementioned enumerations necessitate revision to encompass all four dimensions of geopolitical power: 1) geographical power, encompassing factors such as size, location, and resource endowment; 2) social and political power, encompassing demographic characteristics, ideological influence, and public diplomacy; 3) economic power, reflecting the economic indicators and factors that influence it; and 4) military power. Geographical power is rooted in parameters such as territorial expanse, state positioning, and availability of natural resources. Social and political power incorporates demographic statistics and the political conditions necessary for stability. Visualizations of economic power are contingent upon the data considered and may vary accordingly (Zorko and Cesarec, forthcoming 2024). The WorldAtlas combines different economical parameters and the data because: “golden palaces on public display are not always the full story behind a country's financial worth. Thanks to the digital age, the accuracy of modern economic data can now reveal whether nations are a financial success or a disaster in disguise. To do so, three metrics measure the wealth of a country: First, purchasing power parity (PPP) is a metric used to compare the buying power of different countries' currencies, measured by the price of certain goods in each country. Second, gross domestic product (GDP) is an annual measure of the market value of all the final goods and services produced and sold in a country. 'GDP per capita (PPP)' is therefore found by dividing GDP by the total population after adjusting for PPP. Last, GNI per capita is the gross national income divided by population. After accounting for the relevant 2023 data from the International Monetary Fund, these Richest Countries in the World stand out amongst their peers.” (www.worldatlas.com, 3/27/23)

The final aspect, military power, should also be approached with a multi-dimensional perspective. By combining various indicators related to firepower, army strength, and military capabilities, a more comprehensive understanding of this facet of state power can be obtained. Military power, while intricately linked to economic, technical, and industrial capabilities, holds a distinct position as an indicator in geopolitical analysis. For instance, Josip Lučev (2014) introduced the Current

Capacity Indicator (CCI) during his analysis of superpowers and their military capacities. CCI proves valuable in comparative assessments of superpowers as it combines indicators of economic and military power, highlighting their potential. In the realm of cyberspace, cyber capabilities have the potential to compensate for deficiencies in other dimensions of state power. The cyberspace represents a novel domain in which even small states can attain power, transcending conventional definitions and classical notions of power associated with geography or social power (Zorko and Cesarec, forthcoming 2024).

Bearing in mind different Indexes of World Power and World Power Distribution, they often include several key indicators such as economic power, military power, political or geopolitical power, geographical factors, and technological advancements. Such visualizations often include assessing and analyzing the relative strength, influence, and capabilities of different actors in the international system. World power distribution refers to the distribution or allocation of power among nations and entities on a global scale. Measured by different authors the scale might change over time as well.

Picture 3 – The visualization of world power distribution over time in the competitiveness⁵

⁵ Source: The Visual Capitalist, <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/cp/competitive-countries-rankings/>, 7/16/2023.

Picture 4 – Economic power and projections for future⁶

It's important to note that power distribution is a dynamic and complex concept that evolves over time. It requires continuous assessment and analysis, considering multiple dimensions and indicators, to understand the changing dynamics of global power structures. States can be divided regarding power scale in various ways, depending on the specific criteria or framework used for analysis. Here are a few common ways in which states are often categorized based on their power scale: superpowers, great powers, regional powers, middle powers and small states. Somewhere in-between these definitions there are Huntington's states that does not fit into its civilizational (regional) framework. "In the post-Cold War world, countries relate to civilizations as member states, core states, lone countries, cleft countries, and torn countries" (Huntington, 1996: 135) Huntington, in the realm of affiliation, explains member and core states as ones belonging to civilizational patterns, lone states as ones that do not belong to either big world civilization and cleft and torn countries as ones that do not belong to its civilizational core. Although there is a lot to be said about Huntington thesis his countries that does not fit its civilizational background generate instability and multiply fraud lines that could be interpreted as shatter zones.

Finally, political cartography may provide fairest solution – by keeping accurate geographical parameters and adding power-relations as well. Political cartography

⁶ . Source: The Visual Capitalist, www.visualcapitalist.com, 7/11/2023.

“is not an illustration that follows and imitates previous or given contents, which is a characteristic of every illustration. In contrast, political cartography precedes conclusions, and the spatial relationships and contents it portrays serve as the basis for relevant political analyses and conclusions” (Pavić, 1984: 103). In the roughest definitions of maps in political cartography by Radovan Pavić (2012: 117) there are “two kinds of maps: first, general geographic maps, which are of a synthesizing nature as they contain as many different contents as possible, aiming to represent the objective and comprehensive reality as fully as possible. And secondly, there are applied maps that portray only specific contents, issues, and ideas, and they can also be of two types: a) analytical when they represent only one content, and then b) synthesizing when they show various specific contents, but not in a simple accumulation manner, rather in the form of interconnectedness and interplay of individual contents gathered around a common idea or problem”. Following these instructions, we are using both analytical and syncretical political cartography approach in our visualization of modern shatterbelts.

The Modern Shatterbelts: Global “Regional System” and its fraud lines

The methodology for our concept is based on political cartography visualization of big data. Combining aforementioned indexes of world power, classifying them into power related state categories and bearing in mind regional specifics driven out of Huntington classification our map present contemporary global regional system and its fraud lines defined as frontiers of interest rather than shatterbelts.

Envisioning the current world power distribution and bearing in mind power-related categories as superpowers, great powers and regional powers we followed Geographics Magazine’s *Guide of International Power* and combined it with Pareto’s *Global Power Index Ranking for 2023* (<https://pareto-economics.com/global-power-index/>, 7/29/2023). We decided to sort superpowers (current, ex and emerging) with great powers, and they are USA, China, Russia, United Kingdom, Germany, France and Japan. Regional powers and regional Pivots are following: Argentina, Australia, Brazil, Egypt, India, Indonesia, Iran, Israel, Italy, Mexico, Nigeria, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, South Korea, South Africa, Turkey and Vietnam. European Union and Global cities are noted as well since new subjects emerge other than states. The ranking list for 2022 in global cities is New York, London, Paris, Tokyo, Beijing (<https://www.kearney.com/industry/public-sector/global-cities/2022>, 7/29/2023). Trough centre-periphery theory author’s sheched spheres of influence accordingly.

Bearing in mind strong interconnections between shatterbelts and places of war and insecurity author’s combined three online sources for mapping world conflicts and illustrated them (<https://www.visualcapitalist.com/mapped-where-are-the-worlds-ongoing-conflicts-today/>, <https://www.thenewhumanitarian.org/maps-and-graphics/2017/04/04/updated-mapped-world-war>, and <https://www.cfr.org/global-conflict-tracker>, 7/29/2023.. They are as follows:

Russo-Ukrainian War, Nagorno Karabakh (Armenia-Azerbaijan) conflict, Turkish internal conflict with Kurds, Israel-Palestine, Wars in Afghanistan and in Syria, instabilities in Iraq and Yemen, Lebanon, Egypt and DR Congo, Libyan and South Sudanese civil wars, US-Iran conflict, India-Pakistan conflict, Tigray war in Ethiopia, Mali war, Boko Haram Militancy in Nigeria, Al-Shabaab in Kenya and Ethiopia, violence in Central African Republic, East and South China Sea disputes and North-South Korea Crisis. Although mentioned sources include Mexico as well authors suggest interpreting this drug-cartel related insurgencies as internal conflict and problems of a weak political system.

Picture 5 – Author's Power Map⁷

⁷ Tool for creation: www.mapchart.net, 7/29/2023

Sources: Global and Regional pivots, Great Powers and Superpowers – Geographics Magazine, Guide of International Power, https://web.facebook.com/geographics2.0/posts/guide-of-international-powers-can-you-tell-whats-difference-between-a-regional-p/300315378213373/?_rdc=1&_rdt, 7/29/2023.

Spheres of Influence (centre-periphery based) – author's visualization

Global cities – Kearney, <https://www.kearney.com/industry/public-sector/global-cities/2022>, 7/29/2023.

Current War Zones. Combination of Sources: The Visual Capitalist, <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/mapped-where-are-the-worlds-ongoing-conflicts-today/>, 7/29/2023; The New Humanitarian, <https://www.thenewhumanitarian.org/maps-and-graphics/2017/04/04/updated-mapped-world-war>,

7/29/2023; The Center for Preventive Action's (CPA) Global Conflict Tracker, <https://www.cfr.org/global-conflict-tracker>, 7/29/2023.

Global Borders of Walled World. Big Think, 2019, <https://bigthink.com/strange-maps/walled-world/>, 7/29/2023.

Macoregional Shatterbelts – Frontiers of Insecurity of Global World System – author's interpretation

Before concluding and defining Macroregional Shatterbelts – Frontieres of Insecurity of Global World System – in author’s interpretation authors included concept of Walled World in its Power Map political cartography analysis. As it is shown in Power map modern shatterbelt is consistent of local fraud lines interconnection in global frontier of insecurity that stretches from Eastern Europe to Eastern Asia including African continent. It would be important for future research to further classify local African shatterbelts and research its origins and potential reaches.

Conclusion

The main division in rethinking the theory of shatterbelts in contemporary relations has at least two perspectives. Classical geopolitical thought is based on regional perspective of big intersecting regions over time and their contact points. Critical geopolitical thought relies on constructivism, geopolitical imaginations and perceptions of belonging rather than geographical givens in particular timeframes. The classical approach to geopolitics emphasizes the importance of states, territories, and geographical factors in shaping international relations. It focuses on the strategic significance of geographical locations, resources, and territorial control. In such constellation shatterbelts are expected outcomes of world regional system in constant contestation. Classical geopolitics assumes that the world is primarily shaped by the struggle for power and control over territory.

The critical approach challenges the traditional state-centric perspective and explores the power dynamics, social constructions, and discourses that shape geopolitics. It examines how geopolitical knowledge is produced, contested, and used by different actors. Therefore, shatterbelts are constructs of imagined outlines in world power struggles and assumed as contested spaces in-between regional powers/actors. Critical geopolitics challenges the deterministic and essentialist assumptions of classical geopolitics. It recognizes that geopolitical narratives and boundaries are socially constructed and contested. Shatterbelts are seen as socially, and politically constructed spaces shaped by competing interests and discourses. Therefore, non-traditional actors (rather than states), and non-traditional spaces (cyberspace) should be taken into consideration as well. Overall, the classical approach to shatterbelts tends to emphasize the physical and strategic aspects of these regions, while the critical approach takes a more nuanced and interdisciplinary view, examining the social, political, and discursive dynamics at play.

Both perspectives share common ground: the definition of world regions and their fraud lines or contested spaces depends on distribution of world power. Therefore, the World System as a whole should be referred to as the unit of analysis. There are two levels of contested spaces that we suggest defining as modern frontieres – ones on the macro level of the world system and ones on the micro level important in local frames. Although even microlevel fraud lines might influence global (in)security, their wellbeing is often linked to internal success and political stability.

Also, such visualizations are time-sensitive so time frame should be included in this kind of research as well. Other than perspectives, the classical and critical geopolitical theory approaches to shatterbelts differ in their assumptions, and analytical frameworks. Analytical Framework of Classical Geopolitical Theory tends to analyze shatterbelts through a state-centric lens, focusing on military strategies, territorial control, and the balance of power between states. It emphasizes geographical factors such as proximity, resources, and transportation routes. The critical approach employs interdisciplinary methods and analyzes shatterbelts through a broader socio-political lens. It examines the social, economic, cultural, and historical dimensions of shatterbelts, including identities, conflicts, power relations, and discourses. Both perspectives were taken into consideration in our analysis.

Moreover, classical geopolitics primarily focuses on the stability, security, and balance of power in shatterbelts. It explores how states and major powers seek to control and influence these regions to enhance their own geopolitical interests. Critical geopolitics focuses on the contestation and power relations within shatterbelts. It examines how different actors, such as states, non-state actors, and social movements, navigate and shape these spaces. Therefore, it is crucial to realize that in both perspectives borders and border theory is relevant and should be taken into consideration when rethinking shatterbelts and shatterbelt theory.

The nature of borders in shattered spaces can vary and is often characterized by fluidity rather than being strictly hard or solid. Additionally, the fluidity of borders in global shattered spaces can be influenced by geopolitical dynamics, power struggles, and changing alliances. As the interests and priorities of different actors evolve, so can the borders and boundaries that demarcate their spheres of influence. Envisioning shatterbelt theory through border studies enriches the concept of border fluidity naming it frontier of insecurity. Such frontier changes and vary accordingly. Other than border theory center-periphery theory should be used for visualization of contemporary contested spaces – current shatterbelts are contested modern frontiers in a frame of power-distribution. Such modern shatterbelts are border zones of power-influence international gameplay. That means that shattered spaces are not geographically doomed, but historically challenged and geopolitically envisioned as spaces of power-play. They are not regions since region envision homogeneity and at least some level of cohesion. Incorporating huge differences between developed and developing world such insecurities multiply accordingly. Author's Power Map based on combination of indexes of world power and using political cartography as a method of data visualization show that current contested space or modern frontier of insecurity cover the vast of developing world along the fraud lines of Walled World (). Although this visualization may remind us on Thomas P.M. Barnett's "The Pentagon's New Map" (2004), authors does not suggest that globalization is or could be the driving force in the case of modern frontiers but distribution of world power.

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**Geo-Politizing the Intermediate Spaces of the World-System:
Semi-Cores and Semi-Peripheries, Geostrategies of Subordination and Autonomy (Cases in Latin America and Southern Europe After the Cold War)¹**

Heriberto Cairo²

Abstract:

This paper aims to deepen on a key yet obscure and imprecise concept, used primarily in world-systems analysis: the semi-periphery, and how it can be useful to explain the position of some countries in several geopolitical regions of the world. After a brief evaluation of the concept's theoretical importance, it reviews various empirical efforts to discern between countries' circumstances by the horizontal tripartite division of the world-economy's areas. It then analyzes its evolution – especially in the most recent decades after the Cold War – and verifies how heterogeneous the semi-periphery is. It then proposes to divide the category by distinguishing semi-centers from semi-peripheries. For this, it is necessary to politicize and “geo-politicize” the concept – that is, to include structural political and geopolitical elements upon its definition and analysis, which until now has based itself fundamentally on the geoeconomic structure. Doing so will also allow us to distinguish between subordinate and autonomous semi-peripheries in relation to the hegemonic contender powers. Some cases of semi-peripheries and semi-centers in different geopolitical orders will be discussed, and we will try to discern the different roles these countries have had in the world system. This would allow us to understand their roll nowadays.

Key words:

World System, semi-core, semi-periphery, Latin America, Southern Europe

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² Heriberto Cairo is Professor of Political Geography at the Department of Political History, Theories and Geography, Faculty of Political Sciences and Sociology, Complutense university of Madrid, Spain.

Introduction: “semi-periphery”, an obscure but necessary concept

In the more traditional core-periphery theories, the concept of “semi-periphery” does not exist. It is quite specific to world-systems analysis, as Immanuel Wallerstein and other authors have understood it, ever since André Gunder-Frank showed in his dependency theory that, in the process of exploitation of the periphery by the core, or, if you like, in the process of production of underdevelopment, the intermediate instances play a fundamental role:

“A whole chain of constellations of metropolises and satellites relates all the parts of the total system from its core in Europe or the United States to the most distant points in the Latin American countries. When we examine the metropolis-satellite structure, we find that each one of the satellites, including today’s underdeveloped Spain and Portugal, serve as an instrument to extract capital or economic surpluses from their own satellites and direct part of these surpluses towards the foreign metropolis of which are all satellites” (Frank, 1967: 162).

To move beyond the obvious examples of Spain and Portugal, the more “developed” satellites, such as the São Paulo region in Brazil, had their own satellites, so that within the same state there were structural situations more like the core and others definitely from the periphery. Frank was pessimistic about the possibility that the “industrial development” of São Paulo, for example, would have a definitive character and succeed in removing “Brazil from the cycle of satellite development and underdevelopment that has characterized its other regions and its national history up to now within the capitalist system” (Frank, 1967: 164). This article will not enter this debate, although I think that the example of Brazil can easily be contrasted with that of the United States, and thus show that the industrial development of a region can lead to the development of the entire state, even at the cost of a bloody war. What is interesting about Gunder Frank’s conceptualization for the present work is the affirmation of the existence of intermediate instances between the core and the periphery.

Later, Wallerstein specifically introduces the category of “semi-periphery” to refer to this phenomenon in the modern world-system, defining it precisely as being

“based on the double antinomy of class (bourgeois-proletarian) and function in the division of labor (core-periphery). The core-periphery distinct [...] differentiates those zones in which are concentrated high-profit, high-technology, high-wage diversified production (the core countries) from those in which are concentrated low-profit, low- technology, low-wage, less diversified production (the peripheral countries). But there has always been a series of countries which fall in between in a very concrete way and play a different role. The productive activities of these semi-peripheral countries are more evenly divided. In part they act as a peripheral zone for core countries and in part they act as a core country for some peripheral areas” (Wallerstein, 1976: 462-463).

But it must be understood that, in the case of the semi-periphery, “there are no semi-peripheral processes; rather, the term [...] is applied directly to the zones, regions or states in which neither the processes of the core nor those of the periphery predominate. This means that the general social relations that take place

in these zones suppose the exploitation of peripheral zones, at the same time that the same semi-periphery suffers the exploitation of the core” (Taylor and Flint, 2002: 22). That is, they are intermediate spaces that also play an intermediary role, but of a different nature in each case. In Wallerstein’s (1976) original definition, they include

- countries from Latin America (Brazil, Mexico, Argentina, Venezuela, and possibly Chile and Cuba);
- from the European periphery (all of the south, Portugal, Spain, Italy and Greece; most of the east, the German Democratic Republic and, although he does not specify it, Poland, Czechoslovakia, and Hungary; and parts of the north, such as Norway and Finland);
- Israel and some Arab countries (Algeria, Egypt and Saudi Arabia);
- Nigeria and Zaire, in Africa;
- Turkey, Iran, India, Indonesia, China, Korea and Vietnam, in Asia;
- and finally, the white countries of the Commonwealth (Canada, Australia, South Africa and New Zealand).

Later, in an important work on the evolution of semi-peripheries in different world-systems throughout history, Chase-Dunn and Hall (2018: 37-38) identify several types throughout history that mix different roles and positions:

- one that mixes core and peripheral forms of organization,
- one that can be located spatially between the core and peripheral regions,
- one that can be located spatially between two or more core regions in competition,
- one that performs mediation activities between the core and peripheral areas, and
- one in which the institutional characteristics are intermediate between those found in the core and the periphery.

In view of this heterogeneity of roles, the authors are cautious about the precision of the concept: “Classifying these different types of semi-peripheries continues to be both an empirical and a theoretical problem. Until more detailed comparisons between different types of world-systems are completed, it would be premature to define the concept of a semi-periphery more precisely” (Chase-Dunn and Hall, 2018: 37-38).

Other authors also believe that this definition is insufficient when constructing this category, as shown in the heterogeneity of countries in the Wallerstein list. In this sense, Terlouw (1993) qualifies the concept as “imprecise” or “elusive”. Boaventura de Sousa Santos (1985) calls it “descriptive”, “vague” and “negative”. It would be descriptive “because it barely has theoretical content, [in the Wallersteinian version] it is little more than a construction by analogy” with the middle classes (1985: 870). These are countries that would cushion the contradictions between those in the core and those in the periphery, in a similar way to the middle classes which play an intermediary role between the bourgeoisie and the proletariat. The concept would

be vague because “the criteria to define a peripheral status are many and difficult to quantify” (Santos, 1985: 870). And it would be negative because semi-peripheral states “lack materiality in themselves and do not have a particular evolutionary logic, and are a mixture of characteristics attributed to central or peripheral states and societies” (ibid.).

All these statements suggest that conceptualizing the semi-periphery is complex and problematic. In fact, I share with Domingues the idea that “it raises the most subtle theoretical and practical problems of our days” (2012a: 13). But we can base our analysis on the definition of Santos (1985), which emphasizes that the concept is associated with an intermediate situation and a certain capacity for intermediation. As an historical example, he gives the case of Portugal as an intermediary between the core sphere and the colonial sphere. But we cannot focus only on this specific situation because when it ended after April 25, 1974, the country could have stopped being “semi-peripheral” in its terms, but it did not. In other words, the semi-peripheries are changeable and in most cases ephemeral, but they have a fundamental role in modernity, which has become a global civilization but is heterogeneous (Domingues, 2012b).

It is necessary that semi-peripheries exist because they are key to balancing the world-system and reducing conflict. Like other triadic concepts —such as Lefebvre’s (1974) spatial “trialectics,” for example, in which spatial representations, spatial practices, and spaces of representation interact to produce space— the core–semi-periphery–periphery conceptualization is intended to provide stability to the system.

But it is important to understand that, at the same time, the movement of the system is also explained by this triadic character: in the case of Lefebvre, the “spaces of representation”, the third element of his trialectic, which refers to the thoughts and practices that in various ways contradict, or at least question, the dominant representations of space and the spatial practices that derive from them. “Spaces of representation” are fundamental to understanding change in space, because they allow resistance to those dominant practices and representations.

In the case of world-systems analysis, the semi-periphery plays a key role, because it allows us to understand the rise of regions and nations from the periphery to the core or the descent from the latter to the former. But this implies very different situations and processes, so the concept of “semi-periphery” to a certain extent becomes a “mixture”.

This article is fundamentally about theoretical reflection, and the case studies presented develop and support the theoretical constructions that I propose, although not necessarily prove them given their small number. In this sense, I adopt the comparative methodology, one of the most traditional in political science, since we do not carry out a single case study. Rather we examine a small selection of case studies in an already relatively small research universe, such as the set of units of the interstate system. In this way, although we cannot prove it, a relatively reduced set

of case studies will allow us to increase control over the hypothesis (Sartori and Morlino, 1999) about the necessary politicization of the concept of semi-periphery. In other words, comparative case studies, a type of case study that Lijphart (1971) proposed many years ago, will allow advancement in controlling the validity of the theory presented (Sartori, 1991).

It is not a question of exhaustively studying Latin America and Southern Europe, but of selecting cases in both regions that support the hypotheses about the semi-peripheries. In what follows, first I will review the forms that have been used to empirically differentiate the core, the semi-periphery and the periphery in the analysis of world-systems. Second, I will move to the evolution of the semi-peripheries in our days. Finally, I will propose a “politicization” of the concept to better understand its different roles. This politicization implies including structural geopolitical elements in the definition and analysis of the semi-periphery — particularly its intermediary nature—, which until now has been fundamentally based on the geoeconomic structure, as discussed below.

The limitations of the empirical definition of core, semi-periphery and periphery

As we have seen, the definitions of these concepts were originally made from the description of economic conditions. In fact, many of the authors who write within the world-systems analysis tradition interpret the semi-periphery primarily in economic terms. Arrighi and Drangel (1986: 15) argue that the term should only be used to “refer to a position in relation to the world division of labor and never to refer to a position in the interstate system”. Korzeniewicz (1990) basically thinks the same and makes the international division of labor the key to understanding the position of a country. Arceo (2004: 17) adopts an even more quantitative strategy, identifying the semi-periphery in 1975 with the “set of countries that had (...), at purchasing power parity, a product per capita two and a half times higher than that of the set from the periphery”.

One of the most important issues to underline then is that this division responds to a single international division of labor, which is based “on the differential appropriation of the produced surplus [so that] the positions [of the countries] are hierarchically ordered, not only differentiated” (Evans, cited in Mahutga and Smith, 2011: 257). These authors are precisely those who make an effort to quantify the degree of “centrality” of states based on the place they occupy in the international division of labor, in order to see if there is a direct relationship with economic growth (Mahutga and Smith, 2011). While this second part does not interest us now, we are going to see the differentiation they make according to the international division of labor, in which they distinguish six groups (Table 1):

- in Group 1 are the most powerful countries in the world, headed by the United States, whose production processes are marked by high technology and heavy industry;

-
- Group 2 includes several European countries and some of the most dynamic countries in the developing world, including China, India, Brazil, South Korea and Singapore, whose production processes have evolved towards those of the previous group;
 - Group 3 includes most of the dynamic economies of the developing world (Indonesia, Ireland, Malaysia, Thailand or Turkey) that have evolved from a model of low wages and light manufacturing to increasingly include heavy industries;
 - Group 4 are countries with agrarian economies that have been evolving to others of low wages and light manufacturing (Peru, Honduras, Uruguay, Iran, Malta or the Ivory Coast);
 - Group 5 includes some very rich countries in terms of per capita income, which are absolutely dependent on their extractive economy, as is the case of oil producers (Saudi Arabia, Kuwait, Libya, but also Venezuela); and
 - Group 6 are the weakest (Central African Republic, Malawi or Samoa), characterized by an extractive economy that is becoming progressively more sophisticated
 - .

Table 1. Position of countries in the world-system according to the international division of labor

<i>State and rank in 1965</i>	<i>1965</i>	<i>1980</i>	<i>2000</i>	<i>State and rank in 1965</i>	<i>1965</i>	<i>1980</i>	<i>2000</i>
1 United States (Ws)	1	1	1	48 Chili (LA)	4	3	3
2 France (Ws)	1	1	1	59 Panama (LA)	4	3	4
3 Germany (Ws)	1	1	1	49 Costa Rica (LA)	4	4	4
4 United Kingdom (Ws)	1	1	1	53 Peru (LA)	4	4	4
5 Italy (Ws)	1	1	1	55 Honduras (LA)	4	4	4
6 Japan (As)	1	1	1	58 Uruguay (LA)	4	4	4
7 Netherlands (Ws)	1	1	1	60 Iran (ME)	4	4	4
9 Canada (Ws)	1	1	1	50 Nicaragua (LA)	4	4	5
11 Belgium (Ws)	1	1	1	54 Malta (Ws)	4	4	5
8 Sweden (Ws)	1	1	2	61 Ivory Coast (Af)	4	4	5
10 Switzerland (Ws)	1	2	2	62 Iceland (Ws)	4	4	5

21 Spain (Ws)	2	2	1	51 Venezuela (LA)	4	5	4
12 Denmark (Ws)	2	2	2	63 Ecuador (LA)	4	5	4
13 Austria (Ws)	2	2	2	52 Jamaica (LA)	4	5	5
14 Czechoslovakia (EE)	2	2	2	57 Senegal (Af)	4	5	5
15 Norway (Ws)	2	2	2	64 --- (Af)	4	5	5
16 Hong Kong (As)	2	2	2	65 Ethiopia (Af)	4	5	5
17 Finland (Ws)	2	2	2	66 Paraguay (LA)	4	5	5
18 Australia (Ws)	2	2	2	56 Angola (Af)	4	6	6
19 Yugoslavia (EE)	2	2	2	70 Cyprus (Ws)	5	4	4
20 India (As)	2	2	2	73 Sri Lanka (As)	5	4	5
22 Hungary (EE)	2	2	2	78 Saudi Arabia (ME)	5	5	3
23 Portugal (Ws)	2	2	3	67 Kuwait (ME)	5	5	5
24 China (As)	3	2	2	68 Trinidad/Tobago (LA)	5	5	5
25 Argentina (LA)	3	2	2	71 Bahrein (ME)	5	5	5

26 Brazil (LA)	3	2	2	72 Libya (ME)	5	5	5
29 Ireland (Ws)	3	2	2	74 Cameroon (Af)	5	5	5
32 Singapore (As)	3	2	2	75 Jordan (ME)	5	5	5
36 South Korea (As)	3	2	2	76 Barbados (LA)	5	5	5
28 New Zealand (Ws)	3	2	3	77 Bolivia (LA)	5	5	5
30 Malaysia (As)	3	3	2	69 Ghana (Af)	5	6	5
31 Mexico (LA)	3	3	2	79 Zambia (Af)	5	6	6
37 Thailand (As)	3	3	2	91 Mauricio (Af)	6	5	5
27 Israel (ME)	3	3	3	80 Togo (Af)	6	5	6
34 Greece (Ws)	3	3	3	82 Benin (Af)	6	5	6
40 Philippines (As)	3	3	3	88 Qatar (ME)	6	6	5
41 Indonesia (As)	3	3	3	90 Brunei (As)	6	6	5
33 Morocco (ME)	3	3	4	81 Congo, Dem Rep (Af)	6	6	6
42 Turkey (ME)	3	4	3	83 Malawi (Af)	6	6	6

35 Pakistan (ME)	3	4	4	84 Gabon (Af)	6	6	6
38 Egypt (ME)	3	4	4	85 Burkina Faso (Af)	6	6	6
39 Nigeria (Af)	3	4	5	86 Niger (Af)	6	6	6
44 Colombia (LA)	4	3	4	87 Chad (Af)	6	6	6
45 Guatemala (LA)	4	4	4	89 Mali (Af)	6	6	6
46 El Salvador (LA)	4	4	4	92 Central African (Af)	6	6	6
47 Tunisia (ME)	4	4	4	93 Gambia (Af)	6	6	6
43 Algeria (ME)	4	5	5	94 Samoa (As)	6	6	6
<p>Group 1: Core; Group 2: Core-contender; Group 3: Upper-tier semiperiphery; Group 4: Strong periphery; Group 5: Weak periphery; Group 6: Weakest periphery.</p> <p>Af: Africa; As: Asia; EE: Eastern Europe; LA: Latin America; ME: Middle East; Ws: West.</p>							

Source: Mahutga y Smith (2011).

One of the advantages of this work is that, by including indices at three moments (1960, 1985 and 2000), it shows the dynamism of world production and the evolution of the international division of labor, particularly the differences between the period before and after the end of the Cold War.

The countries of Group 1 in the three moments of Table 1 (United States, France, Germany, United Kingdom, Italy, Japan, Holland, Canada and Belgium) do not offer any classificatory problem. All the authors would undoubtedly consider these as “Core”. And, evidently, the same type of core cannot be those that have been hegemonic powers in some period (Netherlands, the United Kingdom and the United States), including those that have been powers challenging that hegemony (France, Germany or Japan), that countries like Italy, Belgium or Canada, which neither were hegemonic or challenging powers. But now is not the time for that discussion.

At the other extreme, the countries in Groups 4, 5 and 6 are all classified as periphery, but the differentiation offered by Mahutga and Smith (2011) is fundamentally quantitative (strong, weak and weaker periphery). Few distinctions are made between the countries that are dedicated to light manufacturing and those that base their economy on extractivism. In a particularly interesting study, Durand, Lévy and Retailé (1992) make the world of the periphery more structurally complex, distinguishing between “integrated” peripheries, in which countries receive investment flows from the core as a result of the relocation of industries and produce for the core, “exploited” peripheries, which are incorporated into the system thanks to the exploitation of its resources, and “abandoned” peripheries, which include the poorest countries on earth, characterized rather by their disconnection from the global economic flows.

States that are in groups 2, 3 and 4 are characterized by high mobility. That is, they have characteristics of what the authors of world-systems analysis call semi-periphery. But these bands include countries as dissimilar as Sweden, Switzerland, Spain or Denmark, in the highest part of Table 1, to Ethiopia, Paraguay, Angola or Cyprus, in the lower part. This latter group, as well as the majority of those that oscillate around Group 4, are usually considered as periphery, so we are going to concentrate in the next sections on the countries of Groups 2 and 3 in the year 2000, which are the ones that Mahutga and Smith (2011) call “Core-contender” and “Upper-tier semi-periphery”. As Andersen says, the problem is “that countries as different as Norway, Iran, Nigeria, China and Italy can be conceptualized as ‘semi-peripheries’” (2016: 187). Such broad categories, covering so many different types of cases, are not very explanatory, and for this reason I think that subtypes should be established in the semi-peripheries. For this, the international division of labor is not useful; rather we must focus on the different intermediary geopolitical roles that they play.

It is true that I also believe that there are different types of core and peripheries — for example, the “integrated peripheries” of Mahutga and Smith (2011) are peripheries, but also partly encompass the “semi-periphery” of group 3— but this

discussion already exceeds the objective of this paper, and although I will make some reflections in line with the explanation, we will leave it for another time.

Mahutga and Smith (2011) point out that semi-peripheral countries contain a relatively balanced mix of core and periphery forms of production, and generally benefit from maintaining both capital-intensive and work force-intensive productions. In this way, production costs are lower than in the core, and technological capacity is greater than in the periphery, thus becoming more attractive for industrial investment. Given that the interest of these authors, as we have said, is to establish correlations between the position in the international division of labor structure and economic growth, they are especially interested in understanding the role of the semi-periphery in economic development. They conclude that “semi-peripheral countries occupy structural positions that encourage upward mobility more than peripheral countries” (Mahutga and Smith, 2011: 259). In fact, there is empirical evidence that they grow faster than the countries of the core or those of the periphery. The same authors even affirm that “the semi-periphery is converging towards the core in terms of the structure of its productive forces, but diverging from the periphery, which continues to export primary goods or light manufactures produced with low wages in the year 2000” (Mahutga and Smith, 2011: 270).

Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes (2014) abound in another type of explanation, which leads them to opposite conclusions. They also make a factorial analysis of the economies of the main core countries (those of the triad: the United States, Japan and the European Union) and some of the semi-periphery (Argentina, Brazil, China, India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Mexico, Korea South, the Russian Federation, South Africa, Thailand and Turkey, to which are added the peripheral countries of Egypt and Morocco, to see if there is a differentiated behavior of the semi-periphery with the periphery). Their aim is to understand what happens in the semi-periphery of the capitalist world-economy. To do this, they take two previous steps:

“First, we opted to move from a “commercialist” vision of the Core/Periphery conception to a “productive” vision, defined in terms of relative autonomy with respect to the Core/Periphery system, of the capital accumulation process within the framework of the “national economy”. This first step, which serves to define self-centered and extroverted economies, following Samir Amin’s terminology, has given way to a new stage in the process of capital circulation, that of global capitalism, which does not annul conceptualization, but rather redesigns the territorial spaces of application, disregarding borders, which would tend to disappear as analytically significant in the Global Capitalist System” (Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes, 2014: 256).

In the second decade of the 21st century, the extraversion of the economy in the semi-periphery —which maintains primary exporting patterns and a low manufacturing profile— continues, so that it continues to be unable to retain the surplus. The core —although with Europe lagging behind— continues to be technologically advanced. China has a unique and very contradictory role, with great weight in the world economy, but with an extroverted economy. Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes (2014: 270) conclude therefore that no “convergence” is taking

place between the semi-periphery and the core. It would be better to stop thinking of the current world system, the capitalist world-economy, as an inter-state system, and definitely assume that it is global and also consider its class structure. In this “global framework of accumulation, self-centeredness and extraversion are already defined at the supranational level.”

Summarizing, for Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes (2014):

1. The United States, the European Union and Japan (the Triad), together with China, have a great weight in the world economy.
2. The United States and Japan play a leading role in terms of technological development.
3. The economies of China and the Asian industrialized countries, a fundamental part of the semi-periphery, are strongly marked by its extraversion (mismatch between its great productive contribution *vs.* its lower participation in consumption).

How can the authors reach such different conclusions, given that both explanations are made from the analysis of production, not trade? There are two main reasons. Firstly, Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes (2014) think that we are already in another phase of the capitalist world-economy, characterized as a “global capitalist system”, while Mahutga and Smith (2011) still think in terms of an interstate system and of “national” economies. Secondly, Martínez Peinado and Cairó i Cespedes (2014) include as semi-periphery only the countries of the global South that were previously in the periphery, while in the classification of Mahutga and Smith (2011), Group 2 in the year 2000 includes Sweden, Switzerland, Denmark, Austria, Norway and Australia together with China, Brazil or India. In the same year, Group 3 includes countries such as New Zealand, Greece or Portugal along with the Philippines, Indonesia or Turkey; that is, Mahutga and Smith include in Group 3 European countries and countries of European descent that are usually classified as countries of the core.

To understand the geoeconomic role of the semi-periphery today, it is important to take into account the general value chains (GVCs) that have characterized capitalism since the 1990s. The revolution in information and communication technologies (ICT) a decade earlier allowed the displacement of the classic Fordist forms of industrial organization, which were characterized by large economic units that vertically integrated production and thus consolidated privileged positions in the market. As pointed out by Torres and Ahumada (2022: 172):

“In their place, a disintegration of these hierarchical structures and a concentration of large companies in their main areas of competence have emerged, so that the production of a merchandise has been dispersed, throughout many parts of the globe, in various productive units in charge of different inputs and parts of the product, and whose connection and governance are in charge of one or more actors.”

The central regions have concentrated on controlling “intangible” assets (technological knowledge, design, brands, computerized information) through various control procedures, including intellectual property, which allows them to

control the GVCs. In the semi-periphery, productive processes are developed that require strong capital investments and certain degrees of qualification of the labor force. In the periphery, productive processes with less technological sophistication are developed, which require a greater amount of labor that, in general, is not very qualified.

It would be worth going deeper into this economic discussion of the issue—emphasizing structural reasoning more than empirical measurements—, but I believe that a fundamental issue in the global role of the semi-periphery would be left out: its role as geopolitical intermediary. Politics is key to understanding how semi-peripheral countries are inserted into the capitalist world-economy, their evolution and even their own consideration as semi-periphery. The authors cited above agree in their explanations of the important role of the state in the growth or development of semi-peripheral countries; however, they do not deal explicitly with the issue – perhaps because both papers are fundamentally economically oriented. This is not to deny the geoeconomic nature of the semi-periphery, but to understand that it also plays a political and geopolitical role.

Politicizing and geo-politicizing the category of semi-periphery

The “objective” class structure that is defined from the international division of labor is global; in fact, most of the authors within world-systems analysis think that classes are “global strata” (Taylor and Flint, 2002: 28). However, in “subjective” terms, the social classes continue to be state, and the class struggle develops within the state.¹⁸ This is one of the reasons why the state remains important in the current world-system. The state is not an epiphenomenon that depends on the economic structure, as the most traditional orthodox Marxism claimed, but rather has its own dynamics within the world-system – yes, coupled to the international division of labor and the global class structure, which to a large extent is composed of socio-spatial classes. In other words, the “subjective” classes continue to be state—nationalists of any stripe would claim that they are also national—, and the states have a fundamental role in determining policies so that some regions are core or periphery or pass from one to the other.

As we have seen, attempts to classify states in the horizontal tripartite structure of core, semi-periphery and periphery have been fundamentally economic, since the international division of labor is the ultimate key to that division, but without considering politics it is impossible to achieve a suitable classification. And it is not just about taking into account military or other power in the abstract, as many indices of world power do (see, for example, the works of Rocha Valencia and Morales Ruvalcaba, 2010; 2018; Morales Ruvalcaba, Rocha Valencia and Vargas

¹⁸ I do not want to return here to the old Marxist discussion about class “in itself” and class “for itself”, but simply to underline what is precisely one of the great contributions of world-systems analysis to contemporary social class theory: the existence of a “division of interests” between the dominated classes of the core and the dominated classes of the periphery (Galtung, cited in Taylor and Flint, 2002: 121).

García, 2013), but to understand the internal politics and geopolitical relations in which the state finds itself.

Wallerstein was aware of the political importance of the state in the current world-system:

“From the point of view of entrepreneurs operating in a capitalist world-economy, sovereign states exercise authority over at least seven main arenas of direct interest to them: 1) States impose the rules on the exchange of goods, the capital and labor, and under what conditions they can cross its borders. 2) They create the laws concerning the property rights of states. 3) Create the rules concerning employment and compensation of employees. 4) They decide the costs that the companies must bear. 5) They decide what kind of economic processes should be monopolized, and to what extent. 6) They charge taxes. 7) Finally, when companies established within their borders may be affected, they can use their power abroad to affect the decisions of other states” (2005a: 34).

It is evident that all these elements condition production in a very important way, which obviously makes places where more benefits can be obtained more attractive for investments – for example, because low wages predominate. The industrial relocation from the core to the semi-periphery is largely explained by this procedure. But we should distinguish the (internal) political role of the state from its geopolitical role (in the interstate system).

Regarding the (internal) political role, a good part of the role of the state is that of arbitrator of the conditions of production in the territory under its jurisdiction, for which reason they continue to be decisive in the capitalist world-economy. They can, and in some cases do, become actors with their own role in the development of a country, mainly in its industrialization. This is very common in the semi-periphery, as Domingues (2012a) shows in several of the examples he studies (Korea, Taiwan, Brazil, China or India). The role is changing in each case and not all of them fit well with Evans’ (1995) developmental state model as used by Domingues. Effectively, this means that there can be development in the periphery, “dependent and associated” as Domingues emphasizes, citing Cardoso and Faletto (1972). I would add that this can also apply within the present capitalist world-economy, as shown by the transition of the People’s Republic of China from state socialism to capitalism and from the periphery to the semi-periphery —and perhaps to the core— of that world-system. In Wallerstein’s seminal article (1976: 463), it was already mentioned that both the internal politics of semi-peripheral states and their social structure are distinctive, and, in general, this question of the internal politics of states has tended to be considered.

Regarding the geopolitical role, the seventh arena to which Wallerstein (2005a) alluded, the state has a determining geopolitical role in the struggle of all states for primacy in the world-system (Agnew, 2005), since it implies an action specific foreign exchange on the part of the companies established on its borders. But this action can also be carried out by other countries or directly by transnational companies. Authors like Chase-Dunn (1990) think that political agency is a fundamental element to take into account in the semi-peripheries. Considering the cases of Mexico and Brazil, Gereffi and Evans (1981: 33) believe that “the

dependent development process is the result of the interaction of the strategies of transnational corporations with the political and economic strategies of social classes, local governments and [the policies and actions] of the states of the host countries”. Smith and Lee (1990) generally share the above arguments based on the study of the South Korean experience. Radice explains with great precision this geopolitical role of the state, which is key to the proper consideration of the semi-peripheries:

“On a global scale, there is a social division of labor between activities that generate a large part of the surplus in value chains (capital-intensive) and those that generate a smaller part (labor-intensive), which implies a self-perpetuating polarization of global resources. The existence of multiple states ensures that this polarization takes a geopolitical form, as states in which (for whatever reason) a higher proportion of core activities are located will not only have higher levels of consumption and wealth, but also more power to ensure that they will maintain or indeed increase that ratio. As companies have grown into gigantic transnational corporations, they have worked together with “their” states to set the rules of the game in trade, investment and finance that reinforce this polarization” (Radice, 2009: 12).

Originally, Wallerstein (1976) also took this question into account. In the discussion about the semi-peripheral countries of the then socialist world, he understood that many of their international relations were not dominated only by economic interest but by ideological conviction; organizing a “socialist” common market might not be the most beneficial economic option, but it would allow reaffirmation of the geopolitical opposition to the “capitalist” countries by the entire Soviet bloc.

In short, geo-politicizing the concept of semi-periphery will not only allow accurate characterization of various political strategies that could be described as “semi-peripheral” and distinguish them according to their objectives, but will also solve the problem, which we have pointed out repeatedly, of having in the same category (semi-periphery) both kind of countries: those that resemble the core countries and are closely associated with them, and those that could fit well into the periphery, with which they are closer. Let us now address this second question.

Distinguishing the semi-cores from the semi-peripheries

Few authors have tried to distinguish types of semi-periphery. Among them, Terlouw (1993) differentiated between politically strong and economically strong semi-peripheral states (Table 2), which, in very descriptive terms, allowed him to distinguish economically strong countries such as New Zealand, Ireland or Portugal, from what he determined to be politically strong countries such as Indonesia, Pakistan, Iraq, Turkey and South Korea.

Terlouw’s distinction is interesting. He understands that the great differences that exist between the countries, which are usually included in the semi-periphery, make it necessary to establish divisions in it, and he also introduces his idea that “political strength” is an important element when defining a state as semi-peripheral, at least in some cases.

Table 2. Types of semi-peripheral states (according to Terlouw, 1993)

		<i>Economic strength</i>		
		<i>Small</i>	<i>Intermediate</i>	<i>Large</i>
<i>Political strength</i>	<i>Small</i>	Periphery		Economic semi-periphery
	<i>Intermediate</i>		Ideal typical semi-periphery	
	<i>Large</i>	Political semi-periphery		Core

Source: Adapted from Terlouw (1993).

The level of political strength leads to different roles in the world-system. Already from its first formulation, Wallerstein stated that the semi-peripheral countries “partly act as a peripheral zone of the central countries and partly as a central country of some peripheral areas” (Wallerstein, 1976: 463). Later he specified: “In moments of expansion of the world-economy the (semi-peripheral) states find themselves attached as satellites to one or another central power and serve to some extent as economic transmission belts and political agents of an imperial power.” (1984: 7). In summary, it is possible to distinguish different roles and, therefore, different geopolitical positions, which could lead to different geostrategies.

Burns, Davis and Kick (1997), following the initial work of Kick (1987), also establish divisions in the semi-periphery, mainly between stronger states and weaker states, in terms of links to global networks. These are also reflected in domestic terms, such as per capita income (relatively high), urban population rate (relatively high), or occupational structure (“the population is increasingly employed in manufacturing and service occupations, which are rapidly industrializing” (Burns, Davis and Kick 1997: 440)). For the strongest states they use the name “semi-core” and for the weakest they maintain the name “semi-periphery”.¹⁹

¹⁹ Kick (1987) classifies the following countries into:

- Semi-core: Australia, Austria, Brazil, Bulgaria, China, Czechoslovakia, Finland, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Israel, New Zealand, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania and Yugoslavia.

- Semi-periphery: South Africa, Saudi Arabia, Algeria, Argentina, Bolivia, Chile, Colombia, South Korea, Costa Rica, Dominican Republic, Ecuador, Egypt, El Salvador, Philippines, Ghana, Guatemala, Guyana, Haiti, Honduras, India, Indonesia, Iran, Iraq, Jamaica, Jordan, Kenya, Kuwait, Liberia, Libya, Malaysia, Mexico, Morocco, Nicaragua, Nigeria, Pakistan, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Singapore, Syria, Sri Lanka, Thailand, Trinidad and Tobago, Tunisia, Turkey, Uruguay, Venezuela and Zaire.

The denominations used by these authors refer more clearly to different structural positions of both countries, but the distinction is based, above all, on the intensity of certain internal socioeconomic characteristics, since it does not explain what connections to global networks consist of. This seems to me to be a fundamental key to the issue.

Chesters (2013) also distinguishes between semi-core and semi-periphery. For her, the semi-core states have political and economic systems strong enough to obtain benefits from their relations with the periphery and the semi-periphery, but “they depend on the core for capital investments, technology and military support [...] and their workers are increasingly employed in occupations in the capital-intensive manufacturing sector and in the service sector” (Chesters, 2013: 249).²⁰

The author’s objective is to examine the relationship between wealth inequality and class stratification in the capitalist economy through the analysis of the spatial distribution of the wealthiest class, the “billionaires”. Therefore, the division argument is also fundamentally economic.

In another line of reasoning, Andersen (2014; 2016) also uses the concept of “semi-core” to refer to “a specific form of historical political association in which certain imperial provinces differ from others in terms of the close relationships they maintain with the imperial metropolis” (Andersen, 2016: 178). In other words, in his case, the global geopolitical structure is fundamental in the definition. The concept is not developed within the perspective of world-systems analysis. As the author himself points out, “it is doubtful that this theory takes the specificity of empire into account analytically, since it is more concerned with the capitalist global system as a whole” (Andersen, 2016: 187). However, the same author admits that others could use the concept differently. And indeed, the examples he works on, Scotland and Norway, may be good examples of transitional spaces in the world-system, closer to the core than to the periphery, playing intermediary roles in the world-system.

In short, the semi-core are geopolitically strong states, which are particularly integrated with the central ones, so that, unlike those in the semi-periphery, they cannot be forced to “reform” their economic structures by external institutions, such as, for example, the IMF (Wallerstein, 2005b: 243). But they neither compete for hegemony in the world-system nor can be considered great powers or major powers of the system – although they can play an important regional role, even far from their location.

²⁰ Chesters’ (2013) classification is:

- Semi-core: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, Denmark, Spain, Hong Kong, Ireland, Liechtenstein, Monaco, Norway, Singapore, Sweden, Switzerland and Taiwan.

- Semi-periphery: South Africa, Saudi Arabia, Argentina, Bahamas, Bahrain, Barbados, Bermuda, Brazil, Brunei, Chile, China, Cyprus, Colombia, South Korea, Costa Rica, Cuba, Dubai, Ecuador, Egypt, Emirates United Arab Emirates, Finland, Georgia, Gibraltar, Greece, Hungary, India, Indonesia, Iceland, Cayman Islands, Israel, Iraq, Kazakhstan, Kuwait, Lebanon, Macao, Malaysia, Mexico, New Zealand, Pakistan, Peru, Poland, Portugal, Qatar, Czech Republic, Romania, Russia, Serbia, Thailand, Turkey, Ukraine and Venezuela.

A good historical example is that of Portugal and its Empire during the 19th and 20th centuries, until 1974 when the April Revolution took place. Let us remember that Santos (1985) stressed that the concept of semi-periphery was associated with an intermediate situation and a certain capacity for intermediation, and mentioned the case of Portugal as an intermediary between the great powers (core) and the colonial sphere (periphery). Although Santos did not distinguish semi-cores from semi-peripheries, I think we could understand the role of Portugal as a semi-core, which is an agent of central countries in the periphery (Table 3).

Table 3. Historical intermediary relationship in Portugal until 1974 (semi-core)

	<i>Colonial relationship →</i>	
<i>Division of labor ↓</i>	England, Germany France...	
	Portugal	Angola, Cape Verde, Mozambique...

Source: Author

One of the political geostrategies of the semi-core, then, implies subordination to the core —particularly to the hegemonic power— on the one hand, and the co-optation of the periphery, through direct investments and using political alliances with semi-peripheral states on the other hand. The Portuguese-British alliance in practice meant the almost complete subordination of Portugal to the global designs of England. It implied that the relationship of this sovereign country with the hegemonic power (England) was not very different from that of Scotland, an integral part of the United Kingdom.

Semi-peripheries are also geopolitically strong states relative to the periphery: “In fact, in the south there are very large states that have real or potential geopolitical power: Russia, China, India, Brazil, Indonesia, Korea, and the list could go on” (Wallerstein, 2005b: 244). They can develop an important regional role, even global in the case of those that evolve towards the core, but in military terms they can hardly resist the attacks and challenges of the core countries, nor can they evade the political decisions of international institutions. They also play an intermediary role between the core and the periphery, but in a different structural position.

A good historical example is that of the United States with respect to the newly independent Latin American countries in the 19th century until 1861, when the Civil War broke out. When Haiti, Brazil and the territories of the Spanish Empire were gaining independence, the United States was not part of the core of the world-system. However, in both economic and geopolitical terms, it cannot be reduced to

a peripheral country. It is more appropriate to characterize it as a semi-periphery that acts with respect to the periphery included in “its” hemisphere (Table 4). Economically, it slowly began to invest in the region, especially in the closest part—the Caribbean—and geopolitically it was opposed to European countries. This is shown in the statement of President James Monroe during his Sixth Address to Congress on the State of the Union in 1823, which gave rise to the so-called Monroe Doctrine. On that occasion, the US president issued a serious warning to the European countries regarding their possible intervention in the affairs of the Western hemisphere – “his hemisphere”. Although its immediate effect, in terms of the defence of the new American states, was purely moral—since his economic interests and his political and military capacity were quite limited—the Latin American leaders of the time appreciated it.

Table 4. Historical intermediary relationship of the United States until 1861 (semi-periphery)

	<i>Geopolitical opposition →</i>	
<i>Economic investment ↑</i>	Mexico, Argentina, Colombia...	
	United States	England, Spain, France...

Source: Author

In 1875, at the end of the British geopolitical order, the United States had ceased to be an autonomous semi-periphery and was a core power. Its economy was thriving and highly productive, and it was engaged in an imperial expansion that implied formally and, above all, informally to Latin America. The relationship with this region and with the rest of the world changed radically.

In the next two sections, I will illustrate the hypothesis on the differentiation between semi-core and semi-peripheries with a brief study of several cases.

Semi-core in Southern Europe after the Cold War

The Southern European region is perfectly suited to show the characteristics of semi-core, in both geo-economic and geopolitical terms. According to the classification by Mahutga and Smith (2011) above, Spain, Portugal and Greece would be in groups 2 and 3 during the period analyzed, which we have considered to be the semi-peripheries. However, due to their geopolitical role, we will try to show that we should consider them as semi-core. Italy must also be included, which in geo-economic terms is comparable to others only in relation to its southern half, but in geopolitical terms its role is more similar to that of Spain.

Hadjimichalis (1987) convincingly describes the semi-peripheralization of the region in three phases:

1. The transition of Western Southern Europe from the core to the semi-periphery (and even the periphery) between the late 16th and 18th centuries due to the drive of capitalism in Northwestern Europe and the emergence of a relatively coherent world market. The Greek territories of the Ottoman Empire, from their peripheral situation, also suffered from this process.
2. The industrialization of England from the middle of the 18th century, the independence of the American colonies in the first third of the 19th century and the war in Africa were going to destroy the markets of Spain, Portugal and the industries of the Piedmont valley. In Greece, the artisan manufacturing cores were destroyed, preventing any industrial take-off. From this time comes the double North-South divide in Europe: not only between Northern Europe (especially North-western) and Southern Europe, but also within Southern Europe itself.
3. Since the last third of the 19th century, North-western European imperialism played a more active role in the southern part of the continent, making investments (especially in the railways) and granting loans to governments, which socially and spatially transformed the region. While Spain and Italy struggled to establish the unity of their states and Greece struggled to liberate all the Greek territories from Ottoman rule, the stabilization of the conditions of capitalist accumulation in the north of the continent allowed it to dominate the south.

And to these phases I would add two more:

4. The situation will change in the second half of the 20th century: the rapid industrialization process, the construction of large infrastructures and the intensification of state intervention build certain integrated national economic spaces. The conservative and/or authoritarian governments of Portugal (1933-1974) and Spain (1939-1975), the anti-communist one in Greece after the civil war, which ended in a military dictatorship (1967-1974), and the right-wing Christian Democrats in Italy (1946-1994), all oriented themselves towards “developmentalism”. This ended the dominant role of the landed bourgeoisie, partly also because industrialization did not take place in traditional places, breaking to some extent the logic of industrial norths and agricultural souths.
5. Although Italy was one of the founding states of the European Economic Community in 1958, the other countries of southern Europe joined the EEC in 1981 (Greece) and 1986 (Spain and Portugal). Their entry into what is now the European Union led most scholars, in a short time, to stop considering them as semi-periphery and to consider them as part of the core, although in the case of Greece often with reluctance. But none of them played a role in the EU or in the world similar to that of Germany or even the Netherlands, as was seen quite clearly, especially from the Great

Recession that began in 2008 and the deficit and balance of payments problems that emerged clearly in all of them. The acronym PIGS (Portugal-Italy-Greece-Spain), with a clearly pejorative meaning, was used to designate the southern EU countries in Anglo-Saxon and northern European political, financial and journalistic circles. Even Ireland, which had similar problems forming the PIIGS acronym, was included.

A) Semi-core articulating the relationship between core and peripheries: Contemporary Spain and Portugal

In the opinion of Santos (1985), the historical condition of Portugal as a semi-peripheral country was maintained even after the end of Portugal’s formal sovereignty over the colonial territories. Portugal’s incorporation into the European Union in 1986 would only have reinforced this semi-core role. To some extent, this would now be more reminiscent of Andersen’s Scotland and Norway, since Portugal would be integrated into that supranational political unit. And the creation in 1996 of an organization in the style of the British Commonwealth with its colonies, the Community of Portuguese Language Countries (*Comunidade dos Países de Língua Portuguesa*, CPLP), made it possible to better articulate this intermediary relationship between Portugal, already a member of the EU, with the countries of America, Africa, Asia, and Oceania whose language is Portuguese.

Table 5. Intermediary relationship between Spain and Portugal, 1986-2020 (core □ semi-core □ far away peripheries)

	<i>Relationship of geoeconomic and geocultural domination</i>	
<i>Division of labor</i>	Germany, Netherlands, France...	
	Spain / Portugal	Argentina, Costa Rica, Peru... / Angola, Mozambique, Cape Verde...

Source: Author

The Spanish case is similar. The incorporation in the EU in the same year also allows their access to the core. In Table 2 we saw that Spain was in Group 2 in 1960 and in 1985, but in the year 2000 it was already in Group 1 (Mahutma and Smith, 2011). I think this is consistent with its new geopolitical role since the 1980s, which implies not only belonging to the EU but also intermediation (Table 5) with the main Latin American countries. This is thanks to the strong investments of “Spanish” transnationals in the region (Arahuetes, 2011), which between 1990 and 2000 were second only to those of the United States. The construction of the structures of the

Ibero-American Community of Nations (CIN) (Cairo and Ríos, 2018), similar to those of the CPLP, have given rise to a relatively consolidated interregionalism (Cairo, 2019) – which, by the way, despite the subordination to the political geostrategies of the core countries, does not exclude the emergence of an interregionalism of resistance (Bringel and Cairo, 2019).

B) Semi-core separating the core and nearby peripheries: Italy and Greece

Although their trajectories in the modern world-system and their situations in the international division of labor are different, Italy and Greece play similar geopolitical roles to other southern European countries today. Since the creation of the Schengen area in 1985, both countries together with Spain have formed the southern border of Europe. Migratory pressure on Italy comes especially from Libya in North Africa, and on Greece from Turkey in East Asia (Table 6).

These are two examples of a semi-periphery that is spatially located between the central and peripheral regions, one of the roles identified by Chase-Dunn and Hall (2018) for this type of area. In the case of Italy, this is especially true of the southern regions. It is a geopolitical task imposed by the core countries, in this case from the EU.

Table 6. Intermediary relationship between Italy and Greece, 1981-2020 (core □ semi-core □ near peripheries)

	<i>Relation of exclusion</i>	
<i>Division of labor</i>	Germany, Netherlands, France...	
	Southern Italy / Greece	Libya, Tunisia... / Turkey, Egypt.....

Source: Author

C) Semi-core intermediating core-core: Ireland

Another type of semi-core has a role in mediating the interests of a core country in other core countries. An example is the case of Ireland after its entry into the then European Economic Community in 1973 (Table 7). It is true that Ireland is not located in Southern Europe, but it is perfectly assimilable, as the acronym PIGS shows. Coakley rightly notes that “in the ‘Celtic Tiger’ years Ireland experienced a growth rate of 6% [...] Ireland became a conduit through which American companies entered the European market. A significant pull factor [...] was the low

tax rate and the numerous tax exemption formulas” (2016: 184). The policies of the Irish state made foreign investment in this country attractive.

In geopolitical terms, Ireland’s relationship with the United States is somewhat similar to Spain’s relationship with Latin America, obviously changing the direction of the flows and their intensity; its role as a “bridge” is based on cultural and/or political elements common to two intervening spatial ensembles.

Table 7. *Intermediary relationship of Ireland, 1970-2020 (core □ semicore □ core)*

	<i>Integration relationship</i>	
<i>Division of labor</i>	United States...	
	Ireland	Germany, France Netherlands...

Source: Author

Now, once the semi-core has been defined based on certain elements of the semi-periphery, we have to return to this category to see if it is convenient to make more identification details, when taking into account the geopolitical role of states.

Distinguishing subordinate and autonomous semi-peripheries in Latin America after the Cold War

The structural location of the semi-periphery allows greater freedom of action and mobility for social movements and their political representatives, while in the core or the periphery, class relations are more established. In addition, the interests of the ruling classes in the semi-periphery are usually divided between those who seek alliances with the core countries to maintain their peripheral-type productions and those who want to promote and expand their core-type activities. As discussed, the classic example is the United States: the confrontation between the industrialized North and the slave-owning and agrarian South ended in the Civil War, the outcome of which placed the United States at the core of the world system. Katz (2011) makes a very good argument for China today about the alternatives offered to the ruling classes: extraverted growth, at the cost of greater exploitation of the Chinese proletariat, or endogenous growth, which would imply improving the living conditions of the population in general.

In Latin America we can see quite clearly the two examples of geostrategy after the end of the Cold War: one of “subordination” and the other of “autonomy”. In geoeconomic terms, they coincide with two of the types of Latin American

capitalisms that Bizberg (2019) talks about: subordination with “international outsourcing capitalism” and autonomy with “neo- or socio-developmental”.

Wallerstein’s (1976) original definition of semi-periphery included six Latin American countries (Argentina, Chile, Brazil, Venezuela, Cuba, and Mexico). During the Cold War, and after the Castro revolution, Cuba played an intermediary geopolitical role between the USSR and peripheral countries of both Latin America (Colombia, El Salvador, Guatemala and Peru, among others) and Africa (Angola and Ethiopia, in particular). Cuba supported the insurgencies that the USSR supported in these countries or supported pro-Soviet post-colonial states against pro-Western insurgencies. Venezuela and Chile could have had thriving economies and intermediate roles in the international division of labor, but to a large extent both lost those characteristics in the post-Cold War period. The fact is that there are currently three Latin American countries that are usually identified by most authors as semi-peripheral: Argentina, Brazil and Mexico. The place they occupy in the international division of labor indicates this, and, as we will see, their geopolitical role confirms it.

A) The geostrategy of subordination in the semi-periphery: The case of Mexico

The geostrategy of subordination implies a relationship with the core, similar to that of the semi-core – although from another structural position. This could be perfectly exemplified by the doctrine of “peripheral realism” (Escudé, 1992), which

“is based on the implicit assumption that in the interstate order there are written and unwritten rules, and that, despite our regrets, the most powerful states have a preponderant role in establishing those rules [...] A few have the power that it allows them to contribute to forging the rules of the game, while the vast majority is forced to behave according to the rules established by this oligopoly. And there is also a third category of states that, without having the power to contribute to establishing these rules, rebel against them, paying very high costs that revert to their inhabitants” (Escudé, 2012: 532-4).

Table 8. Intermediary relationship in Mexico, 1989-2020 (subordinate semi-periphery)

	<i>Dominance relationship</i>	
<i>División of labor</i>	United States...	
	Mexico	Guatemala, Honduras, El Salvador...

Source: Author

From this analysis, it can be deduced that the only “logical” policy for a semi-periphery is to yield to the designs of the countries of the core. Escudé theorized peripheral realism based on Argentine foreign policy, a semi-peripheral country, but

with geostrategies that have oscillated between subordination and autonomy. That is why I think that Mexico is a clearer case of Bizberg's first type (Table 8).

The intermediary mechanisms of Mexico in relation to the core, particularly the United States, are articulated through numerous US economic investments in Mexico, which have especially developed maquila-type production in this country. Formally, the North American Free Trade Agreement (NAFTA) is the main link, but this division of labor is also supported by mechanisms of political subjection. All the governments of Mexico of the period, even that of Andrés Manuel López Obrador, have accommodated themselves to this situation.

In turn, Mexico's domination of the Central American space is articulated through various geopolitical projects that have legal instruments, such as the Puebla Panama Plan (PPP) or the Tuxtla Gutiérrez Treaty, which sought to create a free trade area in Mexico and Central America.

The iron control of the southern border of Mexico —to which the government of López Obrador committed to the US' Trump administration in exchange for stopping the construction of the wall on its northern border— is another good example of the subordinate geostrategy by which Mexico's role is determined, which goes beyond even the alternation of governments of opposing political signs.

B) The geostrategy of autonomy in the semi-periphery: the case of Brazil

But the geostrategy of subordination is not the only possible type. Geostrategies of autonomy are also developed (the rebellions to which Escudé referred) and this is possible because, as Chase-Dunn points out, the semi-periphery is a space of opportunity for social movements and progressive governments:

The idea that the core/periphery hierarchy cuts across and harmonizes class relations in the core, and sometimes in the periphery, but that class struggles in the semi-periphery are not so mute, and thus transformative social movements, the ones that really challenge the logic of capitalism, tend to form and be more successful in the semi-periphery (1990: 2).

The resistance of semi-peripheral peoples to domination and exploitation from the core also provides a sample of the class struggle at a global level (Anderson and Chase-Dunn, 2005).

There is not a single autonomy geostrategy. They can be diverse, since there are different mechanisms to form it, and there can be multiple combinations. However, in general, all of them will use:

- Economic protection against international competition, particularly with respect to the productive sectors of the core.
- Strengthening of autonomous integration processes, such as CELAC, vis-à-vis the OAS and other supra-Latin American integration spaces.
- Coordination of policies with other semi-peripheral countries of the global South, such as India, China or Brazil.

In general, they can be summarized in the practice of affirming one's own voice in regional affairs; trying to weave autonomous alliances, and avoiding the follow-on of the hegemonic power in international affairs; and trying to agree with other powers that also develop autonomous geostrategies. Here we consider the case of Brazil, during the presidencies of Lula da Silva and Dilma Rouseff (Table 9).

Table 9. *Intermediary relationship in Brazil, 2003-2015 (autonomous semi-periphery)*

		<i>Relationship of internal alliance</i>	<i>Relationship of extra-regional agreement</i>
<i>Division of labor</i>	United States, European Union, Japan...		
	Brazil	MERCOSUR, CELAC...	China India African Atlantic countries...

Source: Author

During this period, Brazil was one of the main promoters of the autonomous integration processes in Latin America, such as UNASUR or CELAC. At the same time, Brazil agreed with other peripheries of the global South in various fora, such as the World Trade Organization, and in particular, promoted South-South cooperation within the BRICS.

The impulse of UNASUR and, within it, the creation of the South American Defense Council (CDS) in 2008 (Sanahuja and Verdes-Montenegro, 2014), had the aim of consolidating the region as a zone of peace, building an identity in defence and strengthening cooperation in the military field. Despite the fact that the UNASUR crisis is very deep (Bragatti, 2019), the creation of the CDS has favored the increase in trust between the states of the region. This is essential for the maintenance of regional peace and that favors its autonomous political integration.

In earlier times (for example, during the period of the military dictatorship) Brazil developed semi-peripheral geostrategies of subordination. The concept of “sub-imperialism” by Ruy Mauro Marini (1974; 1977) alludes to this period, and while it is certainly similar to that developed here, once again we find ourselves with a concept defined fundamentally from an economic basis:

“Sub-imperialism corresponds to the emergence of intermediate points in the organic composition of capital worldwide, as it progresses in the integration of production systems, as well as the arrival of a dependent economy at the stage of monopoly and financial capital. Likewise, Brazil can be identified as the purest expression of sub-imperialism, in our days” (Marini, 1974: 7).

It takes into account that it favors the “greater integration of the capitalist productive system and at the same time maintains the hegemony exercised by imperialism on the international scale” (Marini, 1977: 17). Marini identifies Brazil as the best example of sub-imperialism of the time, along with Mexico and Argentina in Latin America.

Conclusion

The introduction of political elements in the definition of the intermediate categories of the tripartite horizontal structure of the modern world-system allows us to successfully differentiate the states that we have called “semi-core” from those that we continue to consider “semi-periphery”. Both categories have an intermediary role, but the structural position they occupy in the world-system is different: the former are more articulated with the core, while the latter are more with the periphery.

Most of the authors define countries that make up the semi-periphery based on their role in the international division of labor and use economic data to differentiate them empirically. Geo-politicizing them has allowed us to better differentiate the semi-periphery from the semi-core, but it is important to understand that the need to geo-politicize the concepts of semi-core and semi-periphery does not mean that they do not have to be defined in geoeconomic terms as well. It must be remembered that the objective of this article was to complement the geoeconomic definition of semi-periphery, not to replace it.

The southern European semi-core have demonstrated their close geopolitical relationship with the core countries, to which they actually belong, and that precisely allows them to develop their intermediary relationship of domination with respect to not only distant or near peripheries, but also between different parts of the core area of the world-system.

The semi-periphery, unlike the semi-core, is framed in the periphery of the world-system, occupying its most dynamic segment which is in transition. It occupies an intermediary role in the general chain of production values. The semi-periphery are powerful geopolitically countries, and on many occasions, moreover, are large.

By politicizing the category of semi-periphery, we have also been able to differentiate two groups of geostrategies of these states: one that includes those more oriented to serve as a transmission belt for the core, and another that includes those that seek the autonomous development of the peoples of the South.

We were able to identify in geoeconomic terms the Latin American semi-peripheries after the geopolitical order of the Cold War, and we saw the contrasts in the characteristics of their economies, in particular their more extroverted or more self-centred character. In geopolitical terms, we find that they develop different geostrategies in the world-system, one more of subordination and another one of autonomy. In the Post-Cold War, Mexico is a good example of the first and Brazil

of the second (at least during the governments of Lula da Silva and Dilma Rouseff). The case of Argentina, which we have not dealt with, is in principle more ambiguous. Hypothetically, during the Kirchner governments, geostrategies of autonomy were adopted, while in the Macri government, geostrategies of subordination were developed, but the distinction does not seem to be so clear.

In short, the cases studied allow us to better support the hypothesis that (geo)politicizing the analysis of the semi-peripheries—that is, also reasoning about them in both geopolitical and geoeconomic terms—allows us to better explain the intermediary roles of these intermediate spaces in the modern world-system.

Scientific classifications cannot have a mere taxonomic purpose, which risk falling into a fatuous rhetorical exercise. I hope that the clarifications made in this article contribute to clarifying the concept of semi-periphery, that most authors consider to be obscure.

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The Changing Landscape of the Contemporary Orthodox World: Understanding its Evolution

Liubov Shmatkova¹

Abstract

For an extended period, the structure of the Orthodox world resembled that of sovereign states, allocating territory among independent churches based on canonical law. Despite professing faith unity, Orthodox relations persistently exhibit confrontations, often intertwined with politics through theological rhetoric. The dual system, blending territorial and national church sovereignty, along with canonical ambiguity, sparks disputes over boundaries and church independence. The national-territorial logic nurtures competing sovereignties. Post-revolution diasporas and overlapping jurisdictions further complicate matters, challenging the canonical 'one city, one bishop' principle. The Moscow-Constantinople schism signals deeper erosion, transforming canonical territories into arenas of competition, questioning the relevance of Orthodox rules. This erosion may extend beyond Orthodoxy, influencing contemporary geopolitics and providing insight for the future.

Key words:

Orthodox world, autocephaly, political geography, religious geography, diaspora, inter-Orthodox relations

¹ visiting researcher at the Center for Spatial Analysis in International Relations, Moscow State Institute of International Relations (MGIMO), lshmatkova@inno.mgimo.ru

Introduction

Over numerous generations, the Orthodox Christian world has been widely perceived and characterized as a notably intricate and multifaceted system of ecclesiastical entities, bearing a striking semblance to sovereign states in terms of its structural intricacies. This ecclesiastical framework is primarily distinguished by its territorial divisions and the presence of independent Orthodox churches, each presumed to hold an equal status within this complex system and all governed by established canonical law. Another widespread assumption was that this superficial resemblance to the organizational structures of nation-states remarkably endured over the course of history.

On the other hand, the Orthodox world itself has proclaimed the concept of spiritual unity. Until recently, it was common to characterize Orthodoxy as "unity in plurality." Comprising more than a dozen local churches with diverse local practices and lacking a centralized structure, body, or figurehead, it was still plausible to assert that Orthodoxy operated as a relatively effective church.

However, it is essential to recognize that beneath this seemingly unified exterior in the ecclesiastical realm, a multifaceted reality unfolds, characterized by profound complexities and a continual state of dynamic transformation.

In recent decades, and particularly in the last ten years, significant divisions have eroded the once-solid unity within Orthodoxy. Events such as the Holy and Great Council of the Orthodox Church in Crete, the Ecumenical Patriarchate's grant of autocephaly to the Orthodox Church of Ukraine, and Russia's military intervention in Ukraine have laid bare deeper rifts within world Orthodoxy. The latter undeniably constitutes a pivotal moment for Orthodoxy, as articulated by Nadieszda Kizenko in her lecture titled "A Vanishing Point: Unity in Orthodoxy and the Ukraine Crisis."

Critical transformations in the Orthodox world are significant not only for believers and church historians. The aforementioned resemblance to the system of nation-states is a reason to scrutinize the ongoing processes more closely. The central focus of this article revolves around the ongoing shift in the structural paradigm of the Orthodox world and its intricate connection with the realm of political processes. While Orthodoxy consistently emphasizes its theological unity, a closer and more nuanced scrutiny of the current ecclesiastical landscape uncovers a diverse and multifarious tableau.

The examination of the Orthodox world's transformation holds significance within the realm of political science for a multitude of reasons. Firstly, this is due to the enduring influence of religion on contemporary political processes, underscoring its continued relevance. This influence extends beyond domestic politics to reach the international stage. Secondly, and of particular intrigue, is how it challenges preconceived notions regarding the alignment between the systems of nation-states and autonomous Orthodox churches.

The Traditional Structure of the Orthodox World

For a substantial duration in history, the structural configuration of the Orthodox world has been likened to that of sovereign states. In this analogy, territories are distributed among independent Orthodox churches, each considered to be of equal stature in accordance with canonical law. These ecclesiastical divisions characterized by defined boundaries, designated capitals, and even ecclesiastical 'diplomatic' missions. This comparison significantly aligns the ecclesiastical landscape of Orthodoxy with the organizational structures of sovereign states, giving rise to analogous challenges.

Among the key concepts within the Orthodox world, the term "canonical territory" stands out prominently. Attempts to define its meaning draw parallels with the sovereign territory of a state. Although the concept of a canonical territory is relatively new, it is perceived as having historical roots (Oeldemann, 2008). In essence, a canonical territory can be succinctly understood as a territorial area whose boundaries correspond to the extent of autocephalous Orthodox Church activities, in accordance with the canons of the church. This concept plays a crucial role in shaping the dynamics of the Orthodox ecclesiastical landscape, influencing issues of jurisdiction, autonomy, and the relationships between different Orthodox churches. The evolving understanding of canonical territories reflects the intricate interplay between tradition, theology, and the contemporary challenges facing the Orthodox world.

One of the most prominent parallels can be observed in the absence of clear, universally accepted regulations pertaining to church independence, sovereignty, or autocephaly. This multifaceted subject transcends its conventional scope, traditionally encompassing matters such as the conferral, acquisition, or withdrawal of autocephaly. However, it has expanded to include a broader spectrum of inquiries, among which are the potential external interventions in the internal affairs of autocephalous local churches and the administration of parishes located outside the canonical territories of autocephalous churches, particularly within the context of the Orthodox diaspora. The analysis also incorporates the operational dynamics and significance of pan-Orthodox (supra-autocephalous) institutions within the context of inter-Orthodox relations (Shishkov, 2014). Simultaneously, the concept of autocephaly encompasses various dimensions that extend beyond canonical law and ecclesiology, thereby imbuing autocephaly with a quasi-mythological character (Hovorun, 2009).

Rather than having clear rules, the determination of ecclesiastical autocephaly predominantly relies on the interpretation of ancient canons established during an era closely associated with the Roman (Byzantine) Empire. Consequently, applying these canons to the contemporary context introduces a layer of ambiguity, as the historical and geopolitical contexts that shaped their creation significantly differ from present circumstances.

Within the Orthodox framework, the concept of church sovereignty lacks a definitive foundation, inviting further comparisons with sovereign states. Typically, a dual system is posited as the basis of church sovereignty, intertwining territorial and national elements. However, the inherent ambiguity in this duality raises questions about the precise nature of ecclesiastical authority and its delineations.

This inherent ambiguity in church sovereignty manifests in recurrent disputes over canonical boundaries and the pursuit of independence by select Orthodox churches. Declarations of independence, akin to acts of statehood, possess the potential to incite interchurch conflicts, often entangling the so-called Mother Church—the ecclesiastical entity from which the breakaway church originated—and other churches with vested interests in the region.

Moreover, the Orthodox ecclesiastical landscape reveals a striking paradox—an array of churches that exist with limited recognition or, in some instances, are entirely unrecognized by the broader Orthodox community. These churches, frequently bolstered by devoted followers and occasionally supported by states, occupy the periphery of Orthodox communion, challenging conventional notions of canonical recognition.

Unlike sovereign states, Orthodox churches lack military apparatuses to assert their claims through armed conflict. Nevertheless, they frequently wield the instrument of state power, forging intricate connections with political authorities to advance their ecclesiastical agendas. This convergence of church and state power underscores the intricate interplay between the ecclesiastical and political domains, further invoking parallels with the dynamics encountered within sovereign states.

Unity of Faith vs. Confrontational Relations

Within the intricate tapestry of Orthodox ecclesiastical structures, a paradox emerges—a professed unity of faith in Eastern Christianity contrasting starkly with the persistent confrontations characterizing relations among Orthodox churches. Despite declarations of a so-called unity of faith within Eastern Christianity, it becomes evident that the landscape of Orthodox interactions is marred by a continuous undercurrent of confrontation. Interestingly, the crux of disputes reverberating within the Orthodox world rarely originates in theological matters but is deeply intertwined with the realm of politics, even though it often veils itself in theological rhetoric.

To gain deeper insights into this paradox, it is essential to examine historical and contemporary examples of confrontations within the Orthodox world. Many of these conflicts have coincided with significant political transformations in their respective regions, shedding light on the intricate interplay between ecclesiastical and geopolitical dynamics.

One of the most conspicuous examples can be observed in the conflicts that unfolded between the Ecumenical Patriarchate and newly declared independent

national autocephalous churches in regions such as Bulgaria, Greece, and Romania (Leustean, 2014). While the specifics of each conflict may vary, the overarching direction remains remarkably similar. These confrontations epitomize the national-territorial logic intrinsic to the Orthodox structural framework, a logic that invariably leads to the assertion of competing sovereignties.

The intricate tapestry of the Orthodox world underwent a profound transformation in the aftermath of the Russian Revolution. The repercussions of this seismic event rippled across borders and reshaped the ecclesiastical landscape in unforeseen ways. A significant consequence of the Revolution was the forced exodus of thousands of Orthodox believers from the newly formed Soviet state. These displaced faithful found themselves scattered across a multitude of Orthodox and non-Orthodox countries, giving rise to a diaspora that would profoundly fracture the previously established Orthodox world structure.

The emergence of these diasporic communities introduced a layer of complexity and ambiguity into the Orthodox ecclesiastical landscape. Overlapping jurisdictions became a prevalent issue, driven by the confluence of revolutions and political transformations that marked the tumultuous 20th century. In some instances, pragmatic compromises were struck to accommodate these displaced communities. For example, in the Kingdom of Yugoslavia, the Serbian Church permitted Russian emigrants to maintain their existing church structures while on Yugoslavian territory. Nevertheless, such instances of fraternal accommodation were the exception rather than the rule.

Complicating matters further, the structures recognized by one Orthodox Church were not universally acknowledged by others. The Serbian Church's recognition of certain governing church structures for Russian emigrants was not reciprocated by the Russian Church in Moscow, exemplifying the divergent stances adopted within the Orthodox world.

In the 1920s, as a result of the mass emigration of Greeks from the territory of the former Ottoman Empire to Europe, America, and Australia, structures of the Ecumenical Patriarchate of Constantinople began to emerge on these continents. The Patriarchate proclaimed, as mentioned earlier, its jurisdiction over the entire church "diaspora," encompassing all countries outside the boundaries of historical Orthodox Churches. Practically, according to this perspective, almost all of Western Europe, North and South America, as well as Australia and Oceania, fell under the definition of the "diaspora." This development further added to the complexity of jurisdictional matters within the Orthodox ecclesiastical landscape, as various Orthodox Churches grappled with defining their roles and territories in the evolving diasporic context.

Another fault line in Orthodox unity emerged in the wake of the Russian Revolution—a conflict between the Ecumenical Patriarchate and the Russian Church over territories that had ceased to be part of the Russian Empire. This dispute encapsulated both the pursuit of national Orthodox Churches within newly

formed nation-states and the intricate question of primacy within the Orthodox world. These complex issues converged, adding a layer of tension to the evolving ecclesiastical landscape.

Deepening Erosion of Canonical Territories

Following the dissolution of the Soviet Union in 1991, several Orthodox churches (re)-emerged in post-Soviet nations, asserting their independence from Moscow. To legitimize this independence, they cited the 'one nation, one faith' model, a prevailing principle in Eastern Orthodoxy that intricately interlinks state and church authority. These post-Soviet churches actively pursued recognition of their autonomy directly from the Ecumenical Patriarchate, despite being situated in what the Moscow Patriarchate regarded as its canonical territory.

The culmination of this enduring conflict between the Ecumenical Patriarchate and the Russian Church found its most contentious point in a dispute over church jurisdiction in Estonia in 1995. This dispute, rooted in historical grievances and unresolved issues of church territory, epitomized the lingering divisions and unresolved gaps that continued to plague the Orthodox world.

The events unfolding within the Orthodox world may initially seem disconnected from the broader transformations of the modern world, but they are actually closely intertwined with contemporary political processes.

This deep connection between ecclesiastical conflicts and political dynamics is particularly evident in the case of Ukraine. The granting of autocephaly to the independent Church of Ukraine serves as a vivid illustration of how politics and church governance intersect, resulting in a complex and highly politicized narrative. In January 2019, the Ecumenical Patriarchate in Istanbul granted independence to the newly established Orthodox Church of Ukraine. This decision was based on an imagined Byzantine heritage and asserted cultural leadership within the Orthodox community. Rooted in the Constantinopolitan Consensus, which recognizes the Patriarchate in Istanbul as the primary authority among Orthodox churches, this move led to political tensions. Ukrainian President Poroshenko made church autocephaly a central part of his 2019 re-election campaign (Ponomariov, 2016). Moscow Patriarchate leaders interpreted these developments as hostile actions, further escalating tensions within Ukraine and with Russia.

In fact, the schism between Moscow and Constantinople (now also involving Greece and Alexandria) appears to be one-sided. The Russian Patriarch ceased commemorating the heads of these Churches in the diptychs, yet they did not reciprocate in a similar manner. However, the repercussions of Ukrainian autocephaly reverberated throughout the Orthodox community. People and parishes find themselves compelled to align with one side or the other in a restructuring of institutional frameworks that jeopardizes their sense of belonging and their access to sacred spaces (Kormina, Naumescu, 2020).

This divide was not just a two-sided conflict; it extended beyond the immediate players and had implications for the broader Orthodox world. The Russian Church, for instance, took steps to establish its ecclesiastical structures in regions traditionally under the jurisdiction of the Alexandria Patriarchate in Africa and the Ecumenical Patriarchate in Southeast Asia. These actions challenged previously undisputed canonical territories, escalating tensions within the Orthodox world and placing the ROC in an ambiguous position.

Simultaneously, the Ecumenical Patriarchate, drawing on the rationale outlined in the document conferred upon the Ukrainian Church, intensified its efforts within Lithuania. Historically linked to the jurisdiction of Constantinople but presently recognized as falling under the canonical purview of the Russian Church, Lithuania became the next focal point of this ecclesiastical activity. Patriarch Bartholomew's visit to Lithuania in 2023 marked a significant development. During his visit, he met with the Lithuanian Prime Minister and expressed openness to establishing an Exarchate of the Ecumenical Patriarchate in Lithuania. A cooperation agreement was signed, emphasizing the importance of allowing individuals to practice their faith without conflicting with their conscience. This pertains not only to Orthodox citizens of Lithuania but also to Ukrainians seeking refuge from the war instigated by Russia and Belarusians who relocated to Lithuania due to repression in their homeland.

Lithuania has also welcomed a significant number of Russian emigrants with humanitarian visas, including activists, journalists, regional politicians, artists, and musicians. Alongside the Lithuanian Orthodox community, the Belarusian, Ukrainian, and Greek diasporas constitute a potential congregation for the new church structure. Capable and intellectually qualified priests expelled from the Russian Orthodox Church by Metropolitan Innocent of Lithuania expedited the process of creating a parallel structure.

Similar situations are unfolding in other countries considered part of the canonical territories of the Russian Orthodox Church. In Latvia, active state involvement in church affairs led to pressure on entities affiliated with the Russian Orthodox Church to declare autocephaly. In September 2022, the Latvian Saeima approved amendments granting autocephalous status to the Latvian Orthodox Church. In 2023, the Latvian Orthodox Church demonstrated its independence by ordaining the first Latvian bishop in its modern history. Despite contravening the Charter of the Russian Orthodox Church, the Latvian Church invokes the "preservation and strengthening of Holy Orthodoxy in Latvia" within today's historical realities.

In Estonia, after the delineation of spheres of influence between Moscow and Constantinople in 1995, the situation seems less complex. Nevertheless, political considerations continue to intersect with ecclesiastical matters. In February 2023, Metropolitan Eugene of Tallinn incurred disapproval from governmental authorities due to his involvement in a pro-Russian event. Despite the clergyman's characterization of himself and his ecclesiastical institution as "victims" of a politically motivated provocation, state officials maintain that his actions brought

him uncomfortably close to certain well-defined "red lines," which could result in his expulsion from the country.

In Moldova, an unclear situation is evolving in Kishinev, where a scandal is unfolding within Orthodox communities. Some seek to switch from the jurisdiction of the Moscow Patriarchate to the Romanian Orthodox Church, while others wish to remain loyal to the Russian Orthodox Church.

This dynamic extends across the broader Orthodox world, with almost the entire so-called canonical territory of the Russian Orthodox Church outside Russia itself experiencing transformations tied to political processes. The intricate interplay between politics, ecclesiology, and national identity has become a defining feature of these conflicts, involving not only Orthodox churches but also international organizations and governments. We are presently witnessing a significant schism within Eastern Orthodoxy. Despite the historical alignment of Slavic Orthodox churches with the Russian Orthodox Church, its recent actions, including active support for the aggressive war against Ukraine and assertive initiatives in Africa and Asia, have raised concerns about the potential for the ROC to encounter international or inter-Orthodox isolation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the modern Orthodox world is undergoing a profound transformation that challenges its traditional structure. For centuries, it has been compared to a system of sovereign states, with territories divided among independent Orthodox churches based on canonical law—a structure mirroring nation-state sovereignty. However, beneath this surface lies a complex web of challenges.

The absence of clear rules governing church independence, reliance on interpretations of ancient canons, and disputes over canonical boundaries all contribute to ongoing conflicts. These confrontations are often political rather than theological, as seen in the recent granting of autocephaly to the independent Church of Ukraine.

In summary, we are witnessing a significant erosion of the Orthodox Church's traditional structure, with even previously uncontested canonical territories becoming arenas of competition. This erosion challenges the very foundations of the Orthodox system, ushering in a new era of uncertainty within Eastern Christianity.

One preferable approach to address this challenge is the rejection of the canonical territories system. In this scenario, churches would coexist rather than compete, resembling the Orthodox communities in North America where individuals can attend churches under the Greek Archdiocese, the OCA, or, for instance, a Serbian Church. This alternative aligns more closely with the realities experienced in the

diaspora. However, it necessitates a redefinition of a fundamental principle in ecclesiology and the very idea of the Orthodox structure resembling national states.

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PANEL III
REACTING TO THE „SHATTERED“ WORLD
THE SYSTEM, THE REGION, THE ACTOR

Chair: Vladimir Ajzenhamer

Discussant: Marta Zorko

Sun Tzu “visits” the European Union: Geopolitical subordination and functional specialization in the Strategic Compass

Carlos González-Villa¹ and Branislav Radeljić²

Abstract:

The chapter examines the European Union’s Strategic Compass, its most recent security document. The authors argue that to comprehend the Strategic Compass, it is necessary to look beyond its immediate aims and conveyed messages. Instead, the document should be understood as a symptom of social transformations in Europe, the continuity of geopolitical subordination, and the reproduction of bureaucratic dynamics. To shed light on these questions, the authors turn to the five fundamental factors of war in Sun Tzu’s *The Art of War*: the moral law, heaven, earth, method and discipline, and command. Accordingly, the problems surrounding the definition of the European strategy are above all about the drafter’s position in the European bureaucratic and social ecosystem. In this sense, it can be concluded that European foreign and security policies are controlled by a dominant group rather than a leading one, and this dominance may crumble when individual national interests can be better served independently, such as through direct interactions with the United States.

Keywords:

EU, NATO, Russia, United States, Strategic Compass, geopolitics, war

¹ Assistant Professor of Political Science, Department of Legal Sciences and Public Law, Faculty of Law and Social Sciences, University of Castilla-La Mancha, Toledo, Spain, Carlos.GonzalezVilla@uclm.es

² Professor of International Relations, Department of Government and Society, College of Humanities and Social Sciences, United Arab Emirates University, Al Ain, UAE, radeljic@uaeu.ac.ae; Visiting Professor of European Politics, Department of International Relations, School of Law and International Relations, Nebrija University, Madrid, Spain, BRadeljic@nebrija.es

Introduction

The Strategic Compass (SC),³ adopted by the European Council in March 2022, is the European Union's most recent security document. As such, it meets the expectations of a text of this nature, insofar as it contains an identification of a *thing* worth protecting, including the threats it faces and the means it must have in order to avert them. These questions revolve around that *thing*, and these end up telling a story about the consideration that the drafter of the document has for it and for itself. Thus, the European External Action Service (EEAS), which was in charge of drafting the SC, places the values and interests of the EU in the so-called global rules-based order (European Council 2022, 14)—a context that is as much discussed outside as inside the West that has shaped it (Acharya 2021), and that is not necessarily related to international law (Dugard 2023). Next, the SC is concerned with “multilayered threats”, including instability in the EU's neighborhood, Russia's “aggressive and revisionist actions”, and the “assertiveness” of China's regional behavior (European Council 2022, 17–20). Finally, this lengthy document—the number of pages in the final German version is 47, which more than triples the initial mandate (Wagner 2022, 13)—calls for expanding the EU's Common Foreign and Security Policy complex (also in the area of military capabilities). An underlying message of the document is that the world is no longer what it used to be or, as Josep Borrell has pointed out in one of the metaphors that have characterized his tenure as High Representative and Vice President of the European Commission, “we cannot be herbivores in a world of carnivores” (Rodriguez-Pina 2022).⁴ After all, Europe, as Borrell said on another occasion, is a “French garden” surrounded by a world that obeys the “law of the jungle” (Alemanno & Mouyal 2022), and the defense of Europe requires a different approach from the one resting within the liberal perspective.

Despite being approved just after the Russian military intervention in Ukraine (Wagner 2022), the SC was already obsolete regardless of its ambition, as pointed out by some think tanks sympathetic to the Brussels bureaucracy (EPC 2022; Witney 2022). The ambitions of the document were soon subsumed by the deadlines (the completion of all targets is foreseen for 2030), by unflattering precedents, and, above all, by the closing of ranks with the US as an ally in the framework of the war in Ukraine and renewal of a great power competition. In this way, “strategic autonomy”, the concept that had served as a driver for the drafting of the document, has been significantly blurred.

The strengthening of ties with the transatlantic ally following the Russian intervention in Ukraine has seemed automatic thanks to the fact that “strategic autonomy”—beyond Borrell's standpoint and pomposity of such an approach—is a concept contested from within the EU. The idea of having “an ability to think for

³ Its complete title is: “A strategic compass for security and defense: for a European Union that protects its citizens, values and interests and contributes to international peace and security” (European Council 2022).

⁴ The idea is not original. The concern about the EU being “the last herbivore in a world full of carnivores” had already been present for at least two years in the dissemination apparatuses akin to the EU power centers (Fabre et al. 2020).

oneself and to act according to one's own values and interests" (Borrell 2020) has a limited scope, especially if one attends to the German approach, without which "there can be no European strategic autonomy or autonomization" (Lippert et al. 2019). In an article entitled "Europe still needs America", published by *Politico.eu* in November 2020 and right before the US presidential election, the then German defense minister stated emphatically that "[i]llusions of European strategic autonomy must come to an end: Europeans will not be able to replace America's crucial role as a security provider" (Kramp-Karrembauer 2020). From the German perspective, the reinforcement of European security capabilities must always go hand in hand with the relationship with the Americans despite tensions with the Trump administration (Banka 2022). Significantly, the President of the European Commission (and Kramp-Karrembauer's predecessor in office), Ursula von der Leyen, set a line in her speech to the European Parliament in September 2021 when she refrained from using the term "strategic autonomy"; instead, she associated the idea of a "European Defense Union" with the strengthening of the links between the EU and NATO (Herszenhorn 2021). Thus, the approach that shapes the document, despite being defended by France (Martin 2023), as well as Spain—it declared it a priority of its presidency of the EU Council in the second half of 2023 (La Moncloa 2023)—has primarily been supported by the EU's key members and openly challenged by a large part of the Eastern European states (*New Direction* 2020). Indeed, as suggested by a high-ranking Lithuanian official, it is the American presence that would possibly be key for security of the Baltic state, rather than its NATO membership and German support (Bennhold 2022). In addition to these divergences, since the outbreak of war in Ukraine it seems that the concept has not managed to evolve and transform itself into anything more substantial, as ECFR analyst Ulrike Franke points out (Dempsey 2023).

To come closer to understanding why this is so, it is worth examining the SC more for its symptomatic character as to who is in charge of European foreign policy(ies) than for its actual ability to articulate a consistent approach in a rapidly changing environment. This suggests that, as Gramsci would put it, European leadership is in the hands of a dominant rather than a leading group, which may collapse as soon as different national interests can be served more effectively separately rather than jointly (for example, through direct dealings with the United States). To unpack these dynamics through the SC, we may turn to *The Art of War*, attributed to Sun Tzu ([fifth century BC] 2000), which specifies that the general who masters the five fundamental factors of war wins, and who does not, is defeated. The outlook offered by the Chinese classic is timely, given that, while for him "the art of war [...] is a matter of life and death, a road either to safety or to ruin" (2000, 1), the SC points out that "[i]n this era of growing strategic competition, complex security threats and the direct attachment on the European security order, the security of our citizens and our Union is at stake" (European Council 2022, 14). Corresponding to the fragility of its driving idea, the document does not cover the five factors in a satisfactory and articulated manner.

The moral law

“The Moral Law”, as the first constant factor, “causes the people to be in complete accord with their ruler, so that they will follow him regardless of their lives, undismayed by any danger” (Sun Tzu 2000, 1). The “geopolitical Europe” tries to insert itself into its sociopolitical context through a definition of Europe’s norms and values, which seems less and less adequate to define the actual developments on the continent. Thus, while the SC points out that “[w]e must act as a strong and coherent political actor to uphold the values and principles underpinning our democracies” (European Council 2022, 10), the EU has encountered major economic, sociopolitical, and strategic orientation fractures; they are reflected in growing inequalities, political polarization, and the loss of international economic clout (Rachman 2023). Taking everything into account, the SC represents another turn of the screw in the existential crisis of the EU, in a similar way to that of the Global Strategy of 2016. The latter, in contrast to the so-called Solana strategy of 2003, “can be seen as a new security narrative for the EU [...] in a scenario of widespread citizen disaffection in the face of the social crisis and the erosion of economic and social rights, the growing job insecurity, the uncertainty in the face of socioeconomic change and fear, stirred up by extreme right-wing forces, in the face of terrorism or migration” (Sanahuja 2018, 18). Anderson (2011, xv) had already pointed out more than a decade ago that “the Union is now widely presented as a paragon for the rest of the world, even as it becomes steadily less capable of winning the confidence of its citizens, and more and more openly flouts the popular will”.

However, there are historical continuities in the relationship between policy planners and implementers in Brussels and in European societies. Here, it is worth taking into account the elitist and technocratic *modus operandi* that the process of European integration has had since its early beginning (Anderson 2011, 475–504). In recent decades, this is particularly evident in the bureaucratic expansion of EU foreign policy through the relatively autonomous development of a “transnational space” in which elected officials, think tanks, businesses, academics, and media have been Europeanizing foreign policy debates (Veselinović 2022). Accordingly, the EU is projected as a “normative power” specializing in the export of values (Manners 2002; Rodríguez Prieto 2019).

Another historical continuity is based on the existence of two streams within the political-institutional bureaucracy. While the traditional account of European integration refers to the role that social democracy and Christian democracy once played in pushing forward institutional integration (accompanied, depending on the context, by liberals and Eurocommunists), the present EU is characterized by two political camps that admittedly play a similar role: the social-liberal and the nationalist right. Despite the cultural battles, both blocs have ended up pushing forward the SC in the European Council.

In a more fundamental way, Europe is going through a phase of transition in terms of dominant economic policy approaches that could end with both political factions embracing the approach of the neo-Schumpeterian economic school. This, beyond

the rhetoric and most prominent political references (including, outside Europe, Presidents Gabriel Boric and Gustavo Petro, or US Representative Alexandria Ocasio-Cortez), seems to position itself as a new economic orthodoxy.⁵ The dilemma is that the main representative of this school, Mariana Mazzucato (2013), seems to have inspired debates that have more to do with the difficulties of adaptation of some political actors and the analytical errors of liberal intellectuals (Rallo 2020), than with the real economic proposal of *mazzucatonomics*, which has nothing to do with socialism (Roberts 2019). The advantage of this school is its ability to insert itself into the current political phase after neoliberalism (Bregman 2020), as well as into the historical current of technological transformations. In this framework, as Pérez (2005, 51) points out, “each technological revolution brings with it not only the reorganization of the productive structure but, eventually, also such a profound transformation of governmental institutions, of society, and even of ideology and culture that one can speak of the construction of successive and distinct *modes of growth* in the history of capitalism”.

Social democracy and Christian democracy successfully navigated the maturation phase of what Pérez (2005, 44) calls, the “age of oil, the automobile, and mass production” in post-World War II Western Europe through Keynesian economic policy. In a similar way, today the social-liberal and national-conservative camps may end up cohabiting around a new program of state intervention built on the basis of the retreating economic orthodoxy (neoliberalism). In fact, *mazzucatonomics* does not propose a resizing of the state, but rather a change in the orientation as regards state intervention—through new imaginaries associated with social equality and the creation of new opportunities (Gerbaudo 2021).

This approach seems to be contradicted by short-term political battles and far-right driven culture wars (Veiga et al. 2019), which affect different sectors of the population and convey an image of irreconcilable polarization. But it so happens that, absorbed in this situation, we may forget that the Cold War period in Western Europe was much harsher than in other hotspots, in many respects. The idyllic image of the men (such as Jean Monnet, Konrad Adenauer, or Alcide De Gasperi), who promoted European integration thanks to a mixture of pragmatism and generosity—in reality, implied promotion of economic miracles, supported by *the American friend*. This is immediately tarnished by a panorama characterized by state terrorism, the incorporation of Nazi-fascist cadres into the new state structures and international organizations, colonial wars, the deprivation of the most elementary rights for women, and so on.

Brussels’ technocracy, in charge of drafting the SC, can potentially count on political support to keep the idea of “strategic autonomy” afloat, albeit only within its transnational space. Moving in an ambiguous terrain, in which federalist-leaning

⁵ One of the leading authors of this trend has spoken along these lines on *Twitter*: <https://twitter.com/CarlotaPrzPerez/status/1587515997992669184> (accessed June 20, 2023). Mariana Mazzucato (2021), on the other hand, spoke after the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic about a “new global economic consensus”.

discursive bombast is combined with very limited objectives, the document may survive while awaiting more propitious times.

Heaven

If it were to follow the tone of the years prior to the war in Ukraine, the weather issue would probably be viewed through the lens of Russia’s “hybrid war” against the West, prevalent in the past decade. It would also speak of Russia’s ability (and that of China) to exploit the effects of climate change (in the form of massive population displacement and food insecurity) to their own advantage (Braw 2019). Reflecting earlier discourse in Brussels, the SC contains dozens of references to “hybrid threats” and the development of capabilities to counter them. This includes the development of a “hybrid toolbox”, with military and civilian capabilities which “should comprise for instance preventive, cooperative, stabilization, restrictive, and recovery measures, as well as strengthen solidarity and mutual assistance” in the fields of information, electoral processes, and critical infrastructure (European Council 2022, 34). However, the return of conventional warfare to Europe has significantly reduced the noise generated by the hybrid war discourse. The climate, on the one hand, has become a real element in the development of warfare operations (Al Yafai 2023), which reduces the possibility for the deployment of the “hybrid war” discourse in this case.⁶ On the other hand, the boomerang effect of EU sanctions against Russia also invalidates this reasoning. European decision-makers have gone on the warpath by instrumentalizing the question of energy in the conflict, consequently mobilizing their population to do so. The title of the plan prepared by the International Energy Agency (2022)—“Playing my part: How to save money, reduce reliance on Russian energy, support Ukraine and help the planet”—is symptomatic in this regard.⁷

European planners seem to have overcome the dangers facing the continent in the winter of 2023 thanks to high temperatures and the availability of sufficient energy reserves. From here, three questions emerge. The first concerns medium- and long-term projections. As per different warnings, the situation will be different in the following years, as a result of dwindling reserves, the Chinese economic recovery (which will absorb part of the European LNG demand),⁸ and the possibility that gas trade with Russia could be stopped entirely, all of which may end up in a scenario of consumption restrictions and price increases (Campanella 2023). All this stems from the inability to formulate an alternative to Europe’s energy dependence and poverty. The alternatives being explored, apart from LNG imports, are all long term, and the green hydrogen corridor, optimistically touted by the local propaganda machines, will not be active before 2030 (*Público* 2023). Ironically, that

⁶ More generally, this discourse has lost momentum as it has become clear that Russian influence in the 2016 US elections was non-existent (Starks 2023).

⁷ The membership of this organization does not represent the universal vocation of its name, as only 31 states belong to it, all of them Western allies.

⁸ The EU, moreover, does not have enough long-term LNG contracts in place (Rashad & Bousso 2023).

is the same year used by the SC to mark the completion of the initiatives to strengthen the EU's security policy.

The second question has to do with the consequences that this issue is having on the process of European integration and the way it is proceeding. As Adam Tooze (2022) points out:

“Europe has a track record of big crises with big bills. But this one is particularly tricky to handle. After the banking crises of the late 2000s, Germany did not want to foot the bill for a common bank insurance fund to support weaker banks in Italy and Spain. But at least those countries’ efforts to support their own ailing banks made Germany’s banks more, rather than less, safe. The opposite is precisely the situation regarding energy subsidies. Uncoordinated gas stockpiling by the richest consumers prices poorer consumers out of the market to the benefit of speculators. In this regard, the measures taken so far to meet the crisis are akin to vaccine nationalism or protectionist policies to hoard limited supplies of personal protective equipment.”

But, as Tooze himself notes, the response to the COVID-19 pandemic was based on an agreement between France and Germany, whereas the current relations between these two powers are at a very low level, mostly because of divergences regarding energy supply, and security and defense policy (Gebauer et al. 2023). In this respect, “strategic autonomy” can be seen as one of the “empty signifiers” referred to in theories of populism (Laclau 2007). In the absence of real content, it serves as an umbrella for Paris to defend its defense industry and its own foreign policy priorities—through artifacts such as the European Intervention Initiative (Witney 2018)—while Berlin uses the concept as a formula to win a few months in its battle against time.

The third question relates to the credibility of the EU's foreign policy (and that of its Member States), as manifested in the ups and downs of its approach to Venezuela. It seems that, had the drafter of the document had the opportunity, or paid more attention, he might have preferred to delete the following paragraph in the latest revisions of the SC in view of the dizzying changes that have been taking place (European Council 2022, 20): “A fragile Central America and a persistent crisis in Venezuela contribute to regional divisions and strong migratory pressures, fueling further drug-related organized crime challenges and endangering peace efforts in Colombia”.

This is partly due to the wrongness of the approach. The SC was certainly approved months before the Colombian–Venezuelan reconciliation which, among other things, has allowed Venezuela—for four years, it had promoted and accompanied the dialogue between the Colombian government and the FARC-EP guerrilla (culminating in the Peace Agreements of 2016)—to now host talks with the National Liberation Army. The issue of timing also comes into play: in the new scenario, opened up by the war in Ukraine and uncertainties regarding the supply of energy, attempts to re-establish ties with Venezuela have accelerated. Leaders such as Emmanuel Macron or António Costa ensured that their greeting of President Nicolás Maduro was caught on camera at COP-27, held in November 2022 in Sharm El-Sheikh. This contrasts with the leaked snapshot in January 2019 in which Pedro

Sánchez, walking on snow in Davos, was talking on the phone to Juan Guaidó, a member of Parliament who, in a bizarre move, had just inaugurated himself as president in front of a congregation of supporters in Caracas.

Earth

The third factor “comprises distances, great and small; danger and security; open ground and narrow passes; the chances of life and death” (Sun Tzu 2000, 2). The geographical definition of risks and threats of the SC is subordinated to the North American agenda. This characteristic can be traced back to the origins of the process of European integration. As per Anderson (2011, 17), the success of the Monnet plan and the overcoming of the intergovernmental modus operandi had to do with the predisposition of small states and, above all, with American sponsorship and—at times, pressure—in the context of Cold War battlefield:

“Monnet’s strength as an architect of integration did not lie in any particular leverage with European cabinets—even if he eventually came to enjoy the confidence of Adenauer—but in his direct line to Washington. American pressure, in the epoch of Acheson and Dulles, was crucial in putting real—not merely ideal—force behind the conception of ‘ever greater union’ that came to be enshrined in the Treaty of Rome.”

The vicissitudes of the North American global strategy kept impacting on the evolution of European integration, as it happened after the incorporation of the United Kingdom and the recalibration of US foreign policy in the 1970s. But fundamentally, the European initiatives for a common foreign policy have failed to develop an original definition of security, even in the post-Cold War context, which witnessed the return of German hegemony, the introduction of the EU Economic and Monetary Union, and the deployment of a foreign policy of variable geometry in the EU’s neighborhood. In this scenario, the Common Foreign and Security Policy, institutionalized in 1999 with the creation of the Office of the High Representative, was limited from the outset by Washington’s demands, channeled through NATO’s role in the field of military cooperation. Respectively, the EU focused on the development of its civilian capacities in the field of state-building through its interventions in the so-called failed states (Woodward 2017, 90).

Subsequently, the idea of “strategic autonomy” seemed to transcend the previous reality, or at least provide for what Josep Borrell implied when asking himself: “What is the opposite of autonomy? Dependence. Nope? One is autonomous or dependent. Does anyone want to be dependent? I do not think so. A political entity such as Europe should not pretend to be dependent but to be autonomous” (cited in Lázaro 2020). Along these lines, Anderson (2021, 21) points out that, in the context of Trump presidency, a transatlantic “nuanced unity” developed with respect to China and Russia:

Where China was the prime foe for America, against whom Trump declared an all-out economic and political offensive, Russia was treated as a lesser danger. For the EU both

were menaces to Western democracy, but the order of battle tended to be the opposite. Viewed from Europe, Russia was not only closer geographically, but perceived as a deadlier threat; whereas China was a more distant power, and notwithstanding its own chargesheet of repression, might—if held at arm’s length—serve as potentially pragmatic partner in questions of commerce and climate. With Member States resisting American pressure to cancel the Nord Stream gas line from Russia to Germany, and to defer a trade pact with China, the EU has so far pursued its own economic interests, while joining with the US in resonant demands for an ideologically tough-minded defense of the Free World.

Following the Russian invasion of Ukraine in 2022, those nuances appear to have been further limited. Nord Stream has been permanently disabled, in the face of the thunderous silence of Germany, the main victim of the sabotage suffered by the gas pipelines. The trade relationship with China will end up suffering consequences of the geopolitical confrontation and structural trends related to deglobalization (Manfredi-Sánchez 2021; Mariotti 2022). In the context of the Ukrainian crisis, from both sides of the Atlantic, a wide range of sanctions have been deployed against Russia, the rearmament and training of the Ukrainian army has intensified, and the solution to the conflict is entrusted to developments on the battlefield, ruling out diplomatic means. The dynamic in place is that of consolidation of NATO “as a vehicle for political and military domination in Europe” (Cafruny et al. 2022, 2), and as an ever-expanding organization that threatens international security (González-Villa & Radeljić 2023). Such an ambition is reflected in the three 2022 strategic documents, published on both sides of the Atlantic: the EU’s SC, NATO’s Strategic Concept, and the United States’ National Security Strategy. This dynamic is best understood through the notion of geopolitical codes (Flint & Taylor 2018; Gaddis 2005), or representations of the world contained in security documents including operational principles that underpin security policies of political actors. Specifically, “[s]uch a code will have to incorporate a definition of a state’s interests, an identification of external threats to those interests, a planned response to such threats, and a justification for that response”, in addition to an “evaluation of places” beyond borders, which is based on their strategic importance at the local (relative to neighbors), regional (beyond the immediate neighborhood), and global levels (Flint & Taylor 2018, 51).

Although there are as many geopolitical codes as there are actors, they are still susceptible to the dynamics of politico–military alliances. The EU’s SC does not offer an original geopolitical code, but rather places itself, with few nuances, into that of the United States and its projection within NATO. In all three cases, China and Russia lead the definition of geopolitical codes at a global level, with the exception of NATO’s Strategic Concept, which, after focusing on Russia and before covering China, mentions terrorism, instability in the Middle East and North Africa, and violence against civilians in armed conflicts (NATO 2022, 4–5). Concerning the Asian giant, the Strategic Compass puts forward the idea that China represents “a partner for cooperation, an economic competitor and a systemic rival”, with which issues of mutual interest can be discussed, such as climate change; this is done within a framework of “growing concerns” deriving from “[t]he asymmetry in the openness of our markets” (European Council 2022, 8). This position corresponds to the

North American definition, although the latter is more specific in terms of strategic issues. After outlining the main concern—China’s ability to alter the international order and establish a large area of influence in the Indo-Pacific—the Americans go on to identify areas of common interest, including climate change and global public health, all being key for a “human progress” and “peaceful coexistence” (White House 2022, 23–24).

The differences between the North American and European strategies reflect a “lack of strategic foresight” on the European side, which, despite sharing the assessment of threats with the Americans, underestimates the developments in the Indo-Pacific; at best, the EU is an aspiring regional power (Blockmans et al. 2022). The solution to the problem of how to manage relations in their given environment could emerge from the passage of time, through a policy of *fait accompli*: “More probably, and as usual, Europeans will wait for the US to tell them what to do, as it departs for the Pacific” (Witney 2022). The alternatives would imply a development of diplomacy-based policy that would be capable of stopping the Russo-Ukrainian war and the accompanying supply of armament, although such a move would also require a distancing from warmongering positions in Washington (Aguirre 2022).

The Russian threat—which is subordinate to the Chinese for the North Americans—occupies the first place for the Europeans, which underpins the regional orientation of the SC. In the view of the Atlantic Alliance, it is “the most significant and direct threat to Allies’ security and to peace and stability in the Euro-Atlantic area” (NATO 2022, 4). When talking about the Kremlin and global security, the US resorts to accusations of “imperialist foreign policy” and of violation of the fundamental principles of the Charter of the United Nations in relation to “respect for sovereignty, territorial integrity, and the prohibition against acquiring territory through war” (White House 2022, 25–26). Following a regional review of Russian foreign policy of the previous decade, the EU’s SC emphasizes Moscow’s aim “to establish so-called spheres of influence”, seeing them to “constitute a long-term and direct threat for European security” (European Council 2022, 7).

With regard to addressing the Russian invasion of Ukraine, there is no alternative to supporting the Ukrainian resistance. For the US, “[a]longside [its] allies and partners, America is helping to make Russia’s war on Ukraine a strategic failure” (White House 2022, 26). For the EU, by “[s]upporting Ukraine in facing Russia’s military aggression, [the Europeans] are showing an unprecedented resolve to restore peace in Europe, together with [their] partners” (European Council 2022, 2). Finally, for NATO, “[a] strong, independent Ukraine is vital for the stability of the Euro-Atlantic area” (NATO 2022, 1). However, none of the above is open for diplomacy. At most, the North Americans concede that other scenarios can be assessed once a political change in Russia has taken place (White House 2022, 26). But in the European case, there is a fundamental contradiction in the intention to make the EU a key participant in the disputed multipolar world (European Council 2022, 7), yet without being able to propose an alternative as to how to deal with its most powerful neighbor.

Method and discipline

The fifth factor—we leave the fourth for the end—concerns method and discipline, which “are to be understood as the marshaling of the army in its proper subdivisions, the graduations of rank among the officers, the maintenance of roads by which supplies may reach the army, and the control of military expenditure” (Sun Tzu 2000, 2). The deployment of EU foreign policy is consistent with its technocratic nature. Although it lacks modesty in justifying its actions—European values are characterized by infallibility—there is a correspondence between political and bureaucratic-institutional development. This speaks of an organization that is more focused on its own reproduction than on the protection task entrusted to it despite the importance of the intergovernmental model in the deployment of the EU’s foreign policy, including its theoretical dimension, consequently providing space for new intergovernmentalisms (Salomón 1999). In fact, the narratives and policymaking that surround the process of state-building in the EU’s neighborhood are fully aware of, if not closely related to, federalist and neo-functionalist approaches (Bergmann 2019).

The SC makes repeated references to the EU’s “values and interests”, both to define the document’s referent object—“we set out a common strategic vision [...] to protect our interests and defend our values” (European Council 2022, 15)—and as an objective, as in the policy toward the Western Balkans, where “[t]angible progress on the rule of law and reforms based on European values, rules and standards needs to continue” (European Council 2022, 19). In addition, it is in the name of these values and interests that the prospects of bureaucratic expansion are tested through the proposal of a series of objectives of the EU’s 2030 security and defense policy; the Strategic Compass contains multiple references to capabilities (111 in total), development (53), enhancement (43), innovation (25), fostering (8), optimization (6), and modernization (3). All this is reflected in the length of the document, the final version of which (47 pages) has far exceeded the first draft (28 pages), let alone the initial length, mutually agreed by Member States (15 pages) (Wagner 2022, 13).

Despite its length and listed purposes, the Strategic Compass reveals an ambition that can be misleading. The most obvious targets are far away from the identified threats. They also represent precedents that have not been sufficiently exploited, as in the case of the proposal to create a “rapid deployment capacity” of up to 5,000 soldiers (European Council 2022, 6). In addition, such an idea disregards the existence of the scarcely used combat groups of 1,500 soldiers (Reykers 2017), which clearly suggests that “there seems no obvious reason why Europeans or anyone else should take this new initiative seriously” (Witney 2022). Another of the document’s star proposals concerns an intent to revisit the application of Article 44 of the European Union Treaty. This happens five years after the introduction of the EU-led Permanent Structured Cooperation, whose security- and defense-related projects have already experienced major delays (Barigazzi 2021), as well as disagreements between allies, such as the one between France and Germany as to where to position

a missile defense system, the nature of which also involved some Eastern European allies.

The Strategic Compass calls for strengthening of “intelligence-based situational awareness and relevant EU capacities, notably in the framework of the EU Single Intelligence Analysis Capability, as well as the EU Satellite Center” (European Council 2022, 33). In the absence of clarification in relation to the pursuit of “situational awareness”, previous precedents should not be downplayed here, whatsoever; while the existing mechanisms have managed to provide decision-makers with valuable analysis, problems have still arisen when decision-makers decide not to consider the material provided. The consequences accompanying the Arab Spring can serve as a case in point. Even though the then Joint Situation Center (renamed European Union Intelligence Analysis Centre in 2012) had warned of potential repercussions of a hypothetical crisis in the Middle East—the rise of terrorist threats, influxes of migrants and refugees into the EU, and side effects of sociopolitical disintegration as an alternative to the authoritarian regimes of the region—they were not taken seriously by the respective EU authorities (Arcos & Palacios 2018).

All of this responds to a dynamic of functional expansion framed by the conglomerate of Western institutions specialized in international intervention for stabilization and state-building, which have expanded functionally and bureaucratically based on their own needs to address crises in the relevant peripheries (Woodward 2017). The SC represents a clear example of this trend. Through its geographical analysis—encompassing the Eastern and Southern neighborhood, the Western Balkans, Africa, Asia, and Latin America—there is a racist-tinged neo-imperialist assessment of the peripheries that synthesizes well with the “jungle” evoked by Josep Borrell as antinomian to his “garden” (Eijking 2022):

“Today, the EU is surrounded by instability and conflicts, and faces a war on its borders. We are confronted with a dangerous mix of armed aggression, illegal annexation, fragile states, revisionist powers and authoritarian regimes. This environment is a breeding ground for multiple threats to European security from terrorism, violent extremism and organized crime to hybrid conflicts and cyberattacks, instrumentalization of irregular migration, arms proliferation and the progressive weakening of the arms control architecture. Financial instability, extreme social and economic divergences can further exacerbate such dynamics and have a growing impact on our security. All these threats undermine EU security along our southern and eastern borders and beyond. Where the EU is not active and effective in promoting its interests, others fill the space” (European Council 2022, 18).

The command and the place of the drafter: Toward a conclusion

Considerations on command allow a conclusion to be drawn. *The Art of War* states that “[t]he Commander stands for the virtues of wisdom, sincerely, benevolence, courage and strictness” (Sun Tzu 2000, 2). At times such as the present, Borrell’s attitude, as the commander in charge of the SC’s deployment, responds not only to his own character and ideas, but reflects the perspectives of the federalist and neo-functional bureaucratic factions that may like the idealism from which the notion

of “strategic autonomy” emerges. The drafting of the document—precisely—has been a task of that faction, and this fact has conditioned definitions, as well as values and predictions, with all biases and aspirations that come with the process. Thus, such faction has been able to steer through the institutions and ideological apparatuses of the EU-state complex (including the media, which have become mere replicators of messages issued by bureaucrats, the military, and intelligence services). The federalist perspective is synthesized—in this self-absorbed and provincial Europe—with the perspectives more inclined toward confrontation with Russia, whose message has been well-known in Brussels for the past decade.

From the perspective of “strategic autonomy”, even the confrontational approach to Russia requires a degree of cautiousness and modesty (characteristics that sometimes seem absent in the current commander), since, whatever happens in the short and medium term, the relationship with Russia will have to be re-established in one way or another in the future. To compensate for this contradiction, advocates of “strategic autonomy” present it as part of a historical trend according to which difficulties are driving forces behind creative solutions. Jean Monnet (1978, 417) argued that “Europe will be forged in crises, and will be the sum of the solutions adopted for those crises”, but with a voluntarism that ends up being useful for little more than self-convincement, insofar as it provides ad hoc explanations for the dissonance between political developments in the states, the drift of European society, and the parallel evolution of institutional developments such as the adoption of the SC. Thus, the focus of political willingness, naturally, is often directed at the action of political-bureaucratic structures with a disciplinary vocation while, as far as societies are concerned, their resilience and trust in institutions, even if this is plummeting (Eurostat 2022), are praised.

The SC is a mixture of formal pomposity and unfulfilled desires. To the former, the commander responds, forced by circumstances (and by his own character), to amplify the message. The latter reflects the factor that overdetermines the development of the EU’s actual foreign policy—the transformation of the US empire, which needs to delegate, not cede, its security competences in Europe to focus on the Asia-Pacific region. “The whole art of war is based on deception”, the text attributed to Sun Tzu states. The SC drafter is deceiving itself if it assumes that the fundamentals of Europe’s security will continue to be provided by another power, namely the United States; apart from its own priorities, both domestic and strategic, Washington has repeatedly demonstrated that it has no partners but subjects.

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Earthquakes and tectonic shifts in the regional orders

Tunç Aybak¹

Abstract:

Natural disasters are not only ruptures in the crust of the earth but also have the potential to trigger tectonic geopolitical changes that go beyond the national territories with short- and long-term foreign policy implications. The recent earthquake in Turkey was not the first but one of the worst natural disasters in modern history in terms of its scale and scope. The earthquake hit 10 out of the 81 provinces in Turkey, which contain the home towns of 13.4 million people including the Syrian refugees alongside with the towns and cities on Turkish Syrian border. The earthquake was felt as far as Israel, Palestine, Egypt, Palestine, Lebanon, Cyprus, and the Black Sea coast of Turkey, followed by more than 2,100 aftershocks. The aim of this paper is to assess the geopolitical implications of the recent earthquake in Turkey for the future regional orders in the Middle East, the Caucasus and the Eastern Mediterranean.

Keywords:

Neo-Ottomanism, Earthquake Diplomacy, Foreign Policy, Geopolitics, Refugees

¹ Director of MA International Relations Programme at School of Law, Middlesex University.

Earthquake diplomacy

It was the earthquake in 1999 in Marmara that defused the confrontational diplomatic style between Greece and Turkey. The ongoing ethnic conflict between Turkish and Greek Cypriots in Cyprus in 1975 and the following invasion and conflicting territorial disputes in the Aegean had interrupted the tentative attempts at reconciliation. In 1996 a war was only narrowly escaped. It was the earthquake in Marmara region in August 1999 that created a favourable and empathetic atmosphere in both countries. This was further endorsed in October by Turkish demonstrations of sympathy when Athens, too, was hit by an earthquake. A new “earthquake diplomacy” appeared to be emerging. Some factors played an important role in the earthquake diplomacy between Greece and Turkey. First both parties focused on the low politics issues on which there is no conflict. Secondly, the societal engagement on both sides involved 130 Greek and Turkish NGOs including local government cooperation on both sides of the borders. Third, the media representations have encouraged the public perceptions to move from enmity to more friendly environment. Despite the cooperative atmosphere created as a result Marmara earthquake in 1999, the link between the earthquake diplomacy and foreign policy strategies are still debatable. Ker-Lindsay for instance warns against the simplistic assumptions that diplomatic efforts should be causally linked with the occurrence of disasters. Instead he asserts that disasters may have multiplying and legitimizing effect on diplomatic rapprochement (Ker-Lindsay, 2000).

On the other hand, some scholars who contributed to the disaster diplomacy literature in examining the conditions under which disasters can lead to long-term disaster-related collaboration at both governmental and non-governmental level among states in conflict. Ganabati et al. argue, focusing on the role of the 1999 earthquake, acknowledge the diversity and complexity of disaster diplomacy situations that may lead to long-term disaster-related cooperation among states in conflict when: (1) one party providing disaster relief to another party is followed by a similar reciprocal gesture (i.e. tit-for-tat diplomacy); (2) there is a realization and acceptance that neighbours should come to each other’s assistance in times of disaster; and (3) there is an enabling broader context (e.g. a rapprochement process) conducive to sustaining the long-term cooperation (Ganabati et al. 2010).

The jury is still out whether earthquakes and disasters may lead to rapprochement and more conciliatory diplomatic demarches. In this paper, I will concentrate on the foreign policy implications of the earthquake that hit South East Turkey in February and the following earthquake diplomacy and cooperative efforts between Turkey and . This is not a random selection. These countries are selected on the basis that Turkey has had problematic relations. These neighbouring countries are also directly affected by Turkey’s grand designs and ambitions of its foreign policy strategy.

The rise and fall Neo-Ottomanism:

It is worth putting these developments in the context of Turkish grand foreign policy strategy of Neo-Ottomanism that is the driving force in Turkey's regional hegemonic policy strategy. It was mainly the Prime Minister Davutoglu, formerly in charge of Turkish foreign policy, has been the main strategist behind this Neo-Ottomanist drive. His concept of 'strategic depth' can be located within this new transitional pan-Islamist geopolitical vision (Davutoglu, 2014). Strategic depth is the geopolitical discourse concerning Turkey's position that provides a new direction to increase the power of Turkey in those regions with which claims that Turkey has privileged national interests and close religious and cultural ties that stem from the legacies of the Ottoman Empire as the protectorate of the Sunni Muslims against the Christian west and non-Sunni nations. Davutoglu's key argument is that the civilizational conflict between the Christian West and Islamic Turkey is irreconcilable in the long run. Instead Turkey needs to increase its influence by utilizing its geostrategic location and its Ottoman legacy in its immediate neighbourhoods. This can clearly be still discerned in Turkey's foreign policy actions towards Syria, Armenia and Greece. Since the Syrian crisis unravelled in 2013, Turkey has openly adopted a sectarian policy supporting the Sunni opposition forces against the Assad regime. Despite the declining personal influence of Davutoglu since his resignation, this increasingly confrontational strategy still informs Turkey's foreign policy conduct in relation to Armenia Syria and Greece as manifested in Erdogan's siege mentality discourse that Turkey is surrounded by arch enemies.

In the past, Turkey was favourably treated in the Middle East, the Balkans, and Europe. Surprisingly, the situation had altered so drastically in the early 2010s following the Arab Spring that Kalin, an adviser to the then-prime minister Erdogan and currently the Director of National Intelligence (MIT) described Turkey's situation as one of "precious loneliness," contending that Turkey was marginalised in the international community and surrounded by potential competitors who do not want Turkey to succeed in the region and beyond because it was standing up for its religious values and Ottomanist foreign policy ideals. It is obvious that Turkey's position in the world has changed since then testing the geopolitical ambitions under Erdogan's regime (Atmaca, et al. 2022) Even before the earthquake, it was obvious that Turkey's Neo-Ottomanist drive in the region faced structural obstacles isolating Turkey even further in its immediate region. The confrontation with Greece on the Cyprus Issue and energy exploration in the Eastern Mediterranean region in its militaristic posture towards Armenia on the side of Azerbaijan undermined Turkey's hegemonic intent as an influencer the Balkans, the Middle East and the Southern Caucasus. As Ozel and Balta pertinently argued '... while the fears and ambitions of the political elites paved the way for certain foreign policy choices, at each critical juncture these policy choices Turkey's Foreign Policy were either constrained or enabled by more systemic factors. The result was a foreign policy posture that is perceived to be incoherent and irrational, since it combined both Turkey's grandiose fantasies about being a major power with its

long-held fears and insecurities' (Balta and Ozel, 2021, 557) In this context, it can be argued that to a certain extent, the earthquake in February 2023 played a role of catalyst in the gradual transformation Turkey's foreign policy strategy and its diplomatic style from more belligerent to more accommodating diplomatic style. It must be noted however that any conclusive analysis could be too premature at this point even though some early indicators may shed light on its changing bilateral relations with Armenia, Greece and Syria. Let us look at these bilateral cases in turn in the light of post-earthquake developments in Turkey's immediate neighbourhood.

Syria: from confrontation to rapprochement?

Turkey's bilateral relations with Syria during the Cold War as a NATO member was determined by the Cold War divisions between the Soviet Union and the west. Some territorial issues remained, particularly in Hatay's status- a historically disputed region. The presence of the Kurdish separatists (PKK) in Syria remained another source constant friction. With the end of the Cold War, however, Turkey's immediate neighbourhood was opened for economic penetration. Turkey's economic drive to the Middle East began in the 1990s under various coalition governments. The strong growth of the Middle Eastern economies since the start of the oil boom in 2003 and the rise of the Anatolian business interests penetrating the Middle East in general and trade with Syria along the border. Turkey's so-called success story was more or less facilitated by external circumstances, it is by no means to suggest that the hegemonic model the AKP did not play a key role. As policy brief published in 2008 by SETA foundation for Political, Economic and Social Research-pro-government think tank- summarised 'The rise to power of Turkish Prime Minister Tayyip Erdoğan marks a new era in positive Turkish-Syrian relations. The new Syrian attitude towards Turkey represents a break from past: Syria considers Turkey a reliable partner for brokering a peace deal between Syria and Israel, and Turkey offers opportunities for political and economic cooperation for improving the welfare and security of two countries.' (Moubayet, 2008, 3)

After a decade of cooperation with Syria, Turkey's policy has changed radically as a result of the 2011–12 civil uprisings providing a geopolitical opportunity for Erdoğan's Neo-Ottomanist strategy towards Syria. Erdoğan openly started to call for the overthrow of President Bashar al-Assad's regime and actively sponsored the Sunni opposition and radical insurgency groups. Since March 2011 Turkey has escalated its hostile policy towards Assad regime by cutting diplomatic ties; and, supporting and aiding Syria's political and armed opposition. Turkey's direct military intervention against the Assad regime involved imposition of a no-fly zone or humanitarian corridors for Syrian refugees and military incursions into the Syrian territory to punish Kurds and undermine the self-declared autonomous Rojava canton within Syrian territories. (Cagatay, 2020) However, The recent regional developments exposed the limitations of Erdoğan's agency and his aim to overthrow the regime as Turkey's Neo-Ottomanist strategy that has been confronted by the

systemic and structural constraints at the regional and global level, clashing with Russia's overall strategic objectives in the Middle East as well as the strategic differences between the US and Turkey in relation to the Kurds in Syria (Ozel and Ozkan, 2015). One of the unintended consequences of Turkey's foreign policy in relation to Syria has been the exponential influx of Syrian refugees into Turkey. Currently the number of Syrian refugees settled in Turkey reached roughly 3.6 million which is the biggest issue for the government blurring the boundaries between domestic and foreign policy. Turkey's Syrian foreign policy has been increasingly unsustainable. Since late 2021 to early 2022, Ankara has been promoting two seemingly irreconcilable goals. On the one hand, it has threatened to launch an invasion of northern Syria with military force. Nevertheless, despite continuing drone attacks against prominent Kurdish officials by Turkey with the objective of consolidating victories made in the northeast, Ankara did not launch a land offensive due to a lack of support from Russia, Iran, and the United States. The Erdogan administration has also been working to patch fences with Bashar al-Assad at the same time. The efforts of Ankara to normalise relations with Assad complement those being made in the region to forge alliances. The readmission of Assad to the Arab League, as well as rapprochement between Saudi Arabia and Iran, Arab states and Israel, and Arab Gulf monarchies are all positive regional developments.

However, despite Turkish drone operations against the Kurdish strongholds in Syria. A crucial conference between the defence ministers of Russia, Turkey, and Syria, along with their respective security chiefs, took place in Moscow in December 2022, sparking the process of rapprochement just before the February 2023 Earthquake. (The Guardian, 2022) Normalization between Turkey and Syria was also evident before the recent elections after the earthquake. Moscow hosted a meeting between the defence ministers of Russia, Iran, Syria and Turkey on April 25, as well as the first official meeting of foreign ministers on May 10. There, according to former Turkish foreign minister Mevlüt Çavuşoğlu, the ministers discussed the importance of collaborating to combat terrorism, facilitate the safe return of refugees, and safeguard Syria's territorial integrity.

The earthquake severely damaged the already precarious Syrian refugees in South East Turkey, exposing Erdogan's shortcomings in his approach to refugees. Despite this, the tragedy did not lead to any change in Turkey's stance toward Syria, whose northern regions, including Turkish-controlled Afrin, also experienced widespread death and destruction as a result of the earthquakes. In order to facilitate the flow of UN-coordinated humanitarian aid, Ankara agreed to reopen two border crossings for three months in addition to the one on the border with Idlib. However, it has refused to permit Syrians to enter Turkey. While the Syrian government-controlled border crossings and those leading to Kurdish-held regions are still closed, all three border crossings are open to areas controlled by the rebels. Turkey-backed forces blocked aid convoys from the Kurdish-run northeast for days. (Arab Centre, 2023)

This attitude implies that the feeling of shared suffering has not led to any moderation on the part of Turkey toward Syria and that rigid conditions still apply

to Russian-mediated efforts to mend ties between Ankara and Damascus. Many Syrian refugees still live in misery and uncertainty in the provinces of Turkey that were devastated by the earthquake. Syrians are facing growing public pressure to return home as Ankara struggles to meet the needs of the affected population. The Turkish government and local authorities are increasingly using xenophobic and derogatory tactics against Syrian refugees living there. 2020.3 Financial Times Hatred and anti-refugee sentiments are already at an all-time high, and many Turks now see the disaster as a chance to send the refugees home. (Hurseda Haber, 2023)

Since late 2021 Erdogan on several occasions has threatened to launch an invasion of northern Syria with military force. The development of an autonomous Kurdish political entity under the administration of the PYD/YPG continues to be the main source of tension between Syria and Turkey, according to President Erdogan (Foreign Policy, 2023) However, Ankara's top objective right now is to repatriate Syrian refugees and reach an agreement with the Syrian regime. President Erdogan also made clear that Turkish construction companies could benefit from the resettlement of the Syrian refugees in Syria. Before the earthquake, Erdogan and Assad had reached an understanding regarding the removal of the US-supported Kurdish presence from northern Syria. As a response, Assad made normalising ties with Ankara contingent on Turkey withdrawing its troops from northwest Syria, allowing the Syrian government to retake the area. Erdogan, however, would be more eager than ever to negotiate an arrangement with Assad to ensure the return of 3.6 million Syrian refugees to Syria given the public anger directed at the presence of Syrian refugees in Turkey during the election campaign after the earthquake. Despite the earthquake, the obstacles to reconciliation between Turkey and Syria persist particularly in the areas of border issues and Turkey's interventionist posture in the Syrian territories. In fact, as it was rightly observed by an analyst, Syria's reconciliation with the Arab League may end the Syrian isolation and diminish the possibility of diplomatic rapprochement between Turkey and Syria. (Arab Centre, March 29 2023).

Greece: Rekindling Earthquake Diplomacy

The earthquake also offered an opportunity to rekindle the earthquake diplomacy between Turkey and Greece. Greece was one of the first countries that sent aid to Turkey, despite the fact that before the earthquake Turkey and Greece were on the brink of a military confrontation over territorial disputes in the Aegean Sea and the exploration of the gas deposits over the disputed territorial water. (Greek Reporter) Erdoğan on several occasions adopted a threatening posture against Greece that Turkey might “come all of a sudden during the night” and that Turkish missiles could strike Athens if Greece did not “keep quiet.” (Financial Times, September 2022) This was followed by Greece's post-earthquake goodwill gesture, Erdoğan took a call from Greek Prime Minister Kyriakos Mitsotakis, thus backing down from a prior statement that he would never speak to him again. And Turkish Foreign Minister Mevlut Cavusoglu hosted his Greek counterpart Nikos Dendias,

who visited earthquake-affected areas in Hatay near the Syrian border and stressed the need to improve relations. (AL Jazeera, February 2023) The Greek citizens and NGOs were also actively involved in the delivery of aid and rescue operations. (Aljazeera, February 2023) During Dendias' visit, the Turkish Foreign Minister said that in 1999, as an ordinary citizen, he had written a letter to TIMES magazine he had argued that Greece and Turkey should not wait until the next earthquake to improve their relations. (Reuters, 2023)

Despite the diplomatic demarches, the key issues between Greece and Turkey remain unresolved as geopolitical claims still stand in the way of real and deep cooperation. For instance, Turkey still pursues a long-term objective of exercising its influence and exploration of gas in the Eastern Mediterranean as this was manifested by its Blue Homeland (Mavi Vatan) strategy. (Candar, 2020) While Greece forged an alliance with Cyprus, Egypt and Israel in 2019 with an Eastern Mediterranean Gas forum, which envisages the exploitation and marketing of the gas deposits. Turkey refuses to recognize the maritime borders of Greece and Cyprus and was left out of this alliance. The issues in the delineation of maritime borders and armament of the Aegean Islands still have the potential to restart frictions. This risk is even further enhanced as the Lausanne Treaty, signed at the end of the Turkish-Greek war in 1923, which laid the foundations and settled the borders between two countries nearly 100 years ago, is coming under Erdogan's scrutiny as a result of the change of public perceptions in Turkey. (The Conversation, February 2023).

Armenia: from confrontation to normalization

Turkey and Armenia have had a difficult relationship over the past few decades. Turkey was one of the first countries to recognize Armenian independence after the end of the Soviet Union in 1991, but relations between the states quickly deteriorated after Armenia's invasion of Nagorno Karabakh, a disputed region in Azerbaijan in the early 1990s. By 1993, diplomatic relations between Turkey and Armenia had ended and Turkey's border with Armenia was closed. Since then Turkey has actively supported oil-rich Azerbaijan as a decades-old territorial dispute flared anew into an armed conflict over Nagorno-Karabakh, a mountainous region situated within Azerbaijan controlled by Armenia-backed ethnic separatists. Despite an attempt at reconciliation in 2009, Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan had to step back from diplomatic rapprochement with Armenia due to the Azeri objections. As a result, Erdogan made the establishment of formal ties with Armenia conditional on its withdrawal from Nagorno-Karabakh. (Aydintasbas et al, 2023) In the military clashes between Armenia and Azerbaijan over Nagorno Karabakh in 2020, Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan openly declared his government's support for Azerbaijan extending its military aid and supplying drones to the Azerbaijani military. (New Yorker, 2022)

However, despite these long-standing differences, disaster diplomacy can build on actions taken in the months since the earthquake in Turkey and Armenia. For instance, the foreign ministers of Turkey and Armenia met to talk about the likelihood of diplomatic normalization. As part of talks to normalize relations, both parties have designated special envoys to mediate; Turkish and Armenian airlines have resumed operating direct flights between the two nations; and Armenia lifted its import ban on Turkey last year. Additionally, there is a chance for Ankara and Yerevan to normalize relations because of the ongoing peace negotiations between Armenia and Azerbaijan. Turkey and Armenia may be able to maintain the open border for trade and commerce in the near future by building on the momentum created by the earthquake.

In fact, the Armenian government was one of the first countries to send food, medicine, drinking water and other emergency supplies to devastated cities and towns soon after the quakes. Armenian research and rescue crews also actively engaged in search and rescue operation on the ground. Armenian crews taking part in rescue operations in the region Gaziantep and Kahramanmaras, where large Armenian communities lived in the past, was highly symbolic. More importantly, the aid from Armenia crossed into Turkey through the land border which has been closed by the Turkish authorities since the early 1990s was the most significant gesture. Armenian Prime Minister Pashinyan called Turkish President Recep Tayyip Erdogan to express his condolences, while Armenian Foreign Minister Mirzoyan visited Turkey on February 15 to meet with his counterpart, both parties expressed their willingness to strengthen diplomatic relations. While Mirzoyan requested the full opening of the border between Turkey and Armenia, Cavusoglu's emphasis was that progress in the normalization of relations between Armenia and Turkey, should contribute to peace and prosperity in the region, he proposed that finding a peaceful solution to the issues between Yerevan and Baku was a central condition before opening the Turkish border with Armenia. (Daily Sabah, 12 March 2023] Despite the earthquake diplomacy, Turkey exercises caution not to alienate its traditional ally Azerbaijan.

Conclusion

The question remains: Can disasters induce cooperation amongst hostile countries? Earthquakes undoubtedly have geopolitical implications for societies and states. Disasters can have positive transformative potential as people are brought together in common humanity. This also applies to inter-state relations and nations. Earthquakes and disasters may transform the changing relations between citizens and their states in the wake of tectonic shifts. On the other hand, disaster diplomacy on its own does not resolve interstate conflict but opens up for the channels of communication and societal interaction that may influence public perceptions. As the evidence demonstrates that disaster-related activities can act as catalysis diplomatic activities if actors choose, disaster diplomacy can be put into practice.

As the events unfolded, the earthquake definitely undermined Erdogan's polarizing foreign discourse that Turkey is surrounded by enemies driven by 'we versus them' mindset. The earthquake is not just a sudden rupture a tectonic shift in the crust of the earth but also shake individual and national identities and certainties offering uncertainty but also diplomatic opportunity. The Lisbon earthquake of 1755 caused Voltaire, Rousseau and others to herald the death of God and the beginning of humanism and enlightenment. Just after the earthquake Erdogan declared that the earthquake was 'god's will'. The following election victory reaffirmed Erdogan's religious take on the earthquakes supported by populist national and religious majority.

The earthquakes also trigger diplomatic processes and open up new channels of communication. In the case of Syria, the earthquake did not really lead to diplomatic thaw but created further frictions over border issues and collaboration. In the case of Armenia, the new communication channels have been opened and triggered some good diplomacy starting the conversation between parties which has been absent for a long time. With Greece the relations have been rekindled and the hostile language has been abandoned.

In general disaster have the potential to play the role of a catalyst. However, they cannot alter the grand strategies and long-term objectives in the exercise of foreign policy.

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**Societal Implications of the “World Shattering”:
Collective trauma and the social psychological theory of group
behavior during systemic changes**

Boris Kordić¹

Abstract:

Recent observations increasingly suggest that the global geopolitical system is undergoing a fundamental transformation. Accepting this process as inevitable necessitates an inquiry into how states and societies respond to such systemic shifts. During these transitions, established psychological boundaries—between the safe and unsafe, the familiar and unfamiliar, and the internal and external—are fundamentally disrupted. This paper posits that such shifts constitute a potentially traumatic environment. The central hypothesis is that the processes "shattering" the contemporary world order carry profound societal implications in the form of collective trauma; this trauma, in turn, governs societal and state behavior until a new systemic equilibrium is reached. By utilizing trauma theory, this research bridges the gap between external geopolitical realities and internal psychological responses. Trauma is defined here by the concept of "surplus"—an experience of "too much" that overwhelms existing coping mechanisms. Under the pressure of trauma, rational thought and conventional behavior often give way to automatic defense mechanisms. This paper presents a theoretical model of collective trauma designed to provide a comprehensive framework for assessing and understanding the behavior of states and societies during periods of acute geopolitical instability.

Key Words:

collective trauma, group behavior, geopolitical system change, social groups, society-state relations

¹ Full Professor, Faculty of Security Studies, University of Belgrade kordic@fb.bg.ac.rs

Introduction

The stability of the global geopolitical structure has become increasingly precarious in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. On European soil, this instability was exacerbated by the outbreak of large-scale military operations in Ukraine. Already weakened by the preceding migrant crisis and the systemic shocks of the pandemic, Europe faced further degradation through energy supply crises following the imposition of sanctions against Russia. These overlapping crises elicited diverse reactions from both populations and governing structures. Given the global nature of the pandemic, it provides a unique opportunity to investigate the behavioral regularities of governing bodies under acute stress. This paper examines these phenomena through the lens of psychoanalytic trauma theory, social psychology, and the unconscious functioning of groups to draw conclusions applicable to future systemic crises.

The COVID-19 pandemic shattered a century of perceived immunity to large-scale biological threats in Europe. While previous outbreaks—such as avian or swine flu—remained geographically or conceptually distant, the World Health Organization's declaration of a global pandemic on March 11, 2020, forced a confrontation with the fragility of human life and the inevitability of mortality. Pandemics inevitably revive historical "memories" of medieval plagues, disrupting the perceived permanence of modern daily life. Consequently, COVID-19 acted as an "epidemic of fear," where psychological contagion outpaced the biological virus. The transition from peripheral observation of events in Wuhan to the radical suspension of movement—manifesting in grounded flights, border closures, and domestic lockdowns—represented a profound psychological shock.

As nations implemented isolation measures—including social distancing, the suspension of public life, and the transition to digital labor—the world entered a state of "lockdown." This fragmented the global community into strictly separated units, casting a shadow over the presumed solidarity of entities like the European Union. Confronted by an "invisible enemy" and a lack of clear institutional communication, the public experienced a dissolution of established psychological boundaries. The distinctions between safe and unsafe, known and unknown, and internal and external became blurred. Such environments are inherently traumatic; under the influence of trauma, rational deliberation often ceases, replaced by automatic defense mechanisms and actions that provide only illusory relief.

The pandemic functioned as a universal traumatic event, affecting citizens and state apparatuses alike. The virus—and the attendant fear—did not discriminate between those under care and those in positions of responsibility. In the search for authoritative guidance, the "expert" or "professional" voice was frequently invoked; however, scientific and governing institutions proved susceptible to panic, group pressure, and the demand for immediate certainty. These pressures often compromised critical thinking, leading to hasty decision-making and the presentation of contradictory data that heightened public confusion. As institutional gaps in knowledge became apparent, they were filled by conspiracy theories—

psychological anchors that provided a semblance of security against archaic fears previously suppressed by the routines of modern life.

Analyzing the trauma precipitated by the COVID-19 pandemic requires a multi-disciplinary approach. This paper will first delineate the conceptual specificities of trauma within psychoanalytic theory. It will then examine the unique characteristics of trauma within a pandemic context. Finally, it will analyze the impact of this trauma on large social groups, specifically focusing on the relationship between citizens and the state during periods of geopolitical uncertainty.

The Psychoanalytic Theory of Trauma

The Evolution of Trauma Theory

The concept of psychic trauma was initially introduced to explain the etiology of symptoms in hysterical patients (Breuer and Freud 1893). A central tenet of this theory is the temporal dimension of *Après-Coup* (afterwards), which suggests that a significant past event acquires traumatic meaning only through a later

interpretation that reinvests the experience with psychic energy. Historically, the recognition of trauma evolved through the "war neuroses" of World War I to the profound destructiveness of World War II. The latter confronted humanity with the systematic genocide of the Holocaust and the existential threat of the atomic bomb. Research into Holocaust survivors revealed that trauma is not confined to the individual; it manifests through transgenerational transmission, where consequences are felt by subsequent generations. Furthermore, it became clear that the traumatism of certain events must be recognized at the societal level to facilitate individual therapeutic recovery (Kordić 2018). It was not until the aftermath of the Vietnam War that these observations were codified into the official medical classification as Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD).

The Economic View: Trauma as "Too Much"

The essence of trauma theory is best encapsulated by the concept of "surplus" or "too much" (Perelberg 2015). Originally, trauma was conceptualized as excessive excitation that the psyche could neither discharge through motor action nor associatively integrate into memory (Breuer and Freud 1893). Freud later described this as a breach of the "barrier against stimuli," leading to a catastrophic flooding of the psyche (Freud 1920). The primary consequence is the immobilization of the Ego, which is rendered helpless by its inability to manage the overwhelming stimulus (Freud 1926).

This quantitative "too much" fundamentally alters the quality of psychic life. The traumatized individual experiences what has been described as a "hole in the psyche" (Freud 1892), a sense of emptiness, or a "black hole" within the psychic structure (Bohleber 2002)—a horror that Baranger, Baranger, and Mom (1988) identified as "impossible to name." In these instances, the trauma remains stalled at a physical and

sensory level, bypassing the psychic realm of representation and symbolization. Because the experience cannot be symbolized, it cannot be verbalized. These unintegrated fragments of trauma persist independently, occasionally flooding the consciousness and forcing a vivid repetition of the traumatic experience

Collective Trauma and the State-as-Parent

As social beings, the primary factor in overcoming crisis is the quality of communal support. Humans possess a fundamental need for empathy and understanding; thus, the traumatic impact of an event is often measured by the quality of relationships with "significant others" (Balint 1969). While empathic understanding mitigates trauma, its absence intensifies it. During development, individuals acquire basic security through parental figures who assist in perceiving, processing, and symbolizing life events. This process establishes a "signal anxiety" mechanism, allowing the individual to distinguish between genuine danger and harmless stimuli, thereby reducing individual vulnerability.

When trauma assumes a collective dimension, the societal response becomes paramount. In such contexts, the state functions toward its citizens much like a parent toward a child. Recent Serbian history—marked by civil war, the exodus from the Serbian Krajina, and the NATO bombing—illustrates the consequences of a failure in this "parental" role. Many victims were met with a lack of empathy upon their return, hindering the integration of their experiences into peacetime life. The absence of systematic mental hygiene measures reflected a failure of state concern, the repercussions of which remain visible today, as evidenced by the distress of war veterans during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Solidarity and the Pandemic Challenge

Collective trauma often drives individuals toward mutual solidarity as a defense against pervasive uncertainty. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the emergence of volunteers assisting the elderly represented an active confrontation with adversity, restoring a sense of agency and control. However, the pandemic posed a unique challenge: the necessity of social isolation inhibited traditional active coping mechanisms. In this context, the digital landscape emerged as a "transitional space," allowing schools and organizations to maintain a semblance of communal functioning through online engagement, thereby mitigating the complete collapse of social connectivity.

Specificity of Trauma during the COVID-19 Pandemic

The Interface of External and Internal Reality

Psychic trauma bridges the gap between external reality and internal experience. The COVID-19 pandemic introduced a unique constellation of external stressors: the unpredictability of infection, systemic shortages of medical and personal protective equipment, prolonged quarantine, and the radical restriction of social contact. For many, this was compounded by the simultaneous demands of remote work and

childcare, the exhaustion of leadership structures ("management burnout"), and the economic instability accompanying global lockdowns.

Internally, such situations trigger a spectrum of responses ranging from adaptive to maladaptive. Traumatic impact occurs specifically when mature defense mechanisms fail and the usual functioning of the personality is paralyzed. While psychological defenses like denial may temporarily shield the conscious Ego from recognized danger, such "parallel realities" often harbor hidden psychological conflicts that can manifest later with unpredictable intensity.

The "Modality of Being" and the Intrusive Real

Trauma represents an intrusion of reality that disrupts the psychic order, disabling the individual's ability to feel "alive" and connected—what Erlich (2020) defines as the *experiential modality of being*. It is essential to distinguish between the modalities of being (characterized by togetherness, fusion, and unity) and *doing* (characterized by separation, autonomy, and agency). While these usually function in tandem, trauma can force the modality of being into a negative state of "non-being," akin to an experience of psychic death (Erlich 2003).

In this state, the capacity for symbolization is impaired, and the "Real" becomes tyrannical. The obsessive monitoring of infection rates, mortality statistics, and recovery numbers represents an encroachment of the raw "Real" into a psychic space that has been hollowed out by trauma. Paralyzed and unable to assign symbolic meaning to the crisis, the psyche becomes a repository for cold, uninterpreted data.

The Invisible Enemy and the Paranoid Shift

The primary emotional response to the pandemic is the fear of infection. Because the viral source is invisible, fear is displaced from the virus onto the human vectors who transmit it. During the incubation period, any individual becomes a potential, yet undetectable, threat. This invisibility fosters a "paranoid shift" in social relations. Initially, this was manifested as xenophobia toward those associated with the first outbreaks; eventually, anyone returning from abroad or crossing a border became a subject of suspicion. The ritualization of temperature checks, mandatory quarantines, and border closures transformed the "Other" into a potential bearer of an invisible enemy, and thus, a societal foe.

The Dialectic of Contagion and Rejection

The inverse of the fear of contagion is the fear of social rejection. To be identified as a potential source of infection is to face social excommunication. Quarantine, in this context, takes on the symbolic meaning of imprisonment—a loss of freedom and personal dignity within an environment perceived as saturated with contagion. This creates a secondary trauma: a fear of seeking medical assistance. People may avoid reporting symptoms out of a dread that their illness will be "interpreted" as the virus, leading to their removal from the family nucleus and social environment.

The Unknown and the Rise of Conspiracy

The fear of infection is further intensified by the fear of the unknown. The novel nature of the virus, its uncertain symptomatology, and the mortality of "non-endangered" groups introduced a profound element of unpredictability. This void of knowledge is a fertile ground for paranoid explanations. Conspiracy theories regarding the origin and manipulation of the virus provide a perverted sense of security; they offer a "reason" where science offers only uncertainty. In a desperate search for agency, individuals may cling to unproven "miracle cures" or minimize the danger by comparing it to historical epidemics, all in an attempt to regain a sense of control over an uncontrollable reality. Social Distancing and Psychic Splitting

Finally, social distancing—while a rational protective measure—reconfigured the world into a binary of "safe interiors" (the home) and "dangerous exteriors" (the public sphere). This physical division is mirrored by the defense mechanism of *splitting*. On a societal level, this fuels anti-social tendencies and suspicion toward others (e.g., those coughing or those without masks). On an internal level, the accumulation of stress within the "closed unit" of the home often leads to violent outbursts, substance abuse, or obsessive-compulsive behaviors, such as excessive disinfection and hoarding. These actions serve as symbolic, albeit maladaptive, attempts to purge the "invisible enemy" from one's immediate environment.

Effects of the Pandemic on large social groups

The Developmental Course of Contagion

To understand collective reactions to systemic shocks, Zachary Green and David McCallum (2020) proposed a developmental map detailing the psychological course of contagion. Their framework posits that collective responses oscillate between unconscious defense mechanisms—characterized by regressive behavior—and conscious, proactive strategies rooted in rational concern for the community. These patterns manifest in three distinct temporal stages: *Pre-Contagion*, *Contagion*, and *Post-Contagion*.

Stage I: Pre-Contagion – The Mechanisms of Avoidance

In the stage preceding a local outbreak, the threat is perceived as geographically or psychologically distant. To maintain this sense of security, societies employ a triad of defense mechanisms: **ignorance**, **indifference**, and **denial** (Green and McCallum 2020).

Ignorance manifests as a deliberate avoidance of information, where the community actively suppresses discourse regarding the threat.

Indifference acknowledges the existence of the virus but strips it of emotional investment, treating the crisis as "someone else's problem."

Denial, a more primitive defense, recognizes the danger but forcefully excludes it from consciousness to prevent the onset of anxiety. These maneuvers serve as a collective psychological shield, reassuring the population that their immediate environment remains inviolable.

Stage II: Contagion – From Panic to Containment

The transition to the Contagion stage occurs when the first local infections are confirmed. As the shield of denial shatters, fear spreads more rapidly than the biological agent. In this atmosphere of confusion, the hunger for reliable data often descends into a "sea of misinformation." Green and McCallum (2020) identify four primary social defense mechanisms during this phase:

Contamination (Scapegoating): This mechanism seeks to master the traumatic situation by identifying a "culprit." By directing anger and condemnation toward a specific group, the society draws a rigid boundary between "us" (the healthy/innocent) and "them" (the infected/guilty).

Panic: When scapegoating fails to halt the spread, "mass hysteria" ensues. Rationality is superseded by hostility and irrational survivalism. At the governance level, this stage is often marked by counterproductive or destructive decision-making. Individuals with lower psychological resilience may experience profound despair, numbness, or self-destructive impulses.

Chaos: Paradoxically, "chaos" serves as a social defense mechanism aimed

at establishing a new order amidst the disruption of traditional rhythms. It involves the prioritization of activities and the first attempts at coordinated collective action. However, state interventions during this stage create a profound tension: measures are simultaneously perceived as essential public health mandates and as the potential precursors to a "totalitarian regime" (Green and McCallum 2020).

Containment: This represents the beginning of a sustainable exit from the crisis. Containment allows for a reflective period where ideas regarding the "new normal" begin to mature, translating into new norms of social behavior and coordinated institutional responses.

Stage III: Post-Contagion – Healing and Regressive Isolation

As the infection rate subsides, the focus shifts toward reconciliation and restoration. The social mechanisms in this final stage include:

Isolation: Despite being a late-stage reaction, isolation can be a regressive social defense. While it seeks to isolate the virus, it often perpetuates the "contagion of fear." This state is a double-edged sword: it can foster deep communal reflection and the establishment of new values, or it can lead to negative outcomes such as social inertia and addictive behaviors.

Emergence: Triggered by the official declaration that the danger has passed, this phase is characterized by a dialectic of mourning for the victims and relief

at the restoration of freedom. While the majority of the population reintegrates socially, those with weakened resilience may remain "victims of the contagion of fear," as the pandemic acts as a catalyst for long-term psychological disorders.

Return/Restoration: This final phase is less a defense mechanism and more an adaptation to a new reality. Societies return to a regular rhythm of life, yet this rhythm is fundamentally altered, carrying the "scar tissue" and structural changes necessitated by the preceding crisis.

Mature and Regressive group functioning

The Dialectic of Group Sophistication

The developmental map of contagion highlights that collective reactions to a pandemic are primarily driven by automatic, unconscious processes. This necessitates an analysis of group functioning, specifically the distinction between mature/sophisticated and regressive/primitive levels (Kris 1943; Bion 1961). Mature functioning is the hallmark of the "Work Group," which operates on a conscious level, utilizing rational thought and task-oriented behavior to achieve goals in reality. Conversely, regressive functioning characterizes "Basic Assumption Groups," which operate unconsciously to manage the group's emotional life and anxieties. Ideally, these two planes coexist, with the emotional energy of the basic assumptions supporting rather than obstructing the Work Group's objectives.

Bion's Basic Assumptions in the Pandemic Context

The primary function of a basic assumption group is to manage acute anxiety through unconscious defenses, thereby preserving a fragile relationship with reality (Szykierski 2010). Bion (1961) identified three core categories: Dependency, Fight/Flight, and Pairing. These represent the social manifestation of drives related to attachment, aggression, and reproduction (Erlich 2001). During the pandemic, all three were vividly observable:

Dependency: This was manifested in the collective need for a leader or "parental" figure to provide protection and certainty. This dependency was directed toward the World Health Organization, state authorities, and medical experts. Alternatively, those who rejected official narratives often transferred this dependency to "alternative" authorities who offered salvation through unorthodox treatments or hygiene protocols.

Fight/Flight: This assumption rationalizes anger and hatred by identifying an external enemy. In the pandemic, this was seen in the aggressive "othering" of returnees, pet owners, or citizens perceived as "irresponsible" for being in public spaces. The enemy was no longer just the virus, but the personified "threat" of the non-compliant neighbor.

Pairing: This is characterized by the hope for a future "savior" or an ideal that will resolve the crisis (Kordić 2019). The collective investment in the creation of a

"miracle" vaccine served as the primary pairing mechanism, offering a utopian vision of a world free from infection.

Incohesion: The Fourth Basic Assumption and Annihilation Anxiety

Earl Hopper (2003) extended Bion's model by introducing a fourth basic assumption: **Incohesion: Aggregation/Massification**. Hopper argues that when the basic assumption of dependency fails catastrophically, the social unconscious of a group is traumatized to the point of "annihilation anxiety." In this state, the social system's cohesion shatters, leaving only primitive survival mechanisms. An organization infected by annihilation anxiety regroups around two poles of Incohesion:

Aggregation: A state of aversive "breaking into pieces," characterized by paranoid fantasies and the disintegration of internal bonds of trust. This was visible in the strict closing of borders and the fragmentation of international cooperation.

Massification: An indiscriminate "clinging together" where differentiation is halted. In massified systems, there is an implicit demand for total consensus; members must collude in a shared fiction and "look away" from institutional transgressions (Scanlon and Adlam 2008). To "think one's own thoughts" in such an environment is to risk severe social sanctions (Gabbard and Wilkinson 1994).

The Pandemic as a Cause Célèbre

Massified social systems often unconsciously select a cause célèbre—a "politically correct" symbol that represents their shared assumptions about the source of their oppression (Garland 1982). This symbol allows the group to avoid an authentic awareness of their own helplessness and the violence erupting from the crisis. The COVID-19 pandemic, as announced by the WHO, may be viewed as such a cause célèbre. It catalyzed both massification (the global, undifferentiated demand for compliance) and aggregation (the retreat into isolated, defensive national units). By focusing on the virus as the singular cause of all social ruptures, these systems successfully defended against a deeper recognition of their systemic fragility and the underlying trauma of a changing world order.

Leaders in time of crisis

The Vulnerability of Leadership and the Crisis of Trust

Political leaders are not immune to the psychological pressures of a global crisis; they are susceptible to the same panic, group pressures, and urgent demands as the populations they govern. State leaders often engaged in imitative behavior, mirroring the rapid implementation of pandemic measures across borders. This atmosphere compromises "the feeling of trust"—a crucial social-psychological factor for managing collective crises (Wirth 2021). Effective crisis management depends on leaders cognitively managing information, making well-considered decisions, and communicating truthfully with the populace. In Serbia, for example,

initial official reactions were characterized by denial—dismissing the threat and encouraging normal social activities. As the contagion spread, this denial violently shifted to apocalyptic warnings about insufficient burial space, a dynamic that profoundly eroded public trust.

The Chasm Between Science and Politics

At the outset of the pandemic, the scientific community struggled to connect its nuanced findings with the often binary, urgent messaging emanating from political crisis headquarters. This gap between scientific complexity and political simplicity created significant public confusion. When the chasm widens, experts frequently warn against the very panic that political messaging inadvertently generates. A notable example involved a German expert's critique of initial treatment protocols

—following published medical advice from leading journals led to suboptimal outcomes, illustrating the dangers of dogmatic adherence to emerging data under pressure.

A Proposal for Proactive Leadership

To navigate future crises effectively, this paper proposes that leaders should cultivate three core capacities:

A need for proactive and progressive behavior: Leaders must be acutely aware of their own potential for regressive behavior. To foster innovation over conformity, leadership teams require mechanisms like a "devil's advocate" or a jester—an internal counter-voice to challenge consensus and ensure critical thinking prevails. This fosters the necessary self-awareness for moving beyond automatic, defensive reactions.

The connection with citizens: Leaders must engage with citizens respectfully and responsively, clearly explaining policy decisions through a transparent informational dialogue. Hans-Jürgen Wirth (2021) points to Chancellor Merkel's response to the Fukushima crisis as an example of responsive leadership. In response to overwhelming anti-nuclear sentiment, Merkel rapidly initiated the phase-out of Germany's oldest reactors. While this decision created energy stability issues later (e.g., reliance on Russian gas), at the time, it demonstrated a profound connection to the immediate will of the populace.

The capacity for concern: This is a sign of psychological maturation. Winnicott (1963) defined "concern" as the positive manifestation of responsibility, contrasting it with the negative concept of "guilt." Guilt implies a fear of destroying a loved object; concern implies further psychological integration and the genuine ability to care about the consequences of one's actions, particularly when instinctual drives (like the drive to survive at any cost) enter the relationship. A leader who lacks the capacity for concern will prioritize their own political survival over the preservation of human life during a crisis.

Conclusion

In contemporary discourse, the terms "anxiety" and "stress" have been normalized to the point of dilution, masking a state of chronic systemic trauma. At every level of human existence—from the individual and familial to the organizational, national, and global—we are witnessing processes that fundamentally "shatter" the established world order. To defend against the overwhelming insecurity of these systemic disasters, there is a pervasive tendency for individuals and societies to retreat into narcissistic isolation, effectively denying the existential threats that confront us.

The research presented here suggests that the greatest source of contemporary anxiety is not merely the external threat itself, but the perceived irresponsibility of leaders at the national and global levels. When governance is driven by regressive defense mechanisms rather than a "capacity for concern," the decisions made can jeopardize human life on a catastrophic scale. This climate of instability profoundly narrows the quality of individual existence and stifles the creative contribution of the individual to the collective human project.

Ultimately, existing mechanisms for advocating for the needs of the citizenry have proven inadequate against entrenched, regressive governance practices. To move toward a more stable geopolitical and social equilibrium, a paradigm shift in communication is required. We must develop more robust frameworks for articulating fundamental human needs and demand a commensurate level of transparency and psychological maturity from ruling structures. Only by integrating the lessons of collective trauma can we foster a governance capable of responding to the uncertainties of the future with rational foresight rather than reactive panic.

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PANEL IV

VIRTUAL PANEL

Chair: Charyl Cross

Discussant: Mihajlo Kopanja

The perception of government in remote ethnic communities of East Siberia

Fartyshev Arseniy Nikolaevich¹ and Razmakhnina Julia Sergeevna²

Abstract:

The issues of electoral behavior and the interaction of the electorate and power among the indigenous small people of the soyots, who live in one of the most remote regions of Russia - the Okinsky rayon of Buryatia, are covered. Soyots as a typical long remote community in Russia are characterized by a higher level of support for pro-government candidates and the ruling party, which is based on a sense of non-participation in the federal agenda due to their geographical remoteness, which implies their conformist behavior. In the Okinsky district, there is a high activity of local authorities and a variety of non-trivial political practices, which are described in the article. A pronounced ethnic feature is the high level of political influence among religious actors (buddhist lamas and shamans), that is low researched yet, as well as the presence of public institutions that defend the issues of legislative initiatives at the federal level, which in perception are equated with government. The main problems of soyots that have importance for political campaigns was revealed. We have identified the less perception distance between municipality governments in local long remote communities according to the same distance in urban communities.

Keywords:

electoral geography, geography of power, electoral motivation, Russia, political system, remote areas, ethnic peripheries, Okinskiy district.

¹ Candidate of Sciences (Geography), Head of Laboratory of Geo-Resource Studies and Political Geography, V. B. Sochava Institute of Geography SB RAS, Associate Professor of Department of Political Science, History and Regional Studies Irkutsk State University.

² Candidate of Sciences (Geography), Researcher, Laboratory of Geo-Resource Studies and Political Geography, V. B. Sochava Institute of Geography SB RAS.

Introduction

The ethnic peripheries of both Russia and the whole world are of particular interest in electoral geography, because, as a rule, there are anomalous voting results there in relation to the average level. In relation to concept of failed state, governmental power cannot cover all of the territory of the state and control the space homogeneously (Jessop, 2016), at the first time an intension decreased in remote peripheries at it's rightfully for large countries. Relatively large ethnic minorities can both create their own parties, and among them, other types of “socio-electoral cleavages” can significantly influence (Lipset, Rokkan, 1967). In conditions where there is no party that represents the interests of ethnic minorities in the elections, the votes of local ethnic communities can be extremely unpredictable: both sharply opposed, and, on the contrary, increased vote for the dominating party. Small ethnic communities are more homogeneous, but the main issue lies in formation of the electoral cultures of such communities.

The purpose of all the work was to assess the role of the ethnic factor in political-geographical processes and socio-demographic and economic development of Eastern Siberia.

Methods and data

The Okinsky district of Buryatia is an area inhabited predominantly by a non-Russian population (about 94%) and is part of the ethnic periphery. Soyots are included in list of indigenous ethnoses of Siberia (Bezrukov and Razmakhina. 2021.). According to official data the share of soyots in Okinsky district is 60 %. In conditions of its hard-accessibility and expressed peripheral location, Okinsky district represents a well researching polygon for political and social-geographical science.

Map: Administrative map of Okinsky district of Buryatia

The statistical analysis based on official data of federal election campaigns for the period 2000-2023 of presidential and duma's elections (excluding of single-member constituency elections) that was extracted from governmental automatized system "Vybory".

The qualitative analysis based on field researches that has been waged by authors in Okinsky distict of Peruplic Buryatiya in June of 2021 and 2022. A survey research with elements of semistructured interview (n=279) that took 19,5% of population that have active electoral right of settlements (uluses Sorok, Khurba, Bokson, Nyurgan, Khuzhir, Sayany, Shasnur, Obtoy, Tusmak). Furthermore it was collected the individual in-depth interviews with a representatives of local ethnic and political elite – the heads of municipalities, directors of schools, religious and public firures.

Results

Decision to vote of soyots

In the Okinsky district during the 2000–2010s there is an abnormally increased turnout in the elections, as well as the percentage of votes for the pro-governmental party and candidates representing this party. This situation is not unique in Russia, and is typical for many ethnically non-Russian territories (Ignatov et al, 2022; Shkel et al, 2022). The average excess of turnout in the Okinsky district in relation to the all-Russian level is 14%, and in relation to the regional average it is even higher – 15.9%. It shown on table 1.

Table 1: The average variation of results of federal elections in Buryatia during 2000-2021

Raion Buryatia	of Share russian / non russian ethics	turnout	Average variation by districts from total level			
			Edinaya Rossiya ("dominating party")	Communist Party	Liberal- democratic party	Against all
Barguzin	75,5/22,7	-0,27	1,16	1,30	-1,14	0,12
Baunt	77,6/19,4	1,75	0,95	-0,85	0,61	-0,16
Bichura	87,1/12,1	-4,25	-6,56	8,06	0,57	-0,24
Severobaikalsk	84,2/4,4	-5,87	-9,40	4,36	3,30	0,05

Ulan-Ude	63,6/32,8	<i>-4,35</i>	<i>-10,17</i>	6,31	-1,11	0,05
Dzhida	55,6/41,3	2,41	2,51	1,50	-2,94	0,28
Evarninskiy	43,6/55,1	13,93	6,03	0,08	-3,52	0,27
Zaigraevo	83,1/13,5	-4,51	-1,75	2,79	0,16	-0,08
Zakamenskiy	32,4/65,8	13,43	14,30	<i>-3,32</i>	<i>-5,34</i>	-0,33
Ivolginskiy	37,5/60,8	-2,26	-4,03	4,03	-2,87	-0,05
Kabanskiy	92,4/5,2	-4,55	<i>-7,16</i>	3,08	2,84	0,22
Kizhinga	36,3/62,2	14,43	9,72	<i>-2,82</i>	<i>-5,29</i>	0,48
Kurumkan	30,1/68,6	8,52	6,51	<i>-1,67</i>	<i>-5,04</i>	-0,18
Kyakhta	72,7/23,4	2,85	3,41	-0,39	-0,02	0,05
Muyskiy	84,3/6,1	<i>-12,38</i>	<i>-4,65</i>	0,30	4,18	-0,18
Mukhorshibir	79,9/17,8	-0,39	0,06	2,41	-0,47	-0,16
Okinskiy	6,2/93,4	14,94	5,21	0,38	<i>-5,47</i>	0,23
Pribaikalskiy	95,8/2,3	-1,13	-3,65	1,32	2,01	0,01
Severobaikalskiy	85,5/8,0	0,42	-2,20	1,58	4,09	-0,21
Selenginskiy	61,7/34,4	-1,00	0,85	0,38	-0,89	-0,17
Tarbagatay	92,2/6,1	1,71	-1,30	3,29	-0,31	-0,06
Tunka	33,8/65,2	8,47	4,74	1,60	<i>-4,66</i>	0,07
Khorinskiy	62,1/35,1	7,86	6,65	<i>-1,63</i>	-2,90	-0,01

(maximum values are marked in dark, minimum values are marked in italics)

Statistical analysis reveals that the districts with high share of indigenous people have the heightened rate of turnout and result of pro-governance party in federal elections campaigns of 2000-2021. In opposite most of them has decreased rate of

Communist party and Liberal-Democratic party. Why it has been happening? Can we expect this effect in future?

Based on the results of field research, a really high motivation to vote was revealed, which determines a high level of turnout and a low level of absenteeism. According to the theory of electoral motivation by A. Blais and J.-F. Daoust (2020), the decision to vote or abstain depends on the answers to four key questions: Do I like the policy? Am I required to vote? Do I care about the result? Is it easy to vote? Using the example of the Soyots, the main factor is the duty to vote (“it’s my duty”, “because it’s necessary”), at the same time, the interest in politics and the interest in the voting results is extremely low. Respondents also note that they are afraid not to vote because they want to appear antisocial to others (“what will others think of me if I don’t vote, that I’m somehow different?”). Thus, among the Soyots, the ethical and social aspect of voting motivation predominates, which, on the one hand, is typical for compact communities (Ali, Lin, 2013), on the other hand, is a local feature of the electoral culture at the all-Russian level, where other factors of voting motivation are mixed in.

Elections of parties of soyots

Soyots are characterized by a higher level of support for pro-government candidates and the ruling party, which is based on a sense of non-participation in the federal agenda due to their geographical remoteness, which implies their conformist behavior. In the Okinsky district, there is a high activity of local authorities and a variety of non-trivial political practices (in detail: (Fartyshev et al, 2023)). In conditions of political isolation and local budget deficits, local authorities become more important than even the regional government.

Statistical analysis shows that areas with a high share of the indigenous population (Eravninsky, Zakamensky, Kizhinginsky, Kurumkansky, Okinsky, Tunkinsky districts) on average in the federal election campaigns of 2003-2021 have higher turnout rates, voted more actively for pro-government candidates, while most of them have one of the lowest indicators for the Communist Party of the Russian Federation and the Liberal Democratic Party. At the same time, it should be noted that there is a high dispersion of values for the indicators of the Communist Party of the Russian Federation, but some of the lowest dispersion values for turnout and votes for power. Thus, in the 2011 elections to the State Duma of the Russian Federation in the Okinsky district, the Communist Party (CPRF) received the highest value in Eastern Siberia - 32%, while in the presidential elections in 2004 and 2018 the anomalous result of the Okinsky district was voting for the pro-government candidate V.V. Putin (84.2% and 83.1%, respectively).

Table 2: Preferences of the Soyots to main political parties in Russia (n=270).

Party	Positive	Neutral	Negative
Edinaya Rossiya (for existing power)	163	84	23
Communitistic party	78	164	28
Liberal-democratic party	54	156	60
Spravedlivaya Rossia (social-democratic party)	46	189	35

The survey data confirms a high level of positive attitude towards “Edinaya Rossiya”, but it is still less than what electoral statistics show. The negative perception of the Liberal-democratic party comes mainly from the historical sentence about the nationalist character of this party, which has been entrenched since the 1990s, although in fact such slogans have ceased to be used by 2020. The attitude towards the Communist Party is mostly neutral. On the one hand, an olders remember the forced extermination of Soyot language speakers during the years of the Red Terror; on the other hand, the modern image of the party is poorly linked to the events of the distant past. During the Soviet period, there was no significant industrialization of the territory of the Okinskiy district, with the exception of a few kolkhozes. Neutrality towards the social-democratic party Spravedlivaya Rossia is expressed rather by poor awareness of it, its political agenda and political leaders. The specific of all-russian political culture is memorability of party based on authorities and personality of leaders.

The key characteristic of the electoral behavior of ethnic peripheral territories is conformism, understood as an individual’s uncritical perception of the existing order of things and refusal to develop his own position, which is expressed in voting for the current government again and again (Wantchekon, 2003). As a result of our research, it was revealed that the conformity of the Soyots lies not so much in a passive political position, but in various forms of clientelism (Fartyshv et al, 2023). In exchange for solving local problems of remote rural settlements, loyalty to one or another party is a subject of bargaining, since in conditions of compact living of small ethnic groups, the mobilization of electoral resources is facilitated, which creates conditions for the use of the administrative factor (Veselova and Tchernev, 2018).

Alternative political leaders in Okinskiy district

Historically, the main interaction in the Oka region is between representatives of shamanism and buddhism. In many ways, shamans and lamas are the bearers of power and high authority among the population. The main problems that the local population prefers to solve not through government agencies, but through religious leaders are the treatment of diseases, the search for a missing livestock, problems in family. It is typical that the relationship between religious leaders is complementary: the lama, if it is impossible to help or the forecast does not come true, refers people to the shaman and vice versa. Moreover, several shamans can act in one village, but only one lama, as a spiritual mentor, has significant political weight. This phenomenon explains the tendency of institutionalization of clergy as political actors. In modern Buryatia, shamans are organized into legally formalized professional communities or carry out their activities individually (Mikhalev, 2022). With their authority, they help solve many social and political problems, often succeeding where the official government or police is powerless.

In addition, there are elements of civil society in the area that are positively perceived by the population and through which it is possible to achieve certain political decisions. Issues of legislative initiatives regarding the rights of Soyots are resolved not through official representatives of the electorate in legislatures, but through a public organization - the Association of Indigenous Peoples of Siberia and the Far North. Its recognition among the Soyot population turned out to be high: among the initiatives it implemented, respondents were able to name the reduction of the threshold for entering the retirement age for representatives of indigenous peoples by five years, the revival of the practice of teaching the Soyot language in primary school, obtaining preferential budget places in higher educational institutions of the region (not yet implemented in practice), etc. In the perception of the population, the association is practically equated with power structures, since the main office of the Soyot representative office is located directly in the district administration building.

Rating of political problems

In the next step we asked a respondents about the main problems that should be represented at in election program of candidates. Which one is specify for ethnic community of indigenous people and which one is regular in the context of all-Russian political discourse. What worries the Soyot population most. In the next we show it into the list:

1) Road Mondy-Orlik – 36,8 % from those who answered. Okinsky district connected with other part of Buryatia by unpaved road about 150 km length, that it had been constructed only in 1993. Before that the relation with district had been worked as horse-drawn and aircraft transport (Kuklina et al., 2022). The supply and product prices in district are depended from condition of this road, moreover it can be closed at the rainy period, and that's why it so bother for natives At the time

fencing from the outer world in case of automobile roads might be a own chase of indigenous people (Schweitzer, 2017). In nomad cultures the issue of transport accessibility is being comprehended different than in sedentary ones (Konstantinov, 2009). But the gradual departure of the Soyots from a nomadic lifestyle to a semi-nomadic and sedentary one forces them to take more and more attention to infrastructural benefits.

2) Development of agriculture and especially livestock farming (20,6 %). That shows the main economic interest that is in need of fiscal facilities. So, such governmental initiatives in agriculture as far-eastern hectar (agreement for free use of land) do not so efficient as it purposed at the first time of realization of this program (Zhuravskaya and Ryzhova, 2021), due to intension of natives to use it for privatization of moving and pasturelands.

3) Electricity of homesteads (8,8 %). There is only one branch of electricity power line (110 kW) to neighboring Tunkinskiy district and from time to time power surges and failures are happened in time of climate cataclysm. This problem is of an infrastructural nature, inherent for most of remote peripheral territories, and therefore cannot be attributed to the exceptional cases of Soyots.

4) Quotas for applicants (8,8 %). Several regions of Russia have a practice to give additional budget places for indigenous representatives to studying in university, such as in Sakha(Yakutiya) region where this advantage was realized for 71 native person, that was conquest by mentioned Association of Indigenous Peoples of Siberia and the Far North. But incase of Buryatia it's not working.

5) Problem of learning and speaking in mother language (8,8 %). The Soyot language is considered extinct, since there is not a single native speaker left, but all of the soyots are well speak in Buryat. According to informants, in 1926–1927. purges of those who knew the language took place in the area: “Other peoples of the Eastern Sayan of Turkic origin - Tuvans-Todzhins, Tofalars - retained their language, but Soyot language was banned by Soviet Russia”. Nowadays optional teaching of the Soyot language is conducted only in school grades 1-4 and it is not used in everyday life. On the one hand, the Soyots express concern about the extinction of their original language, but on the other hand, at the present stage, replacement by the Buryat language has already occurred naturally.

6) Problems in licensing hunting and fishing (2,9 %). Indigenous people have a right for free using natural resources on the *Коренные малочисленные народы вправе бесплатно пользоваться природными ресурсами в границах territories of traditional nature management*, but nevertheless they have to get a license. According to the informant: “It’s difficult to receive it. At this time there is no hunting inspector in our area. The hunting county is united with the Mukhorshibirsky district, so the hunting inspector practically does not visit the Okinsky district. On the one hand, the legislative norm does not work, but there is also no supervision over violation of environmental rules for Soyots.

7) The problem of catching wolves (1%). The Soyots are predominantly pastoral people, and they take their herds to the mountains in the summer, where there is an acute problem of wolf overpopulation. There is a law norm about independently catching wolves, whereas the Federal Service for Supervision of Natural Resources buys wolf skins from the hunters. According to the informant: “We give 16 thousand rubles for a wolf. and we’ll hand it over, but there’s no inspector: we’ll have to go to Ulan-Ude.” However, in 2020, 168 were caught, which, although a large number, is not enough to protect the herds. As a result, many households remain in villages and do not go to the mountains because of fear of the wolf threat.

So, most of the problems have a social-economic aspect but they are characterized by local specific. There are many problems of ethnocultural nature like a reconstruction of language heritage and teaching of natural traditions that’s peculiarly for Okinskiy district and it is not conducted in electoral programs of political parties.

Conclusion

The uniqueness of the perception of political power among the soyots lies in the following features:

1. the motivation to vote is based on social and ethical aspects such as a fear of antisocial person appearing in compact community and a sense of duty to vote
2. we indicate a high level of support for pro-government candidates and the party in power is lied in conformist behavior and various forms of clientelism.
3. there are high activity of local authorities and non-trivial methods of solving local problems due to the shorter distance between the authorities and voters.
4. there is a high level of political influence among religious actors: buddhist lamas and shamans.
5. we observes the activity of public institutions in conditions of rural undeveloped political culture that defend issues of legislative initiatives at the federal level, which are equated to power.

The researching group will continue the researches: a surveying, interviews, included observation in different remote areas of Eastern Russia and we would like to invite to dialog to make interregional comparative studies of perception of government in remote areas.

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From Religion to Ethnonationalism: The Argument for Civil Society-Based Programming in Bosnia and Herzegovina

Laura Welty¹

Abstract:

Civil society organisations (CSOs) are widely recognised as critical actors in preventing and countering violent extremism, yet existing scholarship has overwhelmingly focused on religious radicalisation—particularly Salafism—while neglecting right-wing ethnonationalism. This article argues that community-based prevention and de-radicalisation strategies developed in response to Salafist extremism in Bosnia and Herzegovina are not only relevant but transferable to ethnonationalist radicalisation. Drawing on social identity theory and interdisciplinary literature on radicalisation, the article analyses how group belonging, identity formation, and community legitimacy function across ideological contexts. Using Bosnia as a critical case, the study synthesises existing empirical research, policy analysis, and qualitative interview material to demonstrate that civil society-led interventions—particularly those emphasising intergroup dialogue, critical thinking, and local legitimacy—address shared underlying mechanisms of radicalisation. The article contributes to debates in terrorism studies and nationalism scholarship by reframing ethnonationalism as a form of radicalisation amenable to established CVE approaches, while highlighting the indispensable role of civil society in sustaining long-term prevention and disengagement.

Key words:

Bosnia, Ethnonationalism, Radicalisation, Civil Society Organisations, Identity

¹ Lecturer in Political Science, Australian National University, School of Politics and International Relations
laura.welty@anu.edu.au

Introduction

Civil society organisations (CSOs) play a critical role in long-term prevention, disengagement, and de-radicalisation. Existing scholarship consistently demonstrates that sustained personal relationships, community embeddedness, and family support are central to successful disengagement and de-radicalisation outcomes. At the micro level, Social Identity Theory helps explain these dynamics by showing how individuals construct their sense of self through group membership, often reinforcing in-group cohesion through the exclusion or stigmatisation of perceived ‘others’ (Tajfel and Turner, 1986). These identity-based processes are central to both radicalisation and efforts to counter it.

This paper examines right-wing radicalisation and counter-radicalisation in Bosnia and Herzegovina from a local, community-centred perspective, drawing on interpretive approaches, political anthropology, and political ethnography. It argues that community-based interventions—particularly those that cultivate critical thinking skills and facilitate intergroup dialogue—are essential to effective prevention and intervention. Building on insights from existing Salafist counter-radicalisation programming in Bosnia, the paper further argues that these methods are transferable to efforts addressing right-wing ethnonationalism.

This study departs from previous research on extremism in Bosnia and Herzegovina in two key ways. First, the existing literature has disproportionately focused on foreign fighters and Salafi communities, marginalising ethnonationalism as a form of radicalisation despite its broader social and political salience. Second, the analysis demonstrates that ethnonationalist extremists across Bosniak, Serb, and Croat communities share significant commonalities in attitudes and worldviews, even when their ideologies are framed as mutually antagonistic (Halilović and Veljan, 2021). These shared characteristics point to the limitations of ethnically segmented approaches and underscore the need for comprehensive strategies that transcend ethnic divisions. The paper argues that CSOs are uniquely positioned to facilitate such approaches and concludes by outlining evidence-informed recommendations for structuring effective civil society-led programmes.

Literature Review

This literature review provides a brief overview of the radicalisation and counter-radicalisation theory most applicable for evaluating the Bosnian response to Salafism and right-wing ethnonationalism. This paper adopts a processual view of radicalisation and agrees that there is no set universal definition (Nasser-Eddine et al., 2011). While there is an identified interplay among the micro-, meso-, and macro-levels of analysis that provides a holistic view of the drivers of radicalisation, this paper focuses on the micro- and meso-levels.

The Micro-Level

Micro-level analyses centre on the individual and remain dominant within radicalisation research. At this level, radicalisation is frequently associated with experiences of alienation from the social or political status quo, which can provide psychological justification for adopting ideologies that frame that status quo as illegitimate or hostile (Keys-Turner, 2011). Schmid (2013) identifies a constellation of factors commonly associated with micro-level vulnerability,

including identity crises, marginalisation, discrimination, relative deprivation, humiliation, stigmatisation, and moral outrage, often accompanied by feelings of vicarious revenge.

Social Identity Theory offers a particularly useful framework for understanding how these individual experiences translate into group-based radicalisation. The theory posits that individuals derive a significant portion of their self-concept from group membership and that perceived status differentials between in-groups and out-groups can intensify processes of otherisation (Tajfel and Turner, 1986). In this context, radicalisation operates through the consolidation of a threatened or elevated group identity, whereby negative attributes are ascribed to out-groups in order to reinforce in-group cohesion and self-esteem. These identity dynamics underpin the mobilisation of individuals not only at the interpersonal level, but also at broader communal, national, and transnational scales.

The Meso-Level

Meso-level analyses shift attention from individual psychology to the social environments in which radicalisation is embedded. This approach emphasises the role of socio-cultural and ideological contexts in initiating and sustaining radicalisation by shaping the opportunities, narratives, and relational structures available to individuals (Keys-Turner, 2011). Central to this level is the concept of the radical milieu: a supportive or complicit social surround that normalises extremist ideas and behaviours, and provides emotional rewards such as belonging, purpose, and solidarity (Schmid, 2013).

The significance of the meso-level is particularly evident in right-wing extremism, where perceived threats to racial, ethnic, or national groups function as powerful push factors. Group-level propaganda in this context typically draws on cultural myths and identity narratives, framing violence as morally justified through processes of dehumanisation and moral disengagement (Vergani et al., 2020). Similar mechanisms are observed in studies of Islamic radicalisation, where group dynamics—including peer pressure, strong intra-group bonds, fulfilment of belonging and identity needs, and the influence of family or kinship networks—play a decisive role in sustaining extremist commitment (Vergani et al., 2020).

Online environments increasingly replicate these meso-level dynamics by providing digital spaces for community formation, narrative reinforcement, and social validation. Across ideological contexts, the literature identifies recurring demographic patterns, with extremists most frequently described as young men, and, in the case of far-right movements, predominantly white individuals born in the societies in which they radicalise (Vergani et al., 2020). These patterns underscore the importance of social context and group affiliation, rather than ideology alone, in understanding pathways into radicalisation.

Disengagement vs De-radicalisation

Disengagement and de-radicalisation both address individuals who have already been exposed to or involved in extremist ideologies or organisations, yet the literature distinguishes them as analytically and empirically distinct processes. Although the terms are sometimes used

interchangeably, this conflation obscures important differences in mechanisms and outcomes. Disengagement refers primarily to behavioural change—most notably the cessation of participation in extremist activities—whereas de-radicalisation entails a substantive transformation of beliefs and ideological commitments.

De-radicalisation is commonly defined as the process through which individuals reject extremist worldviews and adopt beliefs aligned with socially accepted or non-violent norms (Rabasa et al., 2010). It involves a fundamental shift in cognitive frameworks, such that the individual no longer adheres to the ideological foundations that previously justified extremist behaviour. By contrast, disengagement does not require ideological renunciation. Drawing on Ebaugh's (1988) concept of role exit, disengagement occurs when individuals withdraw from the roles, practices, or organisational memberships associated with extremism, even if elements of the underlying worldview remain intact. As Windisch et al. (2016) emphasise, an individual may disengage from violence or organisational activity while continuing to hold radical beliefs, making disengagement a necessary but insufficient condition for de-radicalisation.

Disengagement can occur through both voluntary and involuntary pathways and is shaped by a combination of push and pull factors as well as exit barriers. Voluntary disengagement is most commonly triggered by ideological disillusionment, leadership failures, interpersonal conflict, or personal life changes, including family considerations (Dalgaard-Nielsen, 2013). These dynamics underscore the importance of preventative and early-intervention programming that identifies and addresses the conditions under which individuals begin to question their involvement. By targeting the relational and contextual factors that facilitate disengagement, such interventions can create exit pathways before ideological commitments become fully entrenched, thereby increasing the prospects for longer-term de-radicalisation.

Push and Pull Factors

The literature on ethnonationalist extremism closely parallels research on Islamic extremism and other forms of radical group membership, emphasising that radicalisation does not stem from a single causal driver. Instead, scholars identify recurring patterns involving grievances, unmet social and psychological needs, ideational framing, group dynamics, and the normalisation of violence. As Neumann (2017) argues, radicalisation across ideological contexts emerges from societal tensions and fault lines that generate identity conflicts and perceptions of injustice, marginalisation, and exclusion.

A central mechanism in this process is the fulfilment of emotional and social needs through group membership. Extremist organisations offer belonging, community, purpose, and recognition—often framed in terms of adventure, power, or moral significance—which can be particularly appealing to individuals experiencing social or economic insecurity (Neumann, 2017). These affective incentives are reinforced through ideational narratives that identify a vilified 'other' and present the group's ideology as a coherent solution to perceived grievances. Radicalisation thus operates as a social process, sustained by interpersonal ties and reinforced by authority figures, charismatic leaders, or tightly knit peer networks that generate trust, loyalty, and peer pressure (Neumann, 2017).

Empirical studies further highlight the structural conditions that function as push factors into ethnonationalist extremism. Vergani et al. (2020) identify relative deprivation—variously expressed as inequality, exclusion, frustration, victimisation, or stigmatisation—as one of the most consistent predictors of radicalisation. In the Bosnian context, Halilović and Veljan (2021) find that individuals with lower levels of education or dissatisfaction with income, family life, and future prospects are significantly more likely to legitimise violence. Their analysis also reveals a strong association between permanent employment and affiliation with ruling ethnonationalist parties, indicating how political patronage networks can reinforce far-right mobilisation rather than mitigate it.

These dynamics underscore the importance of civil society interventions that address radicalisation as a socially embedded and relational process rather than solely an ideological one. CSOs are uniquely positioned to intervene at the level of grievances, identity, and belonging by providing alternative forms of community, recognition, and participation that do not rely on exclusionary or violent narratives. By engaging individuals before extremist identities become fully consolidated—and by addressing the socio-economic and relational contexts in which grievances are interpreted—civil society actors can disrupt recruitment pathways and reduce the appeal of ethnonationalist mobilisation.

The Role of Civil Society

Extremism manifests across the political spectrum, and effective prevention and counter-radicalisation strategies must therefore avoid privileging or excluding particular ideological forms. A consistent finding in the literature is that counter-extremism programming must be grounded in the protection of human rights and civil liberties, including freedoms of expression, religion, and association, and must avoid stigmatising specific communities. Where restrictions on these freedoms are deemed necessary, they must be legally justified, legitimate, and proportionate to the threat identified (OSCE, 2018). This rights-based framework is central to maintaining the legitimacy and effectiveness of counter-extremism interventions.

Within this context, civil society organisations play a critical and distinctive role. The OSCE defines civil society as a diverse constellation of formal and informal actors engaged in public life to advance shared values and social objectives (OSCE, 2018). These actors—including youth groups, women’s organisations, religious leaders, educators, and community representatives—are uniquely positioned to deliver prevention and intervention initiatives because of their credibility, social embeddedness, and sustained engagement with local populations. Civil society actors are often better equipped than state institutions to identify community-specific grievances and vulnerabilities that increase susceptibility to extremist narratives, particularly among marginalised or at-risk groups (OSCE, 2018).

The OSCE’s prevention–intervention–rehabilitation framework further clarifies the functional space in which civil society operates. Prevention efforts focus on strengthening community resilience through awareness-raising, education, dialogue initiatives, and trust-building activities, including interfaith engagement and collaboration with local institutions (OSCE, 2018; Neumann, 2017). Intervention strategies target individuals already exhibiting at-risk behaviours, often through voluntary disengagement and exit pathways designed to prevent escalation into

violence. Rehabilitation programmes, typically operating in custodial or post-custodial settings, aim to support longer-term disengagement and de-radicalisation (OSCE, 2018; Neumann, 2017). While rehabilitation frequently involves state institutions, civil society actors remain essential in providing continuity of support during reintegration and aftercare.

In Bosnia and Herzegovina, civil society has been particularly central to prevention and early-intervention efforts. Existing programmes emphasise community-based approaches that combine critical thinking skills, interfaith dialogue, and locally grounded engagement as core elements of resilience-building (Welty, 2022). The OSCE (2018) further highlights the importance of involving youth, families, women, victims of terrorism, and religious, cultural, and educational leaders in counter-extremism initiatives, recognising their capacity to foster social cohesion and challenge exclusionary narratives from within communities. By operating within a rights-based framework and leveraging local legitimacy, civil society organisations play an indispensable role in sustaining long-term prevention, disengagement, and de-radicalisation processes.

CSOs and Religious Radicalism

Insights from fieldwork interviews further illustrate how identity dynamics and community support shape disengagement and de-radicalisation processes. In an interview, Amra Pandžo (2019) reflected on her experience as a former Salafi and the lessons drawn from her disengagement that now inform her work as a civil society practitioner. Her account demonstrates a core insight of Social Identity Theory: radicalisation and exit are shaped by tensions between competing group memberships. Pandžo described how perceived incompatibilities between her Salafi identity, cultural background, and gendered expectations generated ideological disillusionment and ultimately facilitated disengagement.

While Pandžo could not clearly identify the motivations that initially led her to join a Salafi community, she consistently emphasised several factors that supported her disengagement and longer-term de-radicalisation. These included dissatisfaction with doctrinal positions—particularly regarding the role of women—conflicts with her cultural identity, sustained support from family and neighbourhood networks, the development of critical thinking skills, and access to religious education that encouraged interpretive plurality. Importantly, she underscored the value of community-based approaches that integrate interfaith dialogue and critical reflection, principles she now applies in her peacebuilding and civil society work (Welty, 2022).

These insights align closely with the broader disengagement and de-radicalisation literature, which identifies community, belonging, and education as central mechanisms in both recruitment and exit processes (Ebaugh, 1988; Rabasa et al., 2010; Dalgaard-Nielsen, 2013; Windisch et al., 2016). Extremist groups often exploit unmet needs for belonging and purpose during recruitment; paradoxically, these same needs must be addressed to facilitate successful exit. In Pandžo's case, the presence of a supportive social environment reduced the perceived risks of leaving and mitigated fears associated with social isolation. As Dalgaard-Nielsen (2013) notes, disengagement is frequently triggered by burnout, moral doubt, or changing personal

priorities, but without supportive networks, individuals may delay exit or relapse due to fear of losing their only source of community.

The literature further emphasises that disengagement alone is insufficient without opportunities for identity reconstruction and reintegration. Rabasa et al. (2010) argue that individuals exiting extremist movements must develop alternative identities and social networks to reduce the risk of recidivism. In Bosnia, however, communal cleavages—particularly between mainstream Muslim communities and Salafi groups—can create significant reintegration barriers, reinforcing hesitation to disengage and limiting pathways out of extremism. For exit to be viable, individuals must perceive movement between social groups as possible and socially legitimate.

These dynamics have direct implications for civil society-led counter-radicalisation. The mechanisms that facilitate recruitment—identity affirmation, community formation, and education—can be strategically repurposed in prevention and disengagement programming, including in efforts targeting right-wing ethnonationalism. Strengthening community resilience through education and critical engagement is central to countering extremist ideology and empowering local leaders to challenge exclusionary narratives (Neumann, 2011). In Bosnia, initiatives such as the Nahla Centre for Education and Research, Mali Koraci (Small Steps), Resonant Voices Initiative, Inicijativa Etos, and Youth Education exemplify this approach by prioritising skills development, community building, interfaith dialogue, and digital literacy. Many of these programmes deliberately engage youth and women, recognising their influence within families and communities. Despite demonstrated successes, their broader impact remains constrained by the fact that religious radicalisation is often perceived as less urgent than ethnonationalist extremism within Bosnian society, shaping funding priorities and public engagement (Welty, 2022).

Challenges in the Bosnian Context

Civil society-led de-radicalisation programmes in Bosnia and Herzegovina face persistent constraints related to institutional capacity, funding, and issue prioritisation. Interview data indicate that effective civil society interventions rely on community-oriented approaches that directly engage individuals at risk, with particular emphasis on interfaith dialogue, critical thinking skills, and organisational capacity development. However, a significant challenge lies in the relatively low salience of Salafist radicalisation within broader public perceptions. As Welty (2022) notes, most Bosnians do not view religious radicalisation as an issue that meaningfully affects everyday life. As Funk (2019) explains, Salafism is not widely denied as a phenomenon, but it is rarely considered socially urgent.

By contrast, ethnonationalism occupies a far more prominent place in public concern. Practitioners interviewed for this study consistently framed nationalism—not Salafism—as the primary radicalising force in Bosnia. Funk (2019) captures this shift succinctly, arguing that “the key radicals in Bosnia are not Salafists, but nationalists, nationalist rhetoric, the nationalist element.” This reframing reflects a broader tension between local threat perceptions and donor-driven programming priorities. Salafist radicalisation emerged as a focal point largely because it attracted international attention and funding as a “new” security concern, rather than

because it aligned with locally perceived drivers of instability (Funk, 2019). This disconnect reinforces the central argument of this paper: lessons learned from Salafist counter-radicalisation must be redirected toward addressing ethnonationalist extremism, where local relevance and social resonance are far greater.

Capacity limitations further constrain civil society effectiveness. Interviews with social workers and representatives of Centres for Social Work confirm that public welfare institutions lack the resources and training necessary to meet the needs of vulnerable populations, including those at risk of radicalisation (Turčalo and Veljan, 2018). Professionals consistently reported that insufficient institutional capacity and inadequate training undermine trust between service providers and the very individuals most in need of support. These structural weaknesses are compounded by the limited reach of community-level programming. Much existing Preventing and Countering Violent Extremism (P/CVE) activity remains initiated and directed at the state or entity level, making it difficult to assess responsiveness to local conditions or measure long-term impact (Turčalo and Veljan, 2018).

The absence of genuinely locally owned and community-specific P/CVE initiatives poses a significant obstacle to effective prevention and intervention. Turčalo and Veljan (2018) warn that the lack of locally grounded programming risks undermining social trust and reducing community engagement, particularly in contexts shaped by distinct historical and cultural experiences. These concerns are reinforced by Azinović and Jusić (2016), who identify persistent flaws in Bosnian CVE programming, including reliance on assumed rather than empirically grounded drivers of radicalisation, insufficient contextualisation, and limited inclusion of local expertise. Such shortcomings not only reduce programme effectiveness but may also produce unintended harms by misidentifying target groups, marginalising local actors, and reinforcing perceptions of external imposition in domestic security affairs.

Ethnic Conflict and Narratives of Identity

Ethnic conflict may manifest in both violent and non-violent forms and is best understood as a socially constructed process rather than an inevitable outcome of cultural difference. Wolff (2013) defines ethnic conflict as group conflict interpreted and organised along real or perceived ethnonational divides, in which at least one party mobilises around a distinct ethnonational identity. Ethnonationalism, in this sense, is sustained through adversity and perceived denial, as concessions or institutional recognition can reinforce rather than dissolve separate identities by providing new rallying points for mobilisation (Connor, 1973).

Scholarship on situational ethnicity further highlights the contextual and relational nature of ethnic identity. Nagata (1974) and Mitchell (1974) argue that ethnicity is not fixed but emerges through social interaction, shaped by circumstances, perceptions, and political environments. In multiethnic states, ethnic identification draws on place of birth, lineage, tradition, and culture, but its salience fluctuates depending on context (Zdeb, 2019). Bosnia and Herzegovina exemplifies this dynamic particularly clearly. Historically and contemporarily, ethnicity has functioned less as a static marker of belonging than as a strategic and situational resource shaping social relations, state institutions, and political competition (Zdeb, 2019). As Connor (1973) notes, ethnic groups become nations only when members themselves internalise a

shared sense of distinctiveness, underscoring the importance of self-definition in ethnonational mobilisation.

Despite Bosnia's post-war reputation as a deeply divided society, historical accounts emphasise long-standing patterns of coexistence and everyday pluralism. Fine argues that tolerance characterised much of Bosnia's history, with conflict emerging primarily through external or elite-driven mobilisation (cited in Toal and Dahlman, 2011). Andjelić (2003) similarly observes that coexistence and mutual accommodation outweighed open hostility for much of Bosnia's past. Cultural historians describe this pattern as a "unity in diversity," in which difference was both recognised and normalised within everyday social life (Lovrenović, 1999). Anthropological studies further demonstrate that exposure to cultural and religious diversity was embedded in identity formation for most Bosnians, producing ambivalent but enduring traditions of coexistence (Bringa, 1993).

These traditions were institutionalised through social practices such as *komšijski odnosi* (neighbourly relations) and *zajednički život* (common life), which emphasised accommodation rather than assimilation (Zdeb, 2019). Even contemporary identity categories—such as "Bosnian Muslim"—often denote cultural and historical belonging rather than strict religious adherence, reflecting a lived identity shaped by secularisation, folk traditions, and shared experience (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021). Notably, research suggests that among individuals holding extreme ethnonationalist views, shared attitudes and behavioural patterns often outweigh differences across Bosniak, Serb, and Croat communities, despite divergent symbolic expressions of tradition (Halilović and Veljan, 2021).

Ethnic consciousness nevertheless relies on the recognition of difference, constructing a referent "other" against which group identity is defined (Connor, 1972). Narratives play a central role in this process by shaping meaning, legitimising political claims, and delineating moral boundaries between "us" and "them" (Demirel, 2023). In post-conflict societies, narratives of past suffering are particularly potent, as they reinforce collective identity by defining victimhood, blame, and moral responsibility. Such narratives can impede reconciliation when they harden in-group and out-group distinctions or compete over exclusive claims to victimhood (Demirel, 2023).

In Bosnia, the uneven distribution of wartime violence has intensified these dynamics. Differential exposure to violence has shaped divergent understandings of responsibility and justice, complicating efforts to construct inclusive post-war narratives (Demirel, 2021). As a result, reconciliation is often conceptualised along ethnic lines, with different communities advancing incompatible expectations. While Bosniaks tend to support a moral remembrance model aligned with international norms, many Bosnian Serbs frame reconciliation as the rejection of narratives that cast them as collective aggressors (Demirel, 2023). These tensions are reinforced through denial, historical revisionism, and the mobilisation of wartime symbols and slurs, which continue to function as markers of exclusion and hostility in public discourse (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021).

These narrative dynamics have direct implications for radicalisation. As Oruc and Obradovic (2020) argue, future research must more closely examine the relationship between radicalisation and perceptions of wartime outcomes, justice, and what constitutes a "just peace." In Bosnia

and Herzegovina, ethnonationalist radicalisation is deeply embedded in contested histories and narrative competition, underscoring the need for interventions that address identity, memory, and meaning-making alongside material grievances.

The Relationship Between Religious Extremism and Ethnonationalism

Salafist radicalisation in Bosnia and Herzegovina culminated in two waves of Bosnian-born foreign fighters travelling to Syria and Iraq between 2012 and 2016. Estimates suggest that approximately 220–330 Bosnians participated in the conflict, making Bosnia the largest contributor of foreign fighters in the Western Balkans and the second-highest per capita contributor in Europe (Counter Extremism Project, 2021). By 2016, these flows had largely ceased, and many Salafist parajamaats were dismantled (Azinović and Jusić, 2016). This period prompted heightened international attention to Islamic extremism in Bosnia. At the same time, however, ethnonationalism and political extremism were intensifying domestically. Interview data indicate that many Bosnians viewed religious radicalisation as less pressing than nationalist rhetoric and mobilisation. As Funk (2019) observed, practitioners increasingly framed nationalism itself as a form of radicalisation, arguing that “the key radicals in Bosnia are not Salafists, but nationalists.” Reflecting this shift, scholars and policymakers have begun to acknowledge ethnonationalism as a central security and social challenge alongside religious extremism (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021).

Although Salafism and ethnonationalism are often treated as analytically distinct, the literature highlights significant points of convergence. Perry (2017) argues that both occupy a similar position on the rightward ideological spectrum, particularly in their repatriarchal logics and use of gender norms. Each represents a cultural backlash against feminist gains and promotes an idealised, moralised vision of a “better imagined past.” Both forms of extremism rely on exclusionary identity construction, defining a hostile ‘other’ against which in-group identity is affirmed and sustained. These dynamics are closely tied to nationalism and ethnic politics, privileging notions of blood, heritage, and immutable belonging over civic or pluralist conceptions of community (Perry, 2017).

Empirical research further underscores the entanglement of religion and ethnonationalism in Bosnia. Halilović and Veljan (2021) find that religion plays a significant role in everyday life for the vast majority of respondents, with a substantial proportion reporting strong adherence to religious teachings. Crucially, higher levels of religious devotion correlate with greater acceptance of violence when framed as defence or revenge on behalf of one’s ethnic or religious group. The authors argue that radical interpretations of religion can reinforce ethnonationalist narratives, intensifying polarisation and legitimising extremist attitudes.

Beyond belief systems, religious symbolism functions as a powerful narrative resource within ethnonationalist mobilisation. During the Bosnian war, religiously inflected stereotypes—such as Croats as Ustaše, Serbs as Chetniks, and Muslims as *Balija* or “Turks”—were widely deployed to inflame nationalist sentiment (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021). Religious identity also became a key mechanism of wartime mobilisation: for Bosnian Muslims,

persecution intensified religious identification, while for Catholic and Orthodox Christians, religion was invoked as justification for what was framed as a struggle for cultural and national survival (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021). Christianity, in particular, was frequently positioned as a superior civilisational principle opposed to Islam, which was portrayed as foreign or invasive.

In the contemporary Bosnian context, extremism and hate speech are most commonly associated with right-wing movements overlapping with Serb and Croat ethnonationalism, often infused with Christian symbolism, alongside radical forms of Islam and Bosniak or Bosnian nationalism (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021). While Orthodox and Catholic practices are not typically categorised as extremist, they assume radical significance when mobilised in exclusionary or ethnonationalist ways. Social media analysis reveals the extent to which religious imagery and clerical authority are incorporated into right-wing ethnonationalist discourse, with groups prominently displaying religious symbols and highlighting ties to religious institutions and leaders (Halilović and Veljan, 2021). These online performances frequently intersect with misogynistic, chauvinistic, and antisemitic narratives, targeting perceived out-groups through stereotyping, essentialisation, and abuse (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021).

Taken together, this literature demonstrates that Salafism and ethnonationalism in Bosnia are not isolated phenomena but overlapping forms of identity-based extremism. Their shared reliance on moralised narratives, gendered hierarchies, and religious symbolism helps explain why strategies developed to counter Salafist radicalisation may be adapted to address ethnonationalist extremism more effectively.

Key Recommended Elements for Programming

Inter-group Dialogue

Building on the demonstrated effectiveness of interfaith initiatives in countering religious extremism, civil society organisations (CSOs) should prioritise sustained inter-group dialogue as a core strategy for addressing ethnonationalist radicalisation (Welty, 2022). Empirical evidence from Bosnia indicates that meaningful contact across ethnic lines is associated with lower support for violence, even among individuals who hold ethnonationalist attitudes. Halilović and Veljan (2021) find that respondents who regularly interacted with members of other ethnic groups were more receptive to reconciliation, more likely to recognise the harms of glorifying war criminals, and less resistant to social and civic integration across ethnic boundaries. These patterns highlight the capacity of inter-group engagement to weaken exclusionary narratives and reduce the legitimisation of violence.

CSOs are uniquely positioned to facilitate such dialogue because of their local credibility, sustained community presence, and ability to convene participants across social and institutional divides. Through structured dialogue, joint community initiatives, and educational programming, CSOs can create environments in which contested identities and historical grievances can be addressed without securitisation or stigmatisation. Given the documented

overlap between religious and political extremism in Bosnia, these efforts should explicitly include engagement with religious communities. Educational and awareness-raising initiatives that address the instrumentalisation of religion by far-right movements not only strengthen broader societal resilience but also protect religious communities from co-optation by exclusionary ideologies. Collaboration with the Interreligious Council is therefore essential to ensure legitimacy, inclusivity, and sustained impact in CSO-led interventions (Halilović and Veljan, 2021).

The Role of Women

Women play a critical yet frequently underutilised role in countering radicalisation and extremism, particularly within the Bosnian context. Empirical evidence suggests that women are generally less supportive of violent extremism, and that attitudes toward gender equality are strongly associated with views on violence. Halilović and Veljan (2021) identify a direct relationship between the rejection of gender equality and increased support for violence, indicating that patriarchal value systems function as a risk factor for radicalisation.

Despite this, women's public engagement and activism in Bosnia have often been marginalised or framed as inappropriate under dominant ethnonationalist and patriarchal ideologies (Barton-Hronešová and Hodžić, 2021). This marginalisation stands in tension with women's demonstrated importance in fostering family stability, community cohesion, and informal social regulation—factors consistently identified as protective against radicalisation. Civil society organisations are therefore essential in creating legitimate and accessible spaces for women's participation in prevention and intervention efforts. By supporting women's leadership, amplifying their voices, and integrating gender-sensitive approaches into programming, CSOs can counter exclusionary narratives while strengthening community-level resilience to extremism.

The Role of Youth

Youth represent a key demographic in both the prevention of radicalisation and the reproduction of extremist narratives. Research consistently shows that young men are more susceptible to risk-taking behaviour and violent mobilisation (Budd et al., 2005; Farrington, 2003; Silke, 2008). In Bosnia and Herzegovina, these vulnerabilities are exacerbated by persistently high youth unemployment, social exclusion, and limited future prospects (CIJA, 2016; Bećirević, 2018). Oruc and Obradovic (2020) argue that these conditions foster grievance and a desire for revenge, placing young people at heightened risk of radicalisation relative to other age groups.

Empirical studies further indicate that support for violent extremism is more pronounced among younger cohorts. Halilović and Veljan (2021) find that respondents aged 18–35 express higher levels of acceptance of violence, while earlier qualitative research suggests that youth who did not experience the ethnically heterogeneous society of Yugoslavia are more likely to adopt ethnonationalist attitudes (Hvidemose, 2010). Notably, even adolescents too young to remember the war actively reproduce ethnonationalist symbols and narratives, indicating the

persistence of intergenerational transmission of identity-based grievances. Comparative evidence suggests little change in these patterns between 2010 and 2021, underscoring the durability of youth vulnerability to extremist messaging.

Digital environments further intensify these risks. Studies show that online media play a significant role in shaping radical views among young people, amplifying exclusionary narratives and facilitating exposure to extremist content (Suraya and Mulyana, 2020). Combined with economic frustration and social marginalisation, these dynamics increase susceptibility to push and pull factors associated with ethnonationalist mobilisation. Hvidemose (2010) reports widespread concern among practitioners that youth increasingly reproduce ethnic divisions and nationalist discourse, particularly as unemployment and social frustration disproportionately affect younger generations.

Civil society organisations are therefore central to youth-focused prevention efforts. CSOs are uniquely positioned to provide alternative spaces for belonging, civic engagement, and critical reflection that counteract both offline and online radicalisation pathways. Family influence remains a decisive factor in shaping youth attitudes, with household environments identified as the strongest contributor to susceptibility to ethnonationalism and radicalisation (Hvidemose, 2010). By working with families, schools, and local communities, CSOs can address these dynamics holistically—combining digital literacy, critical thinking, and inclusive identity formation to reduce the appeal of extremist narratives among young people.

Digital Literacy, Propaganda, and the Media

As with Salafist recruitment, online spaces are central to the dissemination of ethnonationalist narratives and the mobilisation of supporters (Perry, 2021). Digital platforms facilitate incremental radicalisation through self-reinforcing content dynamics, in which users are exposed to increasingly extreme material as a result of networked and algorithmic amplification (Madryha et al., 2022). These processes extend beyond explicitly extremist spaces and intersect with broader media ecosystems.

Traditional media also plays a significant role in shaping ethnonationalist discourse. Hvidemose (2010) documents how politically influenced and selectively framed reporting has contributed to the reproduction of ethnic divisions in Bosnia, with inter-ethnic incidents often exaggerated to sustain fear while examples of cooperation and coexistence receive limited attention. Such media practices reinforce polarising narratives and normalise exclusionary interpretations of social conflict.

Civil society organisations are therefore critical actors in contesting dominant narratives across both digital and traditional media. By partnering with independent media outlets, CSOs can foster public discussion around far-right discourse and expose the mechanisms through which ethnonationalist narratives are constructed and circulated (Halilović and Veljan, 2021). Civil society also plays a central role in generating and amplifying alternative narratives that foreground historical periods of coexistence and shared social experience, challenging revisionist accounts that underpin extremist mobilisation (Williams, 2019).

Effective intervention further requires accessible and credible communication strategies to counter disinformation, conspiracy theories, and hate speech. CSOs are uniquely positioned to translate complex historical and political issues into clear, locally resonant messages that strengthen public resilience to manipulation and reduce the appeal of exclusionary narratives (Halilović and Veljan, 2021).

Legal Reform

Bosnia and Herzegovina was the first state in the Western Balkans to criminalise participation in paramilitary and para-police formations through Article 162b of the Criminal Code (Official Gazette No. 47/14). While this represents an important legal precedent, existing frameworks require further expansion to address contemporary forms of right-wing extremism. Civil society organisations play a critical role in advancing this agenda by monitoring implementation gaps, documenting emerging extremist practices, and advocating for the consistent prosecution of hate speech and incitement to violence in cooperation with the police and judiciary (Halilović and Veljan, 2021). As comparative research suggests, adaptive and innovative legal instruments are essential to counter evolving extremist mobilisation strategies (Burchett et al., 2022).

Legal reform should extend beyond paramilitary activity to encompass right-wing extremist organisations more broadly, including those that mobilise through ideological programmes, public messaging, and non-violent but exclusionary activities that contribute to radicalisation and social polarisation (Halilović and Veljan, 2021). In this context, CSOs are particularly well positioned to provide evidence-based assessments of how extremist actors operate below the threshold of overt violence, ensuring that legislation remains responsive without undermining civil liberties.

These reforms must be embedded within a comprehensive strategic framework. The Strategy of Bosnia and Herzegovina for the Prevention and Combating of Terrorism (2021–2026) acknowledges the persistent threat posed by ethnic and national extremism and recognises its destabilising impact on both domestic and regional security, including its frequent entanglement with religious narratives. Aligning legal reform with updated counterterrorism strategies that explicitly address political, ethnonationalist, and religious radicalisation is therefore essential (European Commission, 2022). Importantly, the Strategy recognises civil society as a key actor in combating extremism and fostering social resilience. This acknowledgement underscores the need to move beyond state-centric approaches by institutionalising CSO participation in prevention, monitoring, and resilience-building efforts alongside legal enforcement mechanisms.

Recommendations

Drawing on the literature and the empirical findings of this study, the following recommendations outline how civil society organisations (CSOs) can more effectively address ethnonationalist radicalisation in Bosnia and Herzegovina by adapting lessons from Salafist counter-radicalisation efforts. Taken together, these recommendations emphasise CSOs'

distinctive capacity to intervene at the level of identity, community, and narrative—areas where state-led approaches are often least effective.

First, CSOs should prioritise sustained inter-group dialogue as a core mechanism for countering ethnonationalism. Evidence from Bosnia demonstrates that regular, meaningful contact across ethnic lines reduces support for violence, increases openness to reconciliation, and weakens exclusionary narratives, even among individuals who hold ethnonationalist views. By convening Bosniaks, Croats, and Serbs in structured dialogue and joint community initiatives, CSOs can address grievances and historical narratives without securitisation or ethnic segmentation.

Second, CSOs should actively engage religious communities in education and awareness-raising initiatives that address the instrumentalisation of religion by far-right and ethnonationalist actors. Given the documented overlap between religious and political extremism in Bosnia, partnerships with religious leaders and institutions—particularly through mechanisms such as the Interreligious Council—are essential for challenging exclusionary narratives while preserving religious freedom and community trust. Such engagement also protects religious communities from co-optation by extremist movements.

Third, women should be systematically integrated into prevention and intervention efforts, not merely as beneficiaries but as leaders and programme designers. The evidence presented in this paper demonstrates a strong relationship between patriarchal value systems and support for violence, alongside women's comparatively lower endorsement of extremist positions. CSOs are therefore well positioned to counter repatriarchalisation by promoting gender equality, supporting women's leadership, and leveraging women's roles in family and community cohesion as protective factors against radicalisation.

Fourth, CSOs should prioritise youth-focused programming that addresses both structural vulnerabilities and identity-based drivers of radicalisation. High unemployment, social exclusion, and intergenerational transmission of ethnonationalist narratives place young people at particular risk. Effective CSO interventions should combine civic engagement, critical thinking, and alternative forms of belonging, while also engaging families and schools to address the broader social environments in which youth attitudes are formed.

Fifth, CSOs should expand digital literacy and media engagement initiatives to counter online radicalisation and narrative amplification. Given the central role of digital spaces in spreading ethnonationalist discourse, CSOs should partner with independent media to promote alternative narratives, challenge historical revisionism, and provide accessible responses to disinformation and conspiracy theories. Digital literacy programming should be tailored to different age groups, with particular emphasis on youth, while remaining embedded in broader community-based interventions.

Sixth, CSOs should play an active role in advancing and monitoring legal reforms related to extremism. This includes advocating for the consistent prosecution of hate speech and incitement to violence, as well as contributing evidence and expertise to the development of legislation addressing right-wing extremist organisations. Collaboration with law enforcement and judicial institutions is essential, but CSOs also function as watchdogs, ensuring that legal measures remain proportionate, rights-based, and responsive to evolving extremist practices.

Finally, CSOs should be formally integrated into the development and implementation of national and regional strategies addressing radicalisation. As Bosnia and Herzegovina's counterterrorism framework increasingly recognises ethnonationalist extremism as a persistent threat, CSO participation is crucial for grounding strategy in local realities. Institutionalised collaboration between CSOs and relevant authorities can help ensure that prevention and resilience-building efforts address political, ethnonationalist, and religious radicalisation in a coherent and context-sensitive manner.

Taken together, these recommendations underscore the central argument of this paper: that civil society is not peripheral to countering ethnonationalism in Bosnia and Herzegovina, but essential to its long-term prevention. By adapting proven community-based approaches developed in response to Salafist radicalisation, CSOs can more effectively address the identity-based, relational, and narrative dimensions of ethnonationalist extremism, contributing to greater social cohesion and regional stability.

Limitations

This study has several limitations that warrant acknowledgement. First, much of the existing literature on radicalisation and counter-radicalisation continues to prioritise violent extremism, democratic destabilisation, and terrorism, with a particular empirical emphasis on Salafism. As a result, the conceptual tools and empirical benchmarks used in this paper are more developed for religious extremism than for ethnonationalism. While this imbalance motivates the paper's core contribution—extending insights from Salafist counter-radicalisation to ethnonationalist contexts—it also constrains the analytical depth with which ethnonationalism can be theorised as a distinct form of radicalisation.

Second, the focus on Bosnia and Herzegovina necessarily limits the generalisability of the findings. Bosnia's post-conflict setting, ethnically segmented political institutions, and distinctive history of coexistence and violence shape both radicalisation pathways and the role of civil society in ways that may not translate directly to other regional or political contexts. While Bosnia provides a critical case for examining the interaction between religious and ethnonationalist extremism, caution is required when applying these findings to other societies with different historical trajectories, institutional arrangements, or patterns of identity mobilisation.

Third, while the paper identifies a set of civil society-led practices that appear effective in addressing ethnonationalist radicalisation, it does not fully explore the practical and political constraints associated with their implementation. Factors such as uneven institutional capacity, donor dependence, political resistance, and community mistrust may significantly shape the feasibility and sustainability of these interventions. Future research would benefit from more systematic evaluation of implementation challenges, including comparative assessments of why certain programmes succeed or fail in specific local settings.

Fourth, the analysis does not comprehensively account for external influences on radicalisation and prevention efforts in Bosnia and Herzegovina. Geopolitical dynamics, international interventions, transnational funding streams, and regional political developments may all shape

local radicalisation processes and civil society responses in ways that exceed the scope of this study. A fuller understanding of how domestic and international factors interact would strengthen analysis of prevention and de-radicalisation in post-conflict contexts.

More broadly, this study is situated within an ongoing scholarly debate regarding the drivers and processes of radicalisation. Despite extensive research, there remains no consensus on the relative weight of ideological, structural, relational, and individual factors in explaining why individuals engage in violent extremism or affiliate with extremist organisations. As Vergani et al. (2020) note, future research should further disentangle the interaction between push, pull, and personal factors across both cognitive and behavioural dimensions of radicalisation, with closer attention to how these dynamics vary across local contexts.

Finally, this paper treats civil society primarily as a preventive and resilience-building force, but this framing carries its own limitations. Civil society is not inherently liberal or pro-democratic and may itself become a vehicle for ethnonationalism, populism, or exclusionary politics. As Cossà et al. (2021) caution, civil society actors can propagate radical and xenophobic narratives when embedded in polarised political environments. Recognising this ambivalence is essential for avoiding overly normative assumptions about the role of civil society and for developing more nuanced approaches to engaging CSOs in counter-radicalisation efforts.

Conclusion

This article has examined the dynamics of radicalisation in Bosnia and Herzegovina by integrating insights from radicalisation scholarship with interpretive frameworks, political anthropology, and political ethnography. By foregrounding local perspectives on right-wing ethnonationalist radicalisation, the analysis demonstrates that radicalisation is best understood as a context-dependent process shaped by the interaction of push, pull, and personal factors operating at both cognitive and behavioural levels. Attending to these interactions is essential for designing prevention and de-radicalisation strategies that are socially legitimate, locally resonant, and sustainable.

The central contribution of this study is to demonstrate the indispensable role of civil society organisations in long-term prevention, disengagement, and de-radicalisation. The findings show that personal relationships, community embeddedness, and locally grounded engagement are not ancillary to counter-radicalisation efforts but constitute their core mechanisms. Civil society actors are uniquely positioned to address identity formation, belonging, and narrative construction—key drivers of radicalisation that cannot be effectively managed through securitised or state-centric approaches alone.

Crucially, this paper argues that counter-radicalisation strategies developed in response to Salafist extremism in Bosnia and Herzegovina are transferable to efforts addressing right-wing ethnonationalism. This transferability does not rest on ideological equivalence, but on shared underlying mechanisms of radicalisation, including exclusionary identity construction, grievance mobilisation, and the social reinforcement of “us versus them” narratives. As such, the study challenges the tendency to compartmentalise counter-radicalisation by ideology and instead advances a more integrated, mechanism-focused approach.

The analysis underscores the value of community-based solutions that operate across ideological divides. Inter-group and interfaith dialogue, the cultivation of critical thinking skills, and sustained investment in civil society capacity emerge as indispensable components of effective prevention and de-radicalisation programming. These approaches are particularly salient in post-conflict contexts such as Bosnia and Herzegovina, where ethnonationalist narratives remain deeply embedded in social and political life and continue to shape patterns of mobilisation.

The next stage of this research will extend these findings through an in-depth qualitative and quantitative examination of civil society organisations engaged with issues of ethnonationalism. By analysing their objectives, practices, and constraints, future research will assess the extent to which existing initiatives align with the evidence-based recommendations developed in this study and identify conditions that enable or hinder effective civil society intervention.

This article contributes to terrorism and radicalisation scholarship by reframing ethnonationalism as a form of radicalisation that is amenable to established counter-radicalisation approaches and by positioning civil society as a central pillar of prevention and social resilience. By demonstrating the adaptability of community-based strategies across ideological contexts, the study offers both a conceptual and practical framework for addressing ethnonationalist extremism in Bosnia and beyond.

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Near-home bias, territorial stigmatization and Eurocentrism in country-risk assessments for FDI allocation

Aleksey Domanov¹

Abstract:

The given study provides an analysis of FDI network dynamics after coronavirus outbreak. Shares of FDI stock from individual nation-states to separate country-level destinations have been analysed by computing local indicators of spatial association (LISA).

FDI near-home bias has been identified in the IMF Coordinated Direct Investment Survey results. It could explain divergence investment allocation to various countries after coronavirus outbreak (leading to temporary self-isolation of many economies).

Moreover, this non-uniform distribution of FDI changes between 2020 and 2021 was found to have cluster patterns beyond first-order neighbours. In particular, many European countries received increasing FDI share from economies located at the other side of their continent, at the same time these investors took their capital out of most non-European countries.

These clusters could persist in many cases due to institutional and cultural considerations factored into investors' decision-making, which could lead to territorial stigmatization. Reasons for this willingness to finance projects located in neighboring countries could include political stability, which communicate confidence to capital holders.

Keywords:

LISA (local indicators of spatial association), FDI network, near-home bias, portfolio adjustment, territorial stigmatization, coronavirus restrictions, Coordinated Direct Investment Survey, clustering, qualculation, decision-making.

¹ Research Fellow, Center for the Studies of Ethnic Politics at the Department of European Integration Research, Institute of Europe, Russian Academy of Sciences
domanov.aleksey@gmail.com

Introduction

In contemporary post-scarcity attention economy (especially during overproduction crises periods) there is abundance of foreign direct investment (FDI) variants for an investor: he or she could direct money to various assets worldwide — all the funds to the same «basket» or diversify his or her portfolio.

From attention economy point of view, one could regard FDI assignment process around the world as investors stopping their selection on some country set. By allocating capital to addressees deemed worthy of attention financial institutions reveal their preference for these destinations.

Remaining important to many phenomena, preferences play especially decisive role in the context of «reshoring» policies pursued by many developed countries. These state efforts target investors' behavior, so relevant measures could include stimulating transnational companies to reindustrialize European and American territories instead of maintaining facilities overseas.

Along with static preferences, it would be important to analyze their dynamics after impactful events. For instance, a shift in FDI preferences could be witnessed after coronavirus outbreak, because the pandemic restrictions reshaped global value chains and made companies redefine their strategies of international presence. In particular, some firms reevaluated the usefulness of various modes of market entry, including investment in domestic or nearby facilities (as compared to FDI to developing countries and exporting goods from there to consumers in a domestic country).

Although this dynamic is heterogenous, some regularity could exist in FDI rebalancing after coronavirus outbreak. The given study attempts at finding a spatial structure in outward investment stock changes and provide some examples of these patterns.

Network view of FDI

This type of phenomena could be studied more thoroughly if situated in a network model, so many scholars adopted the network perspective on FDI (Bolívar, Casanueva, Castro 2019; Chin-Lung, Wen-Chang 2009; Damgaard, Elkjaer 2017; De Masi, Ricchiuti 2020; Gorgoni, Amighini, Smith 2018; Koskinen, Caimo, Lomi 2015; Rytter Sunesen, Jeppesen, Theilgaard, Kristensen, Grunfelder 2018). From this point of view flows in a graph represent summarized transactions between investors and destination object or investment project.

Usually in international statistics this description methodology is used at the country level: investment transactions are aggregated into international flows (along the edges of this graph) and all the investors from a domestic economy are united into one FDI source node. On the other side of an edge investments received are also summarized into a single value, which characterizes a sink node - FDI inflow.

Fig. 1. Outward FDI stock from France registered by the OECD.

Fig. 2. Outward FDI stock from Germany registered by the OECD.

E.g. this network approach has been practiced by the OECD data collectors (OECD Data n.d.). In particular, this database allows for computing the share of the overall FDI outflow stock from a source country — this could be operationalized as edge weight in this network. For instance, shares of multiple destinations (although limited to OECD members number) in French and German FDI stock could be visualized as follows (Fig. 1 and 2):

Having taken a closer look at FDI share distribution among destinations, one could notice that some pattern exists in outward FDI: investors prefer allocating money to one set of countries over another. For instance, FDI outflows from France and Germany are distributed unevenly around the world (aforementioned Fig 1 and 2), and investors' preference for nearby countries (respectively, Italy or Belgium, and Austria or Denmark) is noticeable. This relatively high willingness to invest geographically close to domestic economy, was observed in many cases and called "near-home bias" (Muradoglu, Levis, Vasileva 2010).

Deeper analysis of FDI networks would include exploration of *dynamics* in investment flows after an event, one could expect FDI rebalancing. One of the reasons for this expectation is that similar dynamics has been observed during contagion modeling in interbank financial networks (Elliott, Golub, Jackson 2014; Markose, Oluwasegun, Giansante, 2012; Dungey, Harvey, Volkov 2019) after a money supply shock in the domestic country (e.g. an urgent need to cover other obligations with the funds allocated abroad, i.e. taking money out of overseas projects in order to pay current expenses). As for FDI (not limited to interbank transactions) share, this liquidity stress will result in lower ratio of the overall FDI outflow stock from this donor country.

Fig. 3 and 4. Shares of outward FDI stock made by investors from Germany and France

Following this logic, dynamic perspective could formally presuppose taking post-event deltas — in this case, edges before and after event impact. For researching coronavirus effects the following could be compared: FDI in 2020 against 2021.

Separate edges transformation could also be studied with the OECD database. Like in previous static case, studying edge weights would be a usual step while describing relation *dynamics* between countries. For instance, the relative importance of some German and French investment partners (Fig. 3 and 4) has indeed changed considerably.

Similarly to static case, FDI dynamics from the same country to various destinations diverge considerably. This allocation divergence could be attributed to the aforementioned near-home bias. Mental classification of countries into «near» and «distant» could lead to reticence to close projects in contiguous economies, while pulling resources out of countries on other continents. E.g. this pattern could be traced on the percentile map of Belgian investments (Fig. 5 below).

Clustering in addition to near-home bias

Besides near-home bias, there is more regularity in this non-uniform distribution: investors from some countries demonstrate patterns adding to this near-home bias. Common approach to identifying this structure would be looking for clusters.

Clustering of countries having rising FDI shares (colored in red on subsequent diagrams) would suggest, that their region got preferred rank as a result of investors' "qualculation" process (see «conventions school» of Boltanski, Thevenot and Callon on socially-determined quality evaluation (Boltanski, Thévenot 1991; Callon, Méadel, Rabeharisoa 2002). Capital holders from numerous countries clustered their preferences in Europe, thus revealing Eurocentric focus in their activities.

On the contrary, economies deviating from some standards (accepted by investors) get bad assessments and therefore have decreased FDI share and consequently are located out of this «positive» cluster. Moreover, if these destinations form a cluster with surrounded countries (colored in blue on subsequent diagrams), this similarity could hint a categorization of this whole geographic zone as unattractive (e.g. due to unreliability) and not worthy of investor's attention and resources — some locations could be deemed «territorially stigmatized» (Wacquant, Slater, Pereira 2014).

A suitable algorithm for this approach is LISA (Anselin 1995) — processing local indicators of spatial association for overlaid variables' values on a world map. In order to identify regions in the world with statistically high dependence in neighboring countries the following formula was applied:

$$L = \frac{N}{\sum_j \sum_j w_{ij}} \frac{\sum_i \sum_j w_{ij} (z_i - \bar{z})(z_j - \bar{z})}{\sum_i (z_i - \bar{z})^2}$$

where N is the number of cells/partitions, z_i is the calculated indicator for the cell i , w_{ij} is an estimate of spatial weights reflecting whether i and j are neighbors, such that if they are not, it is equal to zero, and if they are equal to $\frac{1}{|\delta_i|}$, where $|\delta_i|$ is the number of neighboring cells i .

The local indications of spatial association were mapped for the countries with indicators of a level of significance of the p-value at less than 0,05. The given method reveals four types of local clusters: *high-high* is a cluster of spatial autocorrelation of high values in neighboring countries (colored in red on the diagrams below), *low-low* is a cluster of spatial autocorrelation of low values in neighboring countries, *high-low* are the items of high values, appearing in the neighborhood of cluster of low values, *low-high* are the items of low values, appearing in the neighborhood of cluster of high values.

Clustering methods (e.g. the one used during LISA computation), require information about more edges of the worldwide network than provided by the OECD dataset used on previous stages of our study. We should move from analyzing edges set of an individual node (directions of FDI from a country) to revising relations between destination nodes: this technique would allow for completing the connectivity graph with data about non-OECD states as well as OECD members.

In order to move from OECD-limited to the worldwide network, a suitable dataset could be provided by the IMF-made Coordinated Direct Investment Survey (CDIS). This source provides connectivity matrices updated annually, so it is feasible to calculate the change between reported FDI stocks of country i in country j in 2020 and 2021 — like OECD statistics on Fig. 3 and 4 above could be interpreted as increments. This variable should be operationalized as the difference between absolute FDI stock addressed to country j in 2021 vs. 2020, which is taken relative to the overall reported FDI stock (divided by the sum of investments to all the countries).

Before looking for clusters it is worth noticing that improved network connectivity data still allows for finding structures, which do not necessarily form a cluster — e.g. the aforementioned near-home bias judging by links to immediate neighbours of country i . Indeed, the CDIS data makes us believe that near-home bias exists for the variable operationalized above: it will be shown further together with clusters.

Fig. 5 and 6 Increase in shares of Belgian outward FDI stock (percentile map and LISA of IMF CDIS)

Clustering supplementary to the "near-home bias" consequence is demonstrated on Fig. 5 and 6. According to these diagrams, shares of nearby countries in Belgian FDI stock changed mostly in accordance with "near-home bias" hypothesis (increased in contiguous Germany and France). Besides the percentile map, LISA diagram emphasizes that to the North-East from Belgium these shares grew in more FDI destinations, highlighting that in Denmark this value increased along with nearby Norway and Germany.

Fig. 7. Increase in shares of Portuguese outward FDI stock, LISA of IMF CDIS

The largest zone of preferred FDI allocation has been found also visible to the North-East from Portugal (Fig. 7). At the same time, Portuguese investors didn't pay growing attention to Mahreb countries (even though they are located closer than the UK or Denmark).

Conclusion

Not only was FDI near-home bias found several years ago, but also it was identified in FDI destinations rebalancing dynamics after a major event (coronavirus outbreak leading to temporary self-isolation of many economies). This bias could explain divergence in resources allocated to or pulled out of various countries.

Moreover, this uneven distribution of FDI changes between 2020 and 2021 was found to be moderated by cluster patterns spreading beyond first-order neighbours (e.g. many European countries got increasing FDI share from economies located at the other side of their continent).

These clusters could persist in many cases due to institutional and cultural considerations factored into investors' decision-making, which could lead to territorial stigmatization. Reasons for this willingness to finance projects located in neighboring countries could include political stability, which communicate confidence to capital holders.

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Adoption of the Nordic Balance Model, as a Security Regime in Ukraine

Arie Leo Geronik¹

Abstract

For a suggested solution of the ongoing war in Eastern Europe to be viable, it must meet the security needs of Russia, Ukraine and the separatist regions of Luhansk and Donetsk simultaneously. To achieve this, we must alter our point of view and widen our perspective so that the entire European continent will be included.

Such a way of thinking which contributed to the security in Northern Europe throughout the Cold War, and which can be reproduced in Eastern Europe is the "Nordic Balance" model. In this framework, the USSR was on one side, the NATO-member Scandinavian countries were on the other and neutral Finland and Sweden were in the middle, serving as buffer states. **Thus, becoming regional powers,** who serve as a **stabilizing factor** in the sub – system.

In Eastern Europe, for reasons that will be clear in the course of this paper, Russia can assume the role of the USSR on one pole, the West European NATO member countries, can play the part of Denmark and Norway on the other, and Ukraine and the regions of Luhansk and Donetsk can serve as buffer states, taking the role of Sweden and Finland, thus becoming the hearth of the model.

The mutual dependence arising from such a situation, the fact that each country safeguards the neutrality of the other, **is what ensures stability.**

Keywords:

International Relations, Regional Stability, Balance of Power, Europe, War, Ukraine, Scandinavia

¹ The Open University of Israel
Tel Aviv University

A new perspective

During the Vietnam war, Secretary of Defense Robert S. McNamara was asked by his generals to authorize additional troops, based on their belief that two decades of experience in Vietnam would assure victory. McNamara countered that, far from accumulating twenty years of experience, the US had simply repeated one year's worth of mistakes for twenty years.

Similarly, those who look with equal parts of optimism and frustration at years of failed peace initiatives between Russia and Ukraine are ignoring the fact that each "new" plan has been nothing more than a repetition of past unsuccessful efforts.

The Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022 substantially undermined the security situation extant in Europe since the Second World War. With the ongoing potential for escalation between Russia and the West, developments force states to calculate new routes in a changing reality.

History teaches that small states cannot take their survival for granted. For example Athens decreed that Melos should be wiped out, despite the islands efforts to stay out of the Peloponnesian War. Other small states, in more recent history, such as Estonia, Czechoslovakia and Kuwait suffered at the hands of large, threatening neighbors, sometimes to the point of loss of territory or independence or even destruction (Feldman 2023).

The small state will try, in these circumstances, to encourage its rivals to adopt international norms, rules and laws, join institutions and embed democratic values and patterns and market economy in its rival's society and regime to advance mutual dependence. In other words, the small state will ascribe a central role to soft power in its security strategy and rely less on military strength, and will try in this manner to moderate the aggressiveness of its neighbor peacefully (Keohane & Nye, 1977; Miller,2010; Neumann & Gstohl, 2006; Nye,2002; Rosecrance, 1986; Russell,2020). Sometimes a small state will use soft power to position itself as a leading actor in

international organizations and institutions, form small state coalitions in order to leverage their collective influence and widen their room for maneuver (Chong,2010; Nye,2009; Pape, 2005; Rickli, 2008). Against the balance of threat theory, Kiev sought to reduce the danger it faced from its neighbor by bringing Moscow closer to Europe through soft power, at a time when the environment changed at the end of the Cold War and Moscow was relatively weak.

On the other hand, when a great power is equipping its military, especially when it uses belligerent means to harm the sovereignty of an ally or neighbor or takes unilateral steps that violate international norms and law, these measures signal its

aggressive intentions. In accordance with the perception of intentions component of the balance of threat theory, the small state will realize under these conditions that it has reduced room for maneuver. Its threat perception will thus become more severe. Alongside cultivating its military strength, it will pursue a policy of assertive diplomacy, which includes imposing legal, institutional and normative restrictions on the threatening power with the aim of reducing the latter's overall superiority, harming its international legitimacy, and restraining it (Feldman 2023).

For a suggested solution of the ongoing East European conflict and war to be viable, it must meet the security needs of Russia, the NATO member European States and those of Ukraine simultaneously. To achieve this, we must alter our point of view, widen our perspective so that the entire European continent will be included and to seek for a solution that will be based on balance of power.

The term **balance of power** refers to the general concept of one or more states' power being used to balance that of another state or group of states. According to this way of thinking, in the anarchy of the international system, the most reliable brake on the power of one state, is the power of other states. Balance of power can refer to any ratio of power capabilities between states or alliances, or it can mean only a relatively equal ratio. Alternatively, balance of power can refer to the process by which counterbalancing coalitions have repeatedly formed in history to prevent one state from conquering an entire region.(Goldstein & Prevehouse;2010).

The theory of balance of power argues that such counterbalancing occurs regularly and maintains the stability of the international system. The system is stable in that its rules and principles stay the same: state sovereignty does not collapse into a universal empire. It is important to emphasize however, that this stability does not imply peace. It is rather a stability maintained by means of recurring wars that adjust power relations.

Such a way of thinking which contributed to the security of Northern Europe throughout the Cold War and which can be reproduced in the eastern part of the continent now, is the "Nordic Balance" model. In this framework, the USSR was on one side, the NATO member Scandinavian countries were on the other and neutral Finland and Sweden were in the middle, serving as buffer states. Thus becoming regional powers, who serve as stabilizing factor in the sub- system.

Sweden and Finland together constituted a kind of international strategic vacuum in the grey zone between the blocks, and as in nature, so too in international politics, a vacuum is a condition which has a tendency to be filled. This state of affairs turned these two states into mutually dependent "Siamese twins", where any change in the geopolitical status of one, would immediately result in a change in the geopolitical situation of the other. Possible scenarios at the time, could have been, for example, a Soviet invasion of Finland resulting from Sweden's increasing ties with NATO, or

Sweden joining NATO in reaction of Finland coming closer to the Eastern block, or one of the two becoming an isolated buffer state, an impossible situation on the long run.

The mutual dependence arising from such a situation, the fact that each country safeguards the neutrality of the other, **is what ensures stability.**

in Eastern Europe today, as in Scandinavia during the post-war era, one can find a geostrategic reality which prefers a situation in which two neighboring political entities are bonded together as neutrals between two blocks.

Since it is not unrealistic to assume that the faith of the separatist regions of Eastern Ukraine – Luhansk and Donetsk – whether as an independent entity or in some autonomous custom will be discussed as part of a permanent settlement (**I.A. in order to prevent humiliating Russia**), we can find here too as in Scandinavia during the Cold War, a situation consisted of two political entities between two rival blocks.

In East Europe, Ukraine can fulfill the role of Sweden in the Scandinavian sub-system, and the separatist region – the role of Finland.

The significant political change that must take place in Eastern Europe, if the intention is to adopt the Nordic Balance model, will be characterized by the turning of Ukraine and the future separatist region into neutral entities.

Neutrality is perceived as an attractive policy for small nations, which, because of their strategic location or symbolic political values, stand or may stand in the focus of a struggle for influence or control by regional or global rivals. The neutral state is a country whose political independence and territorial integrity enjoy the permanent recognition of the superpowers, provided that the neutral country does not use weapons against another country except for self-defense and does not enter into contractual obligations with any party that might endanger its status.

The object of neutrality is to preserve international order, to reduce tensions in the system and to bring international disputes to a solution based on agreed norms and institutions. From the point of view of the neutral state, the objective of neutrality is to defend its military security as well as preserve its political and territorial integrity. From the standpoint of the nations bordering the neutral state, the object of neutrality is to preserve the balance of power from being violated.

A distinction which is particularly apposite in this case is the division of neutrality into positive and negative aspects. The positive aspect in the policy of neutrality denotes the complex attempts made by neutral states to make their neutrality as attractive as possible to the contesting sides. This aspect incorporates a series of political measures carried out simultaneously on two planes: one, measures intended

to reduce fears of the contending sides regarding possible damage that might be caused to them by the neutrality of the small country; two – steps intended to strengthen their interest to continue to preserve neutrality.

The negative aspect of neutralist policy refers to deterring the contending sides from violating neutrality by convincing them that the price they would have to pay for such a step will be high. Such deterrence is based on military power.

Since this division is hypothetical, it would be more correct to distinguish between "negative – positive" neutrality, which puts the emphasis first on military deterrence and only afterwards on political reliability, and "positive – negative" neutrality which first underlines reliability and only then deterrence. This is precisely the distinction between the neutrality of Sweden and Finland, respectively. The same distinction would apply to Ukraine and the separatist regions of Luhansk and Donetsk, also respectively.

Contrary to Scandinavia, where neutrality can be defined as traditional neutrality, an attribute of which is freedom of choice, the more appropriate term for the neutrality applicable to Eastern Europe would be neutralization, in the context of which neutrality would be imposed on the state by means of international agreements. The outstanding characteristic of such a nation is that it is not neutral out of choice and, accordingly, cannot change its status according to its own wishes. In Eastern Europe, so filled with suspicions, this would somehow contribute to stability.

It is important to mention that neutrality is not an ideological asset: both Finland and Sweden in Northern Europe, and Austria and Switzerland in Central Europe, even as neutral states, belonged ideologically clearly to the western block.

The main difference between the "Nordic Balance" model and the intention to neutralize Ukraine as part of a future settlement - as has been suggested-is that in Eastern Europe we are referring to a sole neutral state as a buffer between the west and Russia. As we can learn from history (that of Poland during the 20:th century for example), that is not a desirable situation in the long run, since all of the borders of the neutral buffer state, are thus confrontational.

Dyads of neutrals between rival blocks, gives each of them the status of rim – states, instead of buffer – states.

As mentioned before, even since the fate of the separatist regions of Eastern Ukraine is not clear yet, it should be noted that the question of the preferences regarding the future of these areas as a sovereign state or as something less, within the context of a federation or confederation with Ukraine are irrelevant. An examination of recent processes in the international context, especially in Europe in the post cold war era, show that the question of "nationalism" or "supra-

nationalism" is a function of political development; in the modern era, the future seems to lie in the systems of blocks, provided that these are freely chosen (otherwise we're talking about colonialism). In order to achieve political unity of either kind, as in Western Europe for example or as East and West Ukraine confederation proposals advocate, a relatively homogenous group of sovereign states with many years of sovereignty is required. Assets, including sovereignty, cannot be relinquished unless they exist. The cases of former Soviet Union and Yugoslavia show what can be expected when an attempt is made to shorten these developmental processes by skipping over the initial stage of sovereignty. Introducing such a Trojan horse into our backyard would be unwise.

In connection with the different shades of neutrality, as also mentioned before, here too the Nordic case can serve as a model for what can be implemented in Eastern Europe. In addition, the Soviet – Finnish border corrections as well as restrictions regarding the size and quality of the Finnish army determined in bilateral Soviet – Finnish agreements can serve as precedents.

Advantages

This proposal, seems to be advantageous to all parties involved: Russia will safeguard her security interests in the west and achieve regional and international recognition regarding these interests. Luhansk and Donetsk will gain independence anchored in international agreements. Ukraine will achieve international standing and a national role similar to that of Sweden during the cold war. She will become a rim state instead of a buffer state, while protecting her global and regional interests. The entire region will gain stability, even without a clear solution to the East – West tension. This will be achieved thanks to the existence of a subsystem composed of nations, which balance one another, with a dyad of two neutral countries in between, serving together as a regional buffer power.

"Peace by balance" to quote Raymond Aaron.

One of the known obstacles that prevent a successful move from a state of hostility to a state of peace lay in the necessity to change negative attitudes, beliefs and values concerning the opposite side. Paradoxically, the best way to achieve this goal, is by living in peace with each other but one will not do that, prior to these attitude changes. By adopting the framework recommended here, the parties can sign a formal agreement, based on stability, and later, turn to attitude changes by establishing sorts of "Truth and reconciliation committees".

In a speech President Kennedy delivered in the summer of 1963, he mentioned I.A., as a lesson from the Cuban Missile Crisis, less than a year before, that in the nuclear

age, adversaries should avoid situations that might put their rivals before a choice between a humiliating retreat or nuclear war. He added that adopting such a policy in the nuclear age, would be only a sign of the bankruptcy of our policy or a collective death wish of the world.

The world – so it seems – is ripe for a new Kennedy.

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PANEL V

GEOPOLITICAL METHODS AND ANALYSES

Chair: Heriberto Cairo

Discussant: Igor Okunev

Integrating Olavo de Carvalho's concepts and method in Geopolitical Studies

Nuno Morgado¹

Abstract

This chapter analyzes the contribution of the Brazilian philosopher Olavo de Carvalho to political science, integrating that contribution within geopolitical studies. In a time in which the Global South is slowly challenging the Anglo-Saxon hegemony by entering the academic debate, the exam of Carvalho's ideas and their pertinence to an innovative theoretic-methodological framework becomes relevant.

The aim of the paper is twofold: (1) it defines some of Carvalho's main concepts, such as political action, political and historical agent, consciousness horizon, revolutionary mentality, potential and power, intellectual hegemony, intentions and objectives, political network; and (2) it integrates these concepts into a quite innovative, probabilistic, dialectic, and phenomenological approach. In this context, some of Carvalho's received influences are mentioned, and his disregard for *grand* theories – in detriment of case studies – is explained.

Apart from the introduction to Carvalho's approach in the English language, the chapter also incorporates his conceptual and methodological framework into foreign policy and geopolitical studies developing, therefore, these research agendas.

Keywords

Geopolitical studies, State, Power, Agents, Concepts, Methods, Science

¹ CIAS, Corvinus University of Budapest. The author may be reached at nuno.morgado@uni-corvinus.hu A.M.D.G.

Introduction

The objective of this chapter is to abstractly verify whether Olavo de Carvalho's selected concepts and approach have relevance to geopolitical studies in its explanatory causal chain. To achieve that objective, the chapter (1) revises and explains some concepts of that author, and (2) analyzes his methodological approach. Books, articles, courses and seminars authored by Carvalho constitute the body of sources analyzed in this research piece.

The epistemological assumptions include a Christian setting in which a "relative scientific certainty" is possible, and that an objective-descriptive political science, is chosen in detriment of a normative-prescriptive one.

Carvalho's selected concepts with relevance to geopolitical studies

Located *a priori* the scientific method itself, metatheoretical aspects are, however, crucial for the scientific method, as metatheoretical aspects constitutes the ground in which the building of the scientific method is instituted. Principles – initial assumptions that forms any basis – constitute benchmarks within the mentioned metatheoretical aspects. I could systematize three principles in Carvalho's approach (some of which, carry methodological consequences *ab initio*).

First, the rejection of "any aims toward a perfect society" (Carvalho 2016a), which implies the detachment from any ideological commitments. Carvalho recovers the old Aristotelian distinction between the "discourse of the agent" and the "discourse of the scientist". The first one aims to produce effects, whereas the second aims to understand and to explain phenomena. Some of the problems at the Academia today come from the fact that this dualism has been forgotten and, thus, many academics became more political activists than researchers.

Second, the rejection of "any ethnocentric and chronocentric prejudices" (Carvalho 2016a). Whereas the former is relatively overcome, the latter is very much rooted in our societies, namely through the belief that our time is "the best" in human history. The recipe to overcome both these prejudices is to absorb the largest number of perspectives – from historical time and civilizational spaces – in order to broaden the consciousness horizon, a concept that will be subject of analysis in a posterior sub-section. In addition, deculturation (Carvalho, 2016b), meaning a process in which one leaves his own culture, is necessary to be able to observe that culture and other cultures from different angles with more freedom.

A third principle would be that "there is no action without an agent". This notion brings the research to the problem of identifying agents in politics and in history.

Political Agent and Historical Agent

Carvalho defined *human action* as “a deliberate intervention in a certain state of things” – either to change (action) or to stop a change (reaction) (Carvalho 2019). A *political action* is a human action that “impacts entire societies”. Finally, a *historical action* is (usually a political action) which “effects can be observed beyond the limits of the lifetime of the agent” (Carvalho 2016a). The historical action is irreversible (Carvalho 2016b). To stretch the effects of an action for such long-term, the continuity and unity of the agent are critical. For that reason, the agents owning those characteristics are only a few. Dynasties or influential families, the Catholic Church (with its apostolic succession) and similarly dominant religious organizations, esoteric societies (e.g., Freemasonry, Tariqas), or an uninterrupted political party or movement (e.g., the International Communist Movement) are acknowledged as historical agents, thus capable of historical action.

In this context, the state cannot be, therefore, considered an agent but rather an instrument, in the sense that the state is the *subject* of a royal dynasty, an esoteric society – even a terrorist organization – groups that are able to capture the state and rule through its structure of power, including its armed forces and all its remaining repressive apparatus.

Consciousness Horizon of the Political Agent

If to stand as an *agent* (either political or historical) unity is required, then that unity must be methodologically identified. The consciousness horizon – i.e., the mental nucleus that crystalizes what the agent knows and does not know – determines the direction of any *political action*. Hence, in the *consciousness horizon*, Carvalho identified the concept-source that, once being studied, unveils the centripetal unity that is required to identify an *agent*. To Carvalho, “conscious” is a “permanent integration effort, the search for unity beyond the immediate chaos. It is the unification of the diverse, and the resolution of contradictions” (Carvalho 2013, 178).

How to study the concept of consciousness horizon? A methodological necessity imposes itself before anything else – the researcher must necessarily have a broader consciousness horizon than the agent he is studying. Otherwise, he will not be able to grasp and make sense of his study object. Carvalho called this “intellectual hegemony” elsewhere (2016b). While examining the action of the agent – both in the timeline of history and also while observing the context of that action – the researcher is able to point out what fundamental elements the agent ignored, in case there were any. “The map of ignorance delimits the consciousness horizon” (Carvalho 2016a). The following deduction becomes unavoidable – in the situations which the agent does not understand or which elements he ignores, the agent will either possibly not take action at all or will act in an eminently fragmented way. This argument comes in line with the concept of *geomisguidance* that I coined earlier (Morgado 2016). Therefore, *geomisguidance* can be converted into one of the categories to determine the type of consciousness horizon of the agent.

In spite of the singular used form of *agent* – and as mentioned in the previous subsection – the agent can very well be a group of people. In that case, in order to reach the aimed conclusions, the methodological steps for investigation must be adapted from the study of a single person to the internal discussions inside those groups.

Lastly, two remaining ideas about the consciousness horizon. (1) The consciousness horizon appears as the mediator between the facts and the interpretation of those facts. (2) Like it happens with the means of action, also the consciousness horizon helps the researcher formulating scenarios about the real possibilities of political success.

Revolutionary Mentality

One of the types of mentality that Carvalho conceptualized to assist in the investigation of the consciousness horizon was the “revolutionary mentality”. He contended that the origins of the Revolutionary Movement, can be traced into a certain type of mentality or “structure of perception” that has been enduring on the path of History. He designated that structure of perception as “the Revolutionary Mentality”. The revolutionary mentality, Carvalho explained, is “a spiritual and psychological phenomenon, which, however, shows its most prominent expression in politics”. This revolutionary mentality is characterized by (a) a radical belief that an ideal better world is possible; (b) “a mechanism of retroactive justification”, meaning, “what I do now in my political actions – namely the concentration of power – I will unlikely justify in the uncertain future that no one knows about”; and finally (c) duplicity or multiplicity of justifications and tactics, i.e. doing something and its opposite at the same time. Both (b) and (c) are then ways to get to (a), the “better world” (Carvalho 2013, 228-236).

The revolutionary mentality, as a distortion of the notions of time and political limited action, created a brutal and irrational field for political action throughout History. Hitler, Lenin, Stalin, Pol Pot, Mao Zedong could easily illustrate the previous characterization of the revolutionary mentality. In this way, the revolutionary mentality can be identified in the line of time. What can be designated as a “revolutionary movement” was strengthened from the 16th century onwards, in successive steps gushing from the Protestant Reformation and the French Revolution to the October Revolution, Fascist, Anarchist movements, Nazi party, May 68, communist *guerilhas* and communist regimes, São Paulo Forum, etc. Therefore, it is crucial to clarify that the revolutionary movement is constituted by a unitary structure of perception, *i.e.*, the mentioned revolutionary mentality, a “self-conscious continuous phenomenon with a unitary character” as Carvalho stated, rather than by any ideological rigid and unique nature. In fact, the ideological flexibility is a key characteristic of the revolutionary movement, flowing from the revolutionary mentality. Knowing this gives a great help in assessing the relations, objectives, modalities of action of the revolutionary movement. Consequently, the

revolutionary movement is primarily defined by a specific *Weltanschauung* that produces political results.

Potential and Power

The means of action are indeed a predictive element as no *agent* is able to take an *action*, when he does not have the *means of action* to take that action. This assumption conveys the concepts of *potential* and *power* defined elsewhere (Morgado 2023). I have defined *potential* as *capabilities* or “*resources*”, which fits in the concept of Carvalho’s *means of action*. As for my and Carvalho’s definitions of *power*, they also align with the standard definition of power by political science, as a specific *ability* for action (i.e., an ability that produces effects and holds certain objectives). In a sentence: there is no *power* (ability) without *potential* (capabilities).

According to Carvalho, the difference of power (and potential, consequently) should be considered as one of the main problems of political science, as this problem might have not received all the attention it deserves. From all the animal kingdom, only human societies can have an abyssal difference of power (Carvalho 2016a). Two tigers, two camels, or two bulls would never differ much in their strength, while comparing the *power* of, for example, a gulag prisoner and a KGB general. This invincible fact on *difference of power* boils down to the difference of the *capabilities*, as mentioned. Yet, recapturing the concept of *political action*, Carvalho asserted that “politics is a power phenomenon, but it takes place within human societies only” (Carvalho 2019).

How to explain the origins of such variation in the capabilities? Carvalho (2016a) asserts that (a) the chronological factor and (b) the knowledge factor can help in explaining that difference. Regarding the former, the oldest and long-lasting agent will tend to have more power than a younger and less continuous one. This aspect links to the concept of geopolitical continuities (Morgado 2023, 14). Concerning the latter, the more information (namely intelligence) and technology an agent has, the more powerful he will be. This latter assumption is, logically, connected to the concept of consciousness horizon as well, contribution to make this theoretical approach even more solid.

The object of political science is, at last, delimited within the frame of the study of the means to conquer, maintain, and exercise *power* – which is the same to state “real connections between people”, characterized by the crucial concept of obedience (Carvalho 2019).

This *political power* (“ability”) may be categorized through three diverse types of operation. Firstly, the use of physical force, i.e., the capacity to either assassinate or cause physical damage (to torture, to maul, to threaten to do that, etc.). Secondly, to offer or to suppress advantages, such as money, or any sort of privileges. Thirdly, the mental and intellectual influence through ideas and cultural impact. The third one seems to be the most effective, but it works above all on the long-term,

consequently, the agent will not be around to collect the benefits of its achievements. The use of the physical force, by opposition, is the most immediate (Carvalho 2019).

Carvalho's phenomenological method

A central conundrum in Carvalho's method is attached to the features of the researcher himself (Carvalho 2016a). He raised two questions at this level. (1) Who can dedicate himself to study political science in a useful way? (2) What kind of cognitive, moral, and psychological qualities must one have to study political science?

Both questions emerge from the differences among natural sciences and social sciences. While in natural sciences, the collection of data happens through the five senses, as data is external to the researcher, in social sciences (and the same goes for humanities or liberal arts), however, all the data that the researcher has at his disposal was produced by the same means with which the researcher is also studying. In other words, the *data* and the *mental procedures* share the same source. It is certain that replication may eliminate the risks of too much phantasy and too little science. Nevertheless, that sharing directly requires (a) an openness to all the facts, and (b) an identification of the researcher with the agent under study. Again, ideology turns out to be an obstacle, as a highly ideological individual will be unable to identify himself with an ideology that he despises, therefore, failing in matching these requirements.

In this line, Carvalho added that (i) imagination, (ii) morality, and (iii) exclusion are necessary to conduct studies in political science. (i) Imagination for the necessary background in literature and arts, the cultural sphere (Carvalho 2016b), that must exist before science. (ii) Morality for the necessary compassion (until its limits) for the agent under study (compassion does not mean agreement and support). And (iii) exclusion as an imitation of Jesus Christ, excluded by the Jewish authorities. In spite of that exclusion, no resentment is to be shown and, therefore, a position located on the *outside* is created, an indispensable position with distance to observe those inside (Carvalho 2016a).

A specific method is always chosen to answer certain questions. To Carvalho, who is the agent? what are his objectives? what is his consciousness horizon? what are his means of action (potential)? therefore what can he do, and what can't he at all do? – should be the central questions to tailored the type of the method used and, in addition, to answer these question in real-world case studies – and not by general theories (Carvalho 2016a). To fill in the shell of a concept with real-life conditions that allow the reasoning of a concrete phenomenon, i.e., a much needed “materialization of an idea” is a permanent feature in the Brazilian philosopher's approach (Carvalho 2016a). Thus, to Carvalho, the material aspects are always more important than the discourse, as the material aspects directly produce results (Carvalho 2016b).

Carvalho's approach integrates his concepts (some of them defined in the previous section) into a quite innovative, probabilistic, dialectic, and phenomenological approach. To him, the accumulation of evidence to favor a particular hypothesis is not a scientific procedure. It is rather a rhetoric one to persuade an audience of something. Instead of that, a scientific procedure is to distinguish the possible from the impossible, exclude the latter and hierarchize the former (Carvalho 2008 2019).

In fact, forecasting is a major piece in Carvalho's approach. The joint investigation of the *consciousness horizon* and the *means of action* constitutes two essential methodological tasks for prediction in politics. In addition, the prediction will be as accurate as the researcher's precise capability in arranging the scenarios into a hierarchy of probabilities, as mentioned.

Finally, even if subsists in politics a quotient of unpredictability that must be borne in mind, as Carvalho – inspired by the classic political science author, Georg Jellinek – emphasized that the methods in political science require the distinction between (a) what is a result of a fortuitous accumulation of causes, and (b) what is the result of a plan and deliberation (Carvalho 2016a 2019) – and consequently the importance of identification and characterization of the *agent* in the making of such distinction returns – Carvalho asserted indeed that “the accurate forecast in social sciences resembles the certainty of the experimental tests in natural sciences” (Carvalho 2019).

Conclusion

To Olavo de Carvalho, political science is the application of the concepts of *agent*, *consciousness horizon of the agent*, *means of action* and its potentials, to make predictions according to a certain degree of possibility. In other words, the joint investigation of the *consciousness horizon* and the *means of action* constitutes two essential methodological tasks for prediction in politics, under the principle that “there is no action without an agent”.

As a matter of fact, Carvalho's methodological apparatus has been able to offer accurate predictions. Consequently, it has been going beyond being merely a conceptual body of limited empirical relevance. Future research will address his correct predictions.

According to Carvalho, for a successful activity in political science and geopolitical studies, the researcher must possess certain characteristics, namely, the researcher must necessarily have a broader consciousness horizon than the agent he is studying. Among other aspects, the revolutionary mentality was brought up. The revolutionary mentality, a radical structure of perception committed to “creating a better world”, favors concentration of political power and duplicity or multiplicity of justifications and tactics, in order to achieve that goal. The concept of revolutionary mentality is an instrument to study a political agent's consciousness horizon.

As for bridges and converging of knowledge, Carvalho's concepts are useful to geopolitical reasoning in terms of the concepts of *potential* and *geopolitical agent's perceptions and capacities* as causal variables of political action.

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Spatial Autoregression as a Means of Measuring Neighbourhood Effect in Latvian Parliamentary Elections

Lidia Zhirnova¹

Abstract

Neighbourhood effect as an independent voting factor was conceptualized back in late 1960-s in the works by D.R. Reynolds and K.R. Cox and was proved on a local level a decade later by R. Huckfeldt and J. Sprague. Nowadays it is possible to measure the neighbourhood effect nationwide by the means of spatial statistical analysis, using the spatial autoregressive model that adds a spatial lag to the list of independent variables. This approach was employed by I. Okunev to prove the significance of the neighbourhood effect at the 2016 US presidential elections. The current article used the same instrument to evaluate the neighbourhood effect at the Latvian Saeima elections in 2010-2022. Although the Latvian political and electoral system is still mainly defined by the ethnolinguistic cleavage, the neighbourhood effect was identified for both “Russian” and “Latvian” parties. It was the largest for the Progressive party in 2022, the Development/For! alliance in 2018 and the Greens and Farmers Union in 2011.

Key Words:

electoral geography, spatial analysis, voting behaviour, Saeima, spatial lag

¹ research fellow, Center for Spatial Analysis in International Relations, Institute for International Studies, MGIMO-University

Introduction

Although ethnolinguistic cleavage remains the main factor of electoral behavior in Latvia, the country's political system is currently transforming due to the fragmentation of the Russian-speaking electoral field. At the 2022 Saeima elections the Harmony party, a long-standing monopolist of the Russian-speaking votes with a largest Saeima faction, failed to cope with acute competition and did not pass to the parliament. As a result, a large Russian-speaking community is currently represented in the Saeima by a relatively small faction of a new For Stability! party that is even less capable to influence government policies.

These circumstances increase the importance of analyzing other voting factors, whose significance may later increase. These include the neighborhood effect, i.e., the support for a party in a certain region being influenced by the support in the neighboring regions. The article studies the neighborhood effect at the Latvian parliamentary elections in the years 2010-2022.

The research aims at measuring the significance of the neighborhood effect in the electoral support for Latvian parties at the Saeima elections over the studied period. In order to do that, the results of the classical regression model of the voting for parliamentary parties broken down by municipalities are compared with the autoregressive model that takes into account the spatial lag, i.e. the support for the party in the neighboring regions. If accounting for spatial lag increases the explanatory power of the model, it attests to the existence of the neighborhood effect.

The Electoral System of the Latvian Republic

The Latvian unicameral parliament called the Saeima is elected every four years in five electoral districts (Riga, Kurzeme, Vidzeme, Zemgale and Latgale) with a 5% threshold². The indexes of the effective number of parties attest to the increasing fragmentation of the party system (Golosov 2010, 188). Based on the results of the 2022 election, the Laakso-Taagepera index reached 11,8, meaning that apart from the seven parliamentary factions five more parties have a considerable impact on the party system. The Golosov index amounts to 5,4, which is also quite high. It is lower because it leaves out of the consideration those parties that were strongly lagging behind the winner of the election. At the 2018 election the Laakso-Taagepera index was lower – 8,4 (which is still quite high), so its growth indicates the steep increase in fragmentation, which can be linked to the fragmentation of the Russian-speaking party landscape in 2022. And the Golosov index in 2018 was slightly higher (5,8), which can be, probably, explained by the turmoil around the leader of the election that is central to this index: in 2022 the long-lasting leader of

² Saeimas vēlēšanu likums (22.01.2022 red.) Accessed 06.06.2023. <https://likumi.lv/doc.php?id=35261>.

the election – the Harmony party – could not overcome the 5% threshold, and the overall gap between the new frontrunner and other parties decreased.

The ethnolinguistic cleavage between the Russian-speaking and the Latvian population remains the main characteristic of the Latvian political system and electoral behaviour. The party landscape is still clearly divided into the “Latvian” and the “Russian”, and over the last decade only few political powers managed to attract both Latvian and non-Latvian voters (Zhirnova 2022, 154). In case of the Latvian party system the ethnolinguistic divide in fact replaced a more traditional division into the left and the right. The label of the left or the centre-left parties usually stands not for an alternative socio-economic agenda, but for the “Russian” parties, whereas the “Latvian” parties are usually referred to as right or centre-right (Vorotnikov 2018, 85; Ikstens, Balcere 2019, 258).

Although Russian speakers account for about a third of the Latvian population³, the electorate of the “Russian” parties is considerably limited by the alien (non-citizen) status. After the restoration of independence, the Latvian government refused to grant citizenship to those permanent residents, whose ancestors had not lived in Latvia before 1940, giving them alien passports instead and depriving them of the right to vote at any level. Usually those were the Russian speakers who had moved to Latvia in the Soviet times and their descendants. Although the alien status was initially introduced as a temporary one, nowadays every tenth Latvian is an alien. Consequently, Russian speakers account for only about a quarter of Latvian citizens, considerably less than the overall proportion of the population⁴.

The representatives of the “Russian” parties Harmony and For Stability! occasionally speak in favour of changing the voting system from the proportional to the majority electoral system (examples include the interview of the former Harmony leader J. Jānis Urbanovičs⁵, the electoral programme of For Stability!⁶). However, such a transformation will increase the geographic favouritism of the electoral system, i.e. its inclination towards territorial differentiation, which favours large national and small regional parties (Okunev 2023, 101). In this case the “Russian” parties will be put at a disadvantage and will run the risk of losing even

³ Iedzīvotāju skaits un īpatsvars pēc tautības un valstiskās piederības gada sākumā. Centrālā statistikas pārvalde. Accessed 30.09.2021. <https://stat.gov.lv/lv/statistikas-temas/iedzivotaji/iedzivotaju-skaits/tabulas/ire060-iedzivotaju-skaits-un-ipatsvars-pec>.

⁴ 60,8 % Latvijas iedzīvotāju dzimtā valoda ir latviešu. Centrālā statistikas pārvalde. Accessed 30.09.2021. <https://www.csb.gov.lv/lv/statistika/statistikas-temas/iedzivotaji/meklet-tema/2747-608-latvijas-iedzivotaju-dzimta-valoda-ir-latviesu>.

⁵ Krautmanis M. Jānis Urbanovičs: Varu tautai! Neatkarīgā Rīta Avīze. 24.10.2014. Accessed 06.06.2023. <https://nra.lv/politika/127735-janis-urbanovics-varu-tautai.htm>

⁶ Politiska partija Stabilitātei! Priekšvēlēšanu programma: Latvijas Vestnesis. Accessed 06.06.2023. <https://www.vestnesis.lv/op/2022/175.24>.

the current unimpressive representation, because the Russian speaking voters do not outnumber the Latvians in any of the electoral districts.

Previous Research

The neighbourhood effect in elections, when the support for a party is likely to be higher in the regions surrounded by those regions where the support for the party is high, was conceptualized back in 1969 in the works of D.R. Reynolds (1969) and K.R. Cox (1969). Several decades later its significance was proved on a local level in an experiment by R. Huckfeldt and J. Sprague (1995). However, it was not until lately when the development of computer technologies and geoinformation systems allowed to evaluate the neighbourhood effect on a nationwide level using spatial analysis, namely, spatial autoregression. This instrument was employed by I. Okunev (2023, 267) to prove the independent influence of the neighbourhood effect on the outcome of the 2016 US presidential campaign and provide a quantitative estimate of this effect. In this study I. Okunev's methodology is applied to Latvia.

Such an approach of measuring neighbourhood effect has not yet been applied to Latvian elections, although the Latvian electoral system is regularly studied both in Latvia and abroad. As a rule, researchers focus on the ethnolinguistic cleavage as the main characteristic of Latvia's social and political structure.

For instance, the main territorial cleavages are described in a large chapter devoted to the Latvian electoral system in the book from the Modern Electoral Systems series published under the auspice of the Russian Central Electoral Commission. The authors of the chapter N. Mezhevich and A. Solopenko (2021) state that territorial cleavages of the voting behaviour mainly replicate the uneven settlement of the main two ethnolinguistic groups. The Russian speakers, who rather predictably support the "Russian" parties that appeal to them, mostly live in the capital and other large cities as well as Latgale, a region bordering on Russia and Belarus and enjoying cultural and economic specificity. The votes for the "Russian" parties are dispensed accordingly, concentrating primarily in Riga and Latgale. The urban-rural cleavage between polyethnic cities and primarily Latvian countryside is also in place, with ethnic Latvians in cities and in villages tending to support different parties.

A comparative study of electoral cleavages in Latvia, Lithuania, Estonia, Russia and Ukraine aiming at finding regions of electoral anomalies also indicated that in Latvia such a region is Latgale with a significant non-Latvian population and strong support for "Russian" parties (Meleshevich 2006, p. 119). However, a closer study of Latgalian municipalities (Paiders 2014) could not find any considerable changes in the voting behaviour closer to the Russian or the Belorussian border. The

ethnolinguistic factor and the appeal of specific charismatic candidates proved to be of greater importance.

To sum up, most studies view territorial cleavages of the voting behaviour in Latvia as a reflection of the social structure. This article supplements this approach by considering the spatial structure of the society, i.e., the neighbourhood effect.

Data and Method

The research is based on the official result of the parliamentary elections in Latvia over the five latest electoral cycles (2010, 2011, 2014, 2018 and 2022)⁷. The data is analyzed on a municipal level. From 2009 to 2021 Latvia was administratively divided into 119 municipalities, so the Central Electoral Commission provided the voting data for this division. The results of the 2022 elections were published according to the new administrative division with 43 municipalities.

Apart from the parliamentary parties the results of the Latvian Russian Union were included in the study. Despite the fact that it did not manage to get to Saeima over the studied period, it retained its importance for the Russian-speaking community and both the municipal and European representation.

Ethnolinguistic statistics are taken from the 2011 census⁸, because it was the last time, when the Central Statistical Bureau of Latvia provided the data on the proportion of the Russian-speaking citizens in municipalities. Only the proportion of Russian residents in regions is available for the later period, however, it appears unsuitable for the needs of the research, because it includes aliens who have no right to vote. Besides for Latvia the cleavage between Latvians and Russian-speakers is more relevant than that with ethnic Russians (Simonyan 2022, 145). Ethnicity is a relatively stable characteristic, so the 2011 data can be used with certain caution. Of course, all ethnolinguistic statistics are relative rather than precise, but they can help to shape the understanding of the key characteristics of the studied population.

To check the hypothesis about the importance of the neighbourhood effect for the electoral behaviour in Latvia, the spatial autoregressive model (SAR) is employed, adding the spatial lag, i.e. the average value of the dependent variable in the neighbouring regions. If adding the spatial lag increases the explanatory power of the regression model (R-squared), it allows to suggest that the neighbourhood effect

⁷ Saeimas vēlēšanas. Centrālā vēlēšanu komisija. Accessed 08.06.2023. <https://www.cvk.lv/lv/saeimas-velesanas>.

⁸ Latvijas 2011. gada tautas skaitīšanas rezultāti. Centrālā statistikas pārvalde. Accessed 03.03.2021 <https://stat.gov.lv/lv/statistikas-temas/iedzivotaji/iedzivotaju-skaitis/publikacijas-un-infografikas/1299-latvijas-2011>.

is a significant variable with an independent influence on the election outcome (Okunev 2023a, 258).

The dependent variable in the study is the voting results of parliamentary parties in the five latest electoral cycles. The main independent variable is the percentage of the Russian-speaking citizens in the municipalities. Both regression models – the classical (CL) and the spatial lag (SAR) – were computed using the GeoDa software (the detailed manual can be found here: Okunev 2023b, 220-226). The results are represented in Table 1. Three parameters are shown for each calculation: the R-squared, the Akaike information criterion and the logarithmic likelihood. The two latter figures allow to compare the quality of the classical and the spatial regression models: the higher logarithmic likelihood and lower Akaike criterion indicate higher quality of a model (Okunev 2023a, 261). The final table includes only those results, when the p-value of F-statistics, accounting for the overall quality of the model, the p-value the Lagrange multiplier, indicating whether the spatial autoregression can be used, as well as the p-value each of each variable less than 0,05, which is an acceptable significance level for social sciences.

The Results of the Regression Analysis

As the Table 1 shows, in all cases with an acceptable statistical mistake, accounting for the spatial lag, i.e. the support for the party in the neighbouring municipalities, increased the explanatory power of the regression model, indicating the neighbourhood effect. Moreover, the autoregressive models were of higher quality as they had higher log-likelihood and lower Akaike criterion.

The strongest neighbourhood effect was found in the support of the centre-left Progressive party in 2022, the year of its debut at the Saeima elections, when it got 6,16% and 10 parliamentary seats. The results of the party weakly correlate with the number of Russian-speaking citizens in the region (R-squared 0,156), such a regression model cannot be used for analysis. However, adding the spatial lag increases the explanatory power by 0,36 to 0,539, which shows weak dependence, but makes the model suitable for use.

Table 1.

Classical (CL) and spatial lag (SAR) regression models of the Saeima election results in 2010-2022 (empty cell: a high p-value, crossed cell: the party did not participate in the election).

Parties		2010		2011		2014		2018		2022	
		CL	SAR	CL	SAR	CL	SAR	CL	SAR	CL	SAR
Harmony	R-squared	0,919	0,928	0,954	0,958	0,942	0,945	0,951	0,955	0,920	0,938
	Log-lik.	-336	-330	-443	-414	-298	-295	-275	-270	-63	-58
	Akaike	677	667	891	834	600	597	555	547	130	122
Latvian Russian Union	R-squared									0,827	0,843
	Log-lik.									-68	-67
	Akaike									140	139
New Unity	R-squared	0,573	0,718	0,484	0,718	0,152	0,319			0,500	0,720
	Log-lik.	-393	-371	-338	-307	-359	-350			-126	-115
	Akaike	790	750	679	620	723	705			255	236
Greens and Farmers Union	R-squared	0,447	0,601	0,207	0,539	0,360	0,634			0,091	0,345
	Log-lik.	-398	-382	-374	-348	-414	-387			-144	-139
	Akaike	801	771	751	702	832	780			297	284
For a Good Latvia / Latvia First	R-squared	0,151	0,229								
	Log-lik.	-287	-283								
	Akaike	578	571								
National Alliance	R-squared	0,429	0,608	0,494	0,769	0,501	0,784	0,435	0,610		
	Log-lik.	-260	-241	-320	-280	-341	-298	-305	-287		
	Akaike	525	489	644	565	686	601	614	580		

Zatlers' Reform Party	R-squared			0,697	0,714						
	Log-lik.			-327	-324						
	Akaike			658	654						
Development / For!	R-squared							0,275	0,632	0,092	0,268
	Log-lik.							-306	-273	-120	-117
	Akaike							615	552	245	240
Latvian Regional Alliance/ United List	R-squared					0,142	0,180			0,282	0,413
	Log-lik.					-298	-296			-134	-130
	Akaike					560	598			272	268
Conservatives	R-squared							0,503	0,553		
	Log-lik.							-296	-291		
	Akaike							597	589		
KPV LV	R-squared							0,556	0,698		
	Log-lik.							-316	-297		
	Akaike							636	600		
Stability!	R-squared									0,907	0,917
	Log-lik.									-91	-89
	Akaike									186	184
Progressives	R-squared									0,156	0,516
	Log-lik.									-80	-71
	Akaike									164	147

The neighbourhood effect was almost as strong for the alliance Development/For! In 2018 (R-squared increased from 0,275 to 0,632 by 0,357) and for the Greens and Farmers Union in 2011 (R-squared increased from 0,207 to 0,539 by 0,332). In all these cases accounting for spatial lag helped increase the explanatory power of the models higher than 0,5, which made them applicable for analysis.

As for the “Russian” parties (among the studied those are the Harmony, the Latvian Russian Union and the Stability!), the neighbourhood effect also influenced their support, but it usually did not account for more than few per cent of the dispersion. It is probably linked to the fact that the dispersion of votes for them is mostly explained by the regional proportion of the Russian-speaking citizens (R-squared was more than 0,9 for the Harmony and the Stability! and more than 0,8 for the Latvian Russian Union). However, accounting for the spatial lag when analyzing the voting support for the Harmony in 2011 helped to increase the explanatory power of the model from 0,531 to 0,734 by 0,203..

Conclusion

Spatial autoregression allowed to prove the significance of the neighbourhood effect as an independent factor of the voting behaviour in all the studied electoral cycles. The effect was the strongest for the Progressives in 2022, the Development/For! in 2018 and the Greens and Farmers Union in 2011. The neighbourhood effect influenced the electoral support for the “Russian” parties as well, but for them it was not so strong, which can be explained by the paramount importance of the ethnolinguistic factor for these parties. Accounting for the spatial lag allows to ensure a deeper understanding of the voting mechanisms by adding complementing the analysis of the social structure of the electorate by its spatial characteristics.

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